

Elucidating the role of PAR2 and gender in a novel model of post-traumatic osteoarthritis

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Collaborating establishments:

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Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis has been composed by myself, and that it has not been submitted for a DBS, DProf, EngD, PhD or comparable academic degree award. The work contained within this thesis has been carried out independently at the University of the West of Scotland, University of Glasgow and University of Liverpool.

This thesis is associated with the following paper:

Chapter 3 is based on McCulloch *et al.* (2019). Accelerated post traumatic osteoarthritis in a dual injury murine model. *Osteoarthritis and Cartilage*, 27(12), 1800-1810. The candidate designed and performed all experimental procedures and data analysis with support from technical staff at the University of Liverpool to generate histological sections for cartilage scoring. Chapter 3 was written solely by the candidate, and served as the first draft of the aforementioned paper before editing by contributing authors for publication submission.

Personal details withheld.

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Acknowledgements

Abstract

Background: Post-traumatic osteoarthritis (PTOA) is associated with articular cartilage damage and represents a major clinical challenge due to the poor regenerative capability of cartilage. This study presents the development of a novel and robust dual injury murine model of PTOA, which combines destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) and cartilage scratch. This model results in accelerated OA-like symptoms including enhanced osteophytogenesis. Prior studies in the DMM model have demonstrated that loss of proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) in mice results in significant protection from early OA-like symptoms. For many years it has been recognised that there are significant sex-specific differences in the incidence, prevalence and clinical manifestation of osteoarthritis. Females manifest OA differently from males, with certain areas of the knee being disproportionately affected. However, the reason for, and also mechanisms, contributing to the differences in presentation and progression of OA between sexes have not been extensively investigated.

Methods: OA was induced in male and female C57BL/6 wild-type (WT) mice, as well as male PAR2 and PAR2 Col2 KO mice, via (a) DMM, (b) microblade scratches of articular cartilage (CS) or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS). Mice were culled 7, 14 and 28 days post-surgery. Osteophytogenesis and bone changes were monitored using microcomputed tomography, with cartilage damage and synovitis assessed histologically. Dynamic weight bearing was assessed as an indirect measurement of pain at day 14.

Results: Osteophytogenesis analysis via microCT revealed that osteophytes were present in all groups at days 7 and 14 post-surgery. However, in DCS, osteophytes were visually larger and more numerous when compared with DMM and CS. Histological assessment of cartilage at day 14 and 28, revealed significantly greater damage in DCS compared with DMM and CS. Furthermore, a significant increase in synovitis was observed in DCS. Finally, at day 14 osteophyte numbers correlated with changes in dynamic weight bearing.

Quantification of osteophytes revealed that PAR2^{-/-} mice had significantly smaller osteophytes ($p=0.006$) with less mineralised bone ($p=0.003$). Moreover, analysis of metaphyseal trabecular bone on the operated leg showed a significant decrease in % bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) ($p=0.025$). Assessment of pain-related behaviour, using dynamic weight bearing at day 14, demonstrated that PAR2^{-/-} mice exert less load on their front paws.

Although females show an increase in both osteophyte size and mineralisation (often related with increased pain) they do not display altered biomechanical loading indicative of OA-like pain as observed in males. Positioning of osteophyte formation is observed to differ between males and

females in the DCS model. Male mice present more extensive and severe levels of both subchondral and trabecular osteosclerosis 14 days post-surgery.

Conclusion: Joint destabilisation when combined with simultaneous cartilage injury accelerates joint deterioration, as seen in PTOA. Thus, DCS provides a novel and robust model for investigating multiple pathological hallmarks, including osteophytogenesis, cartilage damage, synovitis and OA-related pain. PAR2 plays a role in accelerated OA-like symptoms (i.e., osteophyte formation) in a dual injury model of OA. Furthermore, the loss of PAR2 decreases pain behaviour suggesting that PAR2 is involved in pain sensing. Taken together, these results support the future exploration of PAR2 as a therapeutic target for PTOA. This study further established that sex-differences are present in OA-pathogenesis. The synergistic effects of dual cartilage injury and joint destabilisation observed in male mice were not observed in females to the same extent. Improving our understanding of the mechanisms underlying sex differences in the pathophysiology of OA is instrumental in the development of effective treatments, with the potential of sex specific strategies and therapeutics.

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Abbreviations

μCT	Microcomputed-tomography
μm	Micrometre
ACL/ACLT	Anterior cruciate ligament/ anterior cruciate ligament transection
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
BMD	Bone mineral density
BV	Bone volume
BV/TV	Bone volume/Tissue volume
Col2	Collagen type II
COX-2	Cyclooxygenase-2
Cre	Cre Recombinase
CRP	C-reactive protein
CS	Cartilage Scratch
DCS	Destabilisation of the medial meniscus and cartilage scratch
DHT	Dihydrotestosterone
DMARDs	Disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs
DMM	Destabilisation of the medial meniscus
DNA	Deoxyribose nucleic acid
ECM	Extracellular matrix
ERK	extracellular signal-regulated kinase
FLS	Fibroblast-like synoviocytes
hPAR2	Human Proteinase-activated receptor 2
HRT	Hormone replacement therapy
IFP	infrapatellar fat pad
IGF-1	Insulin-like growth factor 1
IL-1(β)	Interleukin-1 (beta)
IL-6	Interleukin-6
MMP	Matrix metalloproteinases
MMTL	Medial meniscotibial ligament
MSCs	Mesenchymal stem cells
OA	Osteoarthritis
ORX	Orchiectomised
OVX	Ovariectomised
PAR2	Proteinase-activated receptor 2
PAR2 Col2 KO	Proteinase-activated receptor 2 Collagen type II KO
PAR2 F/F	Proteinase-activated receptor 2 Flox
PAR2 KO	Proteinase-activated receptor 2 knock-out
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PGE2	Prostaglandin E2
PTOA	Post-traumatic osteoarthritis
RA	Rheumatoid arthritis
RANKL	Receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand
ROI/VOI	Region of Interest / Volume of Interest

siRNA	Small interfering Ribonucleic acid
TGF- β	Transforming growth factor beta
TNF- α	Tumour necrosis factor alpha
TRP	Transient receptor potential channels
TV	Tissue Volume
WT	Wild-Type

Chapter 1

Literature Review

1.1. Introduction

Synovial joints are the most common type of movable joint in the body, and are comprised of various different types of tissues: synovium, cartilage, bone, meniscus, ligaments and fat pad.

1.1.1. Synovium

The synovial membrane is comprised of smooth connective tissue and surrounds the joint, secreting synovial fluid into the synovial cavity. The synovial membrane can be divided into two layers: the intima (inner layer) and sub intima (outer layer). There are two cell types present within the intima: fibroblast-like synoviocytes (FLS) responsible for producing hyaluronic acid and lubricin (Jay, Harris and Cha, 2001; Yamanishi and Firestein, 2001), and macrophage-like synovial cells, responsible for removing debris from the synovial fluid via phagocytosis.

1.1.2. Cartilage

Articular cartilage is a unique connective tissue present on the surface of bones, functioning to 'cushion' the joints as it helps with lubrication and joint loading. Adult cartilage is comprised of 3 zones: superficial, middle and deep (Grogan et al., 2013) made up of extracellular matrix (ECM) containing collagenous and non-collagenous proteins (Glyn-Jones et al., 2015) with chondrocytes embedded throughout. The outer superficial zone contains un-calcified hyaline cartilage and provides a frictionless surface. Underneath this hyaline cartilage is calcified cartilage which forms a complex with the subchondral bone acting to absorb force through the joint to protect the underlying bone (Oegema et al., 1997). Chondrocytes are the only cell type present in the cartilage. They are encapsulated in lacunae and embedded in the ECM, which is comprised of water, aggrecan and type II collagen (Khan, Williams and Archer, 2009). Chondrocytes differentiate from mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) and begin to secrete aggrecan and type II collagen, forming the ECM (Zuscik et al., 2008) As chondrocytes proliferate, they become flattened, and form columns. In response to biomechanical and chemical stimulation chondrocytes function to regulate the cartilage structure and integrity (Buckwalter, Mankin and Grodzinsky, 2005). During injury, chondrocytes are

unable to migrate and proliferate to repair tissue damage, therefore cartilage has very little to no regenerative capacity (Tew et al., 2001). As cartilage is an avascular and aneural tissue, chondrocytes receive both nutrients and chemical signals from the synovial fluid, as well as the subchondral bone.

1.1.3. Bone

Bone is a hard, dense connective tissue that provides support and protection within the body (Robling, Castillo and Turner, 2006). It is comprised of two types of mineralised tissue: cortical bone and trabecular bone. Cortical bone forms the hard exterior and has a smooth, white appearance. Trabecular bone constitutes the inner layer of bone and has a honeycomb-like structure. Each end of a long bone is known as the epiphysis which consists of cancellous bone filled with red marrow. The epiphysis joins the diaphysis at the metaphysis. The metaphysis contains the epiphyseal growth plate, a layer of hyaline cartilage present in growing bones that is replaced by osseous tissue in older bones and is referred to as the epiphyseal line. Other tissues such as endosteum, periosteum and bone marrow reside within the bone. Subchondral bone is the layer of bone lying distal to calcified cartilage (Burr and Gallant, 2012; Madry, van Dijk and Mueller-Gerbl, 2010) and acts as a shock absorber in weight-bearing joints. Vessels present in the subchondral bone provide over half of the oxygenation, hydration and glucose for the overlying cartilage (Findlay and Kuliwaba, 2016). Subchondral bone can be divided into the subchondral bone plate and subchondral trabecular bone (Goldring and Goldring, 2010). The subchondral bone plate lies directly under the articular cartilage and is a thin cortical lamella (Milz and Putz, 1994). It contains both arterial and venous vessels, and nerves that permeate through the channels and branch onto the overlying calcified cartilage (Holmdahl and Ingelmark, 1950; Madry, van Dijk and Mueller-Gerbl, 2010). The subchondral trabecular bone arises from the bone plate. The trabeculae provide the shock-absorbing property of bone. Similar to the subchondral bone trabeculae contains blood vessels and nerves; however it is more porous, metabolically active and contains bone marrow. Various cell types are present in bone tissue (Buckwalter et al., 1996). Osteoblasts, derived from mesenchymal cells and found on the surface of osteons (the main structural unit of cortical bone), are responsible for bone synthesis and

mineralisation (Capulli, Paone and Rucci, 2014). Osteoclasts, responsible for the break down and absorption of bone, can be found in small cavities on the bone surface known as 'Howship's lacunae' (Teitelbaum, 2000). Osteocytes are the most abundant cell type residing in the lacunae of mature bone (Franz-Odenaal, Hall and Witten, 2006). They are important for communication and regulation, and are formed when osteoblasts become 'trapped' within the bone matrix they secrete (Capulli, Paone and Rucci, 2014). Bones are connected to other bones by fibrous connective tissue known as ligaments, comprised of fibrocytes and bundles of collagenous fibres.

1.2. Osteoarthritis

Osteoarthritis (OA) is globally the most prevalent musculoskeletal disease (Brooks, 2006), with 80% of the population >65 years of age showing radiological evidence of OA (Lawrence et al., 2008). In the UK between 2007 and 2008 over 140,000 primary hip and knee replacements were performed, with an addition of more than 10,000 revision arthroplasties. This represents an NHS cost burden in excess of £1billion per year (de Verteuil et al., 2008). OA is characterised by significant structural changes in joint tissues such as articular cartilage degradation, osteophyte formation (bony outgrowths), subchondral osteosclerosis, epiphyseal bone expansion, synovitis and pannus formation (Figure 1.1). What was once considered a 'wear and tear' disease is now recognised as a complex disorder involving various molecular pathways and inflammatory mediators (Goldring and Goldring, 2007). Clinical diagnosis of OA is difficult due to the lack of plausible biomarkers, gradual onset, unknown aetiology and extreme disease heterogeneity between patients. Standard diagnostic procedures include clinical examination, radiography and also magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (McGonagle et al., 2010).

Risk factors linked to OA include gender, obesity, genetic factors, and joint injury, and although often associated with increasing age, an accelerated OA progression is recognised in individuals suffering previous (often sport-related) joint injury involving multi-tissue damage. Notably, 66% of patients presenting with articular surface damage in their joints progressed towards OA (Curl et al., 1997; Hjelle et al., 2002). Furthermore, current data suggests that patients with chronic OA who suffered

an earlier articular trauma are, upon diagnosis, >10 years younger than those patients with no history of joint injury (Punzi et al., 2016). Taken together, post-traumatic OA (PTOA), as characterised by accelerated joint degeneration, pain and dysfunction, accounts for ~12% of all OA cases (Buckwalter, 2003).

Figure 1.1. Osteoarthritic joint changes. Image illustrating (A) characteristic structures in a normal healthy joint and (B) characteristic changes of an OA-affected knee joint including: osteophyte formation; subchondral osteosclerosis; cartilage degradation; synovitis and pannus formation. Image adapted from (McCulloch et al., 2018).

1.2.1. Pathogenesis of Osteoarthritis

OA is now recognised as a disease of the whole joint (McGonagle et al., 2010) and can be classified as primary or secondary OA. Primary, also referred to as idiopathic OA, affects joints of one site and is primarily associated with aging. Secondary OA occurs in response to an injury (e.g. ACL and meniscal tears). Various tissues in the joint are involved and become altered during the pathogenesis of OA.

1.2.1.1. Cartilage

In OA research, cartilage has been the main focus. Cartilage damage is known to accelerate disease progression (van der Kraan and van den Berg, 2012), and therefore injury to this tissue represents a major clinical challenge. In athletes with ACL ruptures there is a 20-60% rate of both chondral and osteochondral defects leading to a 12 fold increase in OA development (Mithoefer et al., 2009). In healthy cartilage terminal differentiation of chondrocytes is inhibited (van der Kraan and van den Berg, 2012), however, in OA it is believed terminal differentiation is not blocked and results in cellular hypertrophy (van der Kraan and van den Berg, 2012). A hypertrophic-like phenotype in chondrocytes correlates with cartilage damage severity in both experimental and human OA (Gratal et al., 2019). Col10 is considered a marker for chondrocyte hypertrophy, and is not expressed in healthy chondrocytes (van der Kraan and van den Berg, 2012). In OA, cartilage expresses col2 at both protein and mRNA levels (Brew et al., 2010). Runt-related transcription factor 2 (*Runx2*) plays a role in hypertrophic differentiation of chondrocytes, with *Runx2* expression observed to be upregulated in human OA cartilage (Wang et al., 2004). OA severity, as well as col10 and MMP-13 expression is decreased in *Runx2* KO mice (Kamekura et al., 2006). Toll-like receptors (TLRs) are involved in the innate immunity. TLR-2 and TLR-4 are significantly increased in OA cartilage lesions leading to the induction of various catabolic responses that could potentially impact upon other tissues in the joint (Kim et al., 2006). In adults, healthy articular cartilage is avascular (Moses, Sudhalter and Langer, 1990) with a poor regenerative capability. However, vascularisation of the articular cartilage is characteristic of OA pathology with growth of blood vessels from the subchondral bone into the

articular cartilage thought to facilitate OA progression (Walsh, 2004). Animal models have shown an increase in angiogenesis in the subchondral bone during the early stages of OA and, with increasing severity, progression to vascular invasion of the osteochondral junction (Ashraf, Mapp and Walsh, 2011; Mapp et al., 2008; Saito et al., 2012). In humans, blood vessels are known to breach the tidemark in the proximal tibial articular cartilage in patients with OA.

1.2.1.2. Bone

In patients with OA the subchondral bone differs from that of 'healthy' individuals (Weinans et al., 2012). There is a transfer in load to the subchondral bone when the cartilage becomes damaged (Neogi et al., 2010). This load transfer, combined with the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines is thought to contribute to the development of osteosclerosis and other bone remodelling present in the joint (Bellido et al., 2010; Henrotin, Pessesse and Sanchez, 2012). Subchondral bone increases in density and thickness in OA known as subchondral sclerosis, a radiographic hallmark of OA (Donell, 2019). Previous studies have suggested subchondral bone thickening occurs prior to cartilage degradation (Li et al., 2013). Before the development of OA there can be an increased rate in subchondral bone turnover (Huebner et al., 2014). It is thought damage to the knee joint surface in OA causes micro-fractures that are then in a constant state of repair resulting in the production of various enzymes and cytokines that affect the overlying cartilage (Roemer et al., 2010b).

1.2.1.3. Osteophytes

Osteophytes are bony outgrowths (spurs) capped with fibrocartilage. In OA, osteophyte formation is one of the main radiographic features of the disease (Kellgren and Lawrence, 1957). The type of osteophyte is dependent upon the positioning of the spur within the joint. Marginal osteophytes are caused by endochondral ossification stimulated via vascularisation of the subchondral bone marrow, and arise from the periphery of joints usually on one side. Central osteophytes project into the joint space, caused by hyper-vascularity stimulating endochondral ossification. These osteophytes are most commonly found in the hips and knees. Alternatively, osteophytes are classed as 'traction',

'inflammatory' and 'real' spurs (Menkes and Lane, 2004). Traction spurs form at the insertion site of ligaments and tendons. Inflammatory spurs occur at the insertion site of ligaments and tendons to bone. In OA, real spurs (chondro-osteophytes) are the most prevalent and form at the junction between bone and cartilage overlying the bone. MSCs present in the periosteum and synovial lining are believed to be osteophyte precursor cells. Developing osteophytes contain fibroblasts, mesenchymal pre-chondrocytes, hypertrophic chondrocytes and osteoblasts (van der Kraan and van den Berg, 2007). Cells within the bone-cartilage boundary become stimulated to proliferate and undergo chondrogenesis, depositing aggrecan and other matrix molecules in the tissues. Fibroblast-like cells cover the developing osteophyte and further differentiate into chondrocytes. Expression of different types of collagen allow the differentiation stages to be recognised (Aigner et al., 1995). The most central chondrocytes become hypertrophic and then undergo endochondral ossification. The fully developed osteophyte is then integrated with the original subchondral bone expanding the joint surface area, with the surface being covered by a layer of cartilage. Various factors are known to be involved in osteophyte formation, Transforming-Growth Factor Beta (TGF- β) is one of the most potent factor to stimulate chondrogenesis in developing osteophytes (Uchino et al., 2000; van Beuningen et al., 1994), and has been shown to be expressed by human osteophytes (Uchino et al., 2000). In osteophytogenesis, Bone Morphogenetic Protein 2 (BMP-2) is essential in chondrocytic differentiation and endochondral ossification. Developing osteophytes in mice express Insulin-like Growth Factor I (IGF-I), with both IGF-I and IGF-1 receptor co-expressed by chondrocytes, proliferating perichondral cells and osteoblasts (Okazaki et al., 1999).

1.2.1.4. Synovium

Although not considered predominantly an inflammatory disease, OA has been recognised to present with a strong inflammatory component which contributes to disease pathogenesis via the presence of pro-inflammatory cytokines exerting pathological changes on tissues of the joint. There is increasing evidence that synovial tissue is an important contributor in OA development (Scanzello and Goldring, 2012). Histological features consistent with synovitis have been observed in synovium

from OA patients (Farahat et al., 1993; Goldenberg, Egan and Cohen, 1982; Haraoui et al., 1991; Smith et al., 1997) as well as expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Farahat et al., 1993; Smith et al., 1997), and more recently our group have reported considerable heterogeneity of various inflammatory indices in OA synovia (Tindell et al., 2012). Indeed knee arthroscopic studies of OA patients found synovial inflammation to be associated with OA structural severity (Walsh et al., 2009), whilst another study reported that serum C-reactive protein levels in early osteoarthritis predicted likely progressive disease (Spector et al., 1997a); CRP also correlates significantly with disease joint count and radiographic score in OA (Punzi et al., 2005). Supported by previous findings (Jackson et al., 2014), our group have previously detected histologically the presence of synovitis at 14 days post-surgery (Huesa et al., 2016). Along with inflammatory cytokines, growth factors also contribute to OA pathogenesis e.g. TGF- β and Nerve growth factor (NGF). TGF- β , as mentioned previously, plays an important role in OA disease progression. TGF- β activity is increased in the synovial fluid taken from OA patients (Blom et al., 2004), and has the ability to act as a chemoattractant recruiting fibroblasts to the synovium resulting in the formation of fibrotic tissue (Bakker et al., 2001; van Beuningen et al., 1994). In an experimental model of OA intra-articular injection of activated recombinant TGF- β induces proliferation of synovial lining cells, deposition of the ECM and disrupts the apoptotic process and results in hyperplasia and synovial tissue expansion (Bakker et al., 2001; van Beuningen et al., 1994). TGF- β also promotes the production of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 and TNF- α by synovial lining cells (Scanzello and Goldring, 2012). NGF levels are increased in synovial fluid from OA patients (Aloe et al., 1992). Histopathologic analysis indicated patients with advanced OA presenting with severe synovitis also presented with increased levels of synovial NGF (Stoppiello et al., 2014), thus highlighting the role of NGF in OA pathogenesis.

1.2.1.5. Ligaments

Ligaments are fibrous connective tissue that attach bone to bone, functioning to stabilise the joint and protect the tissues within. Ligaments are poorly vascularised resulting in reduced healing and regenerative properties. Various cell types are present in ligament tissue such as fibroblasts, endothelial cells, synovial cells and chondrocytes (Doroski, Brink and Temenoff, 2007; Laurencin et al., 1999; Lin, Cardenas and Soslowsky, 2004; Vunjak-Novakovic et al., 2004). The ECM in the ligament is mainly composed of collagen, with collagen type II being the most abundant (Benjamin et al., 2006). Collagen type III and V are also present, as well as glycoproteins, proteoglycans, cells and water. Fibroblasts are important players in ligament strength as they synthesise and maintain the ECM (Wang, 2006). The ability of ligaments to hold extreme tensile forces as well as their attachment to bones and association with the synovium within joints provides rationale for the role of ligaments in the initiation of early disease OA. It has previously been demonstrated changes in the ACL precede cartilage damage in the Dunkin-Hartley spontaneous OA model (Quasnichka, Anderson-MacKenzie and Bailey, 2006). The development of OA in humans is directly correlated with severe ligament injury (Louboutin et al., 2009).

1.2.1.6. Meniscus

Some synovial joints (such as the knee) contain fibrocartilage structures known as menisci, which are responsible for load dispersal and provide stability (Aagaard and Verdonk, 1999; Messner and Gao, 1998). The composition of the meniscus is similar to ligaments in that it is composed of fibrocartilage material as well as lacking a vasculature. Excision of the meniscus in OA accelerates joint damage (Lanzer and Komenda, 1990; Yeow et al., 2008). Meniscal extrusion also contributes to joint space narrowing observed in the OA joint (Adams et al., 1999), and stimulates a cascade of events that leads to an increase in disease pathology (e.g. cartilage thinning and subchondral bone formation) (Adams et al., 1999; McGonagle et al., 2010).

1.2.1.7. Pain

The origin of pain in OA patients is poorly understood, however it is one of the most common and physically limiting symptoms. Various factors could contribute to pain experienced by patients suffering from OA, although there is lack of a general consensus regarding the exact cause/origin of OA pain. Changes in bone could potentially contribute to OA-linked pain (Glyn-Jones et al., 2015), for example osteophytes have been shown to positively correlate with knee pain experienced by OA patients (Boegard et al., 1998). However, a later study found osteophyte formation did not relate to pain severity in OA (Sengupta et al., 2006). Strassle and colleagues (2010) have also shown the inhibition of osteoclast activity in OA patients during early disease stage resulted in a significant decrease in pain, although this alleviation in pain was not observed in late stage of OA development. Given that synovitis leads to heightened pain sensitivity in knee OA (Neogi et al., 2016); the synovium has been of interest when investigating OA-related pain. Possible mechanisms include various pro-inflammatory factors secreted into the joint space from cells in the synovium. Similarly, the infrapatellar fat pad (IFP) is known to secrete inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 (Ushiyama et al., 2003) as well as being a source of neuro-inflammatory mediators responsible for pain sensitisation regulation (Bohnsack et al., 2005). As previously mentioned, elevated levels of NGF are found in human synovial fluid obtained from OA patients (Aloe et al., 1992). Targeting NGF has been found to provide effective pain relief (Miller, Block and Malfait, 2017) with anti-NGF therapy exhibiting a significant decrease in pain experienced by OA patients (Seidel et al., 2010). NGF receptors are significantly increased in mice with OA (DMM model) displaying pain-related behaviour (Driscoll et al., 2016).

1.3. Animal Models of OA

Clinical studies in humans investigating the pathophysiology of OA development provide many challenges such as: unique presentation of the disease in each patient; long-term development due to the chronic nature of OA; strict ethical issues surrounding human test subjects. Therefore, animal models of OA, while not fully recapitulating the exact disease development observed in humans,

allow for the study of disease time-course and pathogenesis that would not be possible to investigate in human subjects.

1.3.1 Spontaneous mouse models

Spontaneous models are utilised in the investigation of primary OA, and are considered the hallmark model as they closely resemble the slow natural progression of human OA (Bendele, 2001; Lampropoulou-Adamidou et al., 2014; McCoy, 2015). A disadvantage of spontaneous models is the length of time taken for OA to develop as animals are required to reach skeletal maturity. For example, OA develops in the Dunkin-Hartley guinea pig at 3 months of age, however is not considered to reach skeletal maturity until 6 months (Jimenez et al., 1997; Poole et al., 2010).

1.3.2. Chemically-induced mouse models

Chemically-induced OA models require articular injection of agents into the knee joint that induce inflammation and/or tissue toxicity/damage. Collagenase and sodium monoiodoacetate are examples of compounds used in these models. Administration of collagenase causes the breakdown of type I collagen in the cartilage, leading to decreased collagen matrix in both ligaments and tendons resulting in instability of the joint (Moskowitz, 2007; van Osch et al., 1996a). Monoiodoacetate is an inhibitor of glyceraldehyde-3-phosphatase resulting in cellular glycolysis disruption, and eventually cell death (Sabri and Ochs, 1971; van der Kraan et al., 1989). Chondrocytic cell death leads to cartilage degeneration and subsequent alterations in subchondral bone (Guingamp et al., 1997; Janusz et al., 2001). A major benefit of chemically-induced models is the avoidance of possible infection as they are less invasive compared with surgical models (described below). However, questions remain as to how well these represent the joint damage seen in OA due to their unique pathophysiology which does not closely correlate to that of human secondary OA (Teeple et al., 2013).

1.3.3. Surgically-induced mouse models

Aseptic techniques are utilised to surgically induce OA in these models. Well known surgically-induced murine models include the anterior cruciate ligament transection (ACLT) and destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) models (Glasson, Blanchet and Morris, 2007). The ACLT model produces more severe OA-like changes within the knee joint, and is favoured for induction in larger animals; the high surgical proficiency required to carry out the procedure is easier in larger joints. The DMM model is favoured in the mouse as it is a less invasive procedure compared to ACLT. A significant advantage of surgical models is the rapid progression and high reproducibility, making them an attractive model for short-term studies. However, while both ACLT and DMM models recapitulate features of OA pathology, these do not arise directly from an initial multi-tissue injury, as occurs in PTOA.

1.3.4. Post-traumatic mouse models

Lapine models used to investigate PTOA resulting from multi-tissue joint injury, usually involve traumatic rupture of the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) and damage of surrounding tissues including the meniscus via mechanical impact on the patellofemoral joint (Christiansen et al., 2015; Fischenich et al., 2015; Fischenich et al., 2017). Non-invasive loading models were developed to imitate PTOA in humans caused by traumatic and/or continuous impact. Many studies have investigated the effect of repetitive impact on animal models (Christiansen et al., 2012; Furman et al., 2007; Ko et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2014). Repetitive loading in mouse knees was first described by Poulet *et al.* in which the authors characterised a mechanical loading model to study the effects of various loading magnitudes and regimes on knee joint health and OA disease progression (Poulet et al., 2011). Single-impact loading models share similarities with repetitive-impact models; however protocols differ according to whether joint dislocation and ligament damage is induced. In contrast with the transient nature of repetitive loading, single-impact models induce permanent mechanical damage similar to surgical models. Loading models have yielded valuable insight into PTOA progression, but involve relatively undefined damage to various joint tissues, with results differing

between groups due to differences in loading protocols (e.g. magnitude and frequency of loading). As well as this, loading models require a significant amount of time to develop PTOA. Therefore, there is a particular gap in the OA field for an accelerated and more defined model recapitulating multiple joint tissue injury observed in human PTOA.

1.3.5. Genetically-modified mouse models

A major advantage of utilising mouse models in the study of OA is the ability to generate genetically-modified (transgenic) mice, which is not yet possible in larger animal models. Transgenic mice involve the manipulation of genes resulting in either the protection or worsening of OA symptoms. By genetically modifying mice potential therapeutic targets can be investigated since these mice provide a powerful research tool to investigate molecular pathways contributing to the risk/development of OA. Use of transgenic murine models have provided invaluable insight into the effect of pro-inflammatory cytokines in OA development and pathogenesis (Little and Hunter, 2013; Moskowitz, 2007). For example, the *STR/ort* murine model develops naturally occurring OA and has been pivotal in understanding the correlation between chondrocyte metabolism and OA disease pathogenesis (Jaeger et al., 2008; Pasold et al., 2013). Advances in research have allowed the development of the *Cre-lox* system, a powerful tool for genetic manipulation *in vivo* providing researchers with the ability to generate conditional KOs to investigate genes of interest in specific tissues and cells. Cre recombinase (Cre) is a tyrosine site-specific recombinase produced from the Cre gene of bacteriophage P1 (Sternberg et al., 1978; Sternberg and Hamilton, 1981; Sternberg et al., 1986). The *Cre-lox* system requires 2 components: Cre recombinase and its recognition site, *LoxP*. Cre is expressed by a promoter that specifically targets the tissue/cell of interest. *LoxP* sites are used in pairs and flank each end of the gene of interest. Cre recognises the 2 directly repeated *LoxP* sites, and mediates the site-specific excision of the flanked DNA ultimately resulting in the inactivation of the gene of interest (Branda and Dymecki, 2004; Meinke et al., 2016; Nagy, 2000)

1.4. Proteinase-activated Receptor 2

Proteases are a group of proteolytic enzymes that are responsible for maintaining the body's homeostasis. They function by cleaving either the ligand or receptor on the cell surface, resulting in the activation/termination of a signal (Ossovskaia and Bunnett, 2004). Disturbance to these enzymes can lead to disease. A family of receptors, known as proteinase-activated receptors (PARs), recognise and respond to serine proteases.

Proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) is 1 of 4 transmembrane G-protein coupled receptors (PAR1-4), and is known to play a role in various aspects of pathologies. Various cells within tissues in the body have been observed to express high levels of PAR2. For example fibroblasts, smooth muscle cells, endothelial cells, epithelial cells in the gastrointestinal tract and lung, chondrocytes, as well as osteoclasts and osteoblasts in the bone (Abraham et al., 2000; Amiable et al., 2009; Ferrell et al., 2010; Georgy et al., 2012; Smith et al., 2004). The function of PAR2 in different tissues varies from the stimulation of smooth muscle cells contraction and relaxation, to the stimulation of cell proliferation (Akers et al., 2000; Bono, Lamarche and Herbert, 1997; Chinni et al., 2000; Saifeddine et al., 1996). PAR2 can stimulate Ca^{2+} release, activating both nitric oxide synthase (al-Ani, Saifeddine and Hollenberg, 1995) and Ca^{2+} -activated potassium channels (McGuire et al., 2002), causing the relaxation of vascular smooth muscle, artery dilation, increased tissue perfusion, and ultimately decreased blood pressure (McGuire, 2004). PAR2 is expressed on afferent neurons and when activated results in substance P release, leading to hyperalgesia production (Dai et al., 2004; Noorbakhsh et al., 2003; Ossovskaia and Bunnett, 2004; Patwardhan et al., 2006).

1.4.1. Signalling and activation

Trypsin, and mast cell tryptase are 2 of several serine proteases that activate PAR2 via the cleavage of its N-terminus (Belham et al., 1996; Molino et al., 1997). These serine proteases are present in the body, and are released during disease and inflammation. Once cleaved, the N-terminus unveils a tethered ligand which binds intramolecularly to the second extracellular loop of the PAR2 receptor

and triggers the constant activation of the receptor. Once activated PAR2 cannot be reused, the receptor becomes internalised leading to its degradation.

PAR2 activation (figure 1.2) results in the induction of two pathways, canonical G-protein signalling and β -arrestin-dependant signalling (Rothmeier and Ruf, 2012). The activation of the canonical G-protein signalling pathways is dependent on PAR2 being coupled to G-protein α subunits ($G\alpha_i$, $G\alpha_q/11$ and $G\alpha_{12/13}$), which allow the regulation of the G-protein dependent pathway. If induced via β -arrestin adaptor protein, connected to the PAR2 receptor at the carboxyl terminal, this results in the activation of the G-protein independent pathway (DeFea et al., 2000; Seatter et al., 2004).

Figure 1.2. PAR2 activation and cell cycle. PAR2 is activated via the cleavage of its N terminus by serine proteases. This unveils a novel N terminus which binds to the 2nd extracellular loop as a 'tethered ligand' and induces activation which results in initiation of cell signalling pathways via a G-protein. Once the G-protein is uncoupled, β -arrestin binds in its place, negatively regulating the signalling and promoting clatherrin action. The receptor is then internalised and transported for lysosomal degradation.

1.4.2. PAR2 in OA

PAR2 is accepted to play a role in inflammation, and is widely recognised as playing a part in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) (Crilly et al., 2012a; Crilly et al., 2012b; Ferrell et al., 2003; Kelso et al., 2007). However, only recently has inflammation been regarded as playing a major role in OA.

1.4.2.1 PAR2 in Cartilage

Chondrocytes are the primary source of enzymes responsible for the metabolism of the cartilage matrix in OA (Martel-Pelletier, Welsch and Pelletier, 2001). Pro-inflammatory cytokines synthesised and released by both chondrocytes and the synovial membrane are important in the development and progression of OA as they play a central role in cartilage catabolic processes (Martel-Pelletier, Lajeunesse and Pelletier, 2005). Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) are considered crucial in cartilage catabolism as they collectively have the ability to degrade all components of the ECM (Mott and Werb, 2004). PAR2 has been shown to be present in human OA chondrocytes (Xiang et al., 2006). Moreover, *in vitro* culture of chondrocytes revealed maintenance of PAR2 protein (up to 3 passages) in OA chondrocytes which was lost in “healthy” controls, indicating potential epigenetic alterations in these cells to retain PAR2 expression (Xiang et al., 2006).

Selective activation of PAR2 in chondrocytes mediates a stress-activated protein kinases (SAPK)/p38 and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) 1/2 a signalling cascade, which results in the generation of MMP-1, MMP-13 and cyclooxygenase 2 (COX-2) (Boileau et al., 2007). In OA and RA, MMP-1 and -13 and ADAMTS aggrecanases are strongly associated with the degradation of collagen and aggrecan (Rowan et al., 2008), the main components of the ECM. Moreover, pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and TNF α have been shown to upregulate PAR2 expression in OA chondrocytes (Xiang et al., 2006), and PAR2 appears to regulate the synovial release of IL-1 β , a chondrocyte catabolin (Daheshia and Yao, 2008; Kelso et al., 2007). These findings collectively implicate an important auto-feedback loop between PAR2, inflammation and cartilage destruction.

In the murine destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) model, PAR2 has been identified as a critical checkpoint in the pathogenesis of experimental OA (Ferrell et al., 2010). PAR2 KO mice

exhibited substantially less cartilage damage at 4 weeks post DMM than WT littermates (Ferrell et al., 2010), a key finding confirmed in a later study (Huesa et al., 2016), and across several groups (Amiable et al., 2011; Jackson et al., 2014). At 8 weeks post DMM, WT mice presented with more pronounced joint destruction, however protection against cartilage damage was maintained in the PAR2 KO mice (Ferrell et al., 2010). By using either a PAR2 antagonist, or monoclonal antibody specifically targeting the PAR2 protease cleavage site, inhibition of PAR2 in WT mice was observed to be equally effective as gene deletion in curtailing OA progression *in vivo*, but only in early (1 week) stages of the disease (Ferrell et al., 2010).

To further test the hypothesis that PAR2 drives cartilage damage in the DMM model additional experiments using a viral vector containing human PAR2 (*hPar2*), confirmed that intra-articular injection of *hPar2* restored the pathogenic phenotype in PAR2 KO mice compared to mice injected with a control vector (Huesa et al., 2016). Increased cartilage damage but no significant difference in subchondral bone sclerosis was observed in the hPAR2-transfected PAR2 KO mice compared to vector controls. Jackson and colleagues also demonstrated a significant correlation between cartilage damage and subchondral bone sclerosis (Jackson et al., 2014). The authors concluded that, in the DMM model, even in the absence of subchondral bone sclerosis, cartilage damage is mediated via PAR2 (Huesa et al., 2016). PAR2, through the stimulation of MMPs and various other proteases appears to promote cartilage degradation. It is unknown if the mechanism by which PAR2 deficiency confers protection against cartilage erosion is via inhibition of MMP production or alteration of chondrocyte phenotype. By using chondrocyte conditional PAR2 KO animals, experiments can be designed to further understand how this receptor affects chondrocyte biology *in vivo* in arthritic disease states.

1.4.2.2. PAR2 in Bone

PAR2 is expressed both *in vitro* and *in vivo* by osteoblasts (Abraham et al., 2000). In an inflamed joint there are an increased presence of several PAR2 activators e.g. neutrophil proteinase 3, mast cell tryptase and factor Xa in bone tissue, which results in an increase in bone resorption (Smith et al.,

2004). Human osteoblasts release cytokines in response to PAR2 activation; specifically there is an up-regulation of MMP-1, MMP-9 and IL-1, as well as increased levels of IL-1 β , TNF- α , Prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) (Amiable et al., 2009). PAR2 KO mice present with increased cortical and trabecular bone volumes when compared to WT. In trabecular bone PAR2 KOs have a significantly reduced count of osteoclasts and alkaline-phosphatase colony-forming units in bone marrow cultures, with a decrease in both osteoblast and osteoclast surface and osteoid volume (Georgy et al., 2012). These data would indicate the role of PAR2 activation in the determination of osteoclast and osteoblast lineages residing within the bone marrow and therefore contributing to skeletal growth and bone repair. PAR2 KO mice post-DMM induction present with a gradual increase in subchondral bone, whilst WTs present with significantly decreased trabecular thickness and subchondral bone surface area (Amiable et al., 2011). It has been recently determined that PAR2 plays an essential role in osteophyte formation during DMM progression: although osteophytes are detectable in both WT and PAR2 KO mice, the quantity, size, and growth of osteophytes over time is significantly reduced in PAR2 KO animals. This phenotype was subsequently 'rescued' via intra-articular *Par2* adenovirus transfection (Huesa et al., 2016), which restored the pathogenic phenotype observed in WT animals. This appears to contradict a previous study which found no significant difference in osteophyte formation between WT and PAR2 KO (Jackson et al., 2014). However, the difference in techniques adopted in these studies may explain the conflicting results as the former technique offers far more sensitive measurement of subtle changes to the bone. Current pharmaceutical developments (Cheng et al., 2017) have the potential to provide PAR2 inhibitors which may be useful in protection against osteophytogenesis in OA patients.

1.4.2.3. PAR2 in Synovium

Unlike RA, there are no systemic signs of inflammation or evidence of neutrophils within OA synovial fluid. There is, however, evidence of inflammatory (B and T cell) infiltrate into the synovium (Goldring and Goldring, 2007), together with increased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β and TNF- α) and catabolic proteases (MMPs etc.). These are thought to be instrumental in

chondrocyte mediated cartilage destruction. PAR2 mRNA expression was present in both normal and OA synovial fibroblasts, although expression was increased in OA synovial fibroblasts (Xiang et al., 2006). Tindell *et al.* demonstrated that OA synovitis, scored as synovial thickness and monocyte infiltrate levels, correlated with levels of PAR2 expression in synovial tissue. Whilst synovitis scores were reduced in OA compared to RA, increased PAR2 levels were directly associated with inflammatory conditions across all patient groups. These researchers also demonstrated that a PAR2 antagonist (ENMD-1068) dose-dependently inhibited TNF- α production from OA synovial explant cultures. Increased PAR2 expression in the OA synovia is therefore not merely a passive marker of inflammation but likely an active contributor to pro-inflammatory cytokine production.

1.4.2.4. PAR2 in Pain

There is increasing evidence supporting the role of PARs and their activation during nociceptive signalling and chronic pain development, with PARs being expressed in both astrocytes and neurons. PAR2 is already known to play an important role in tissue injury response, especially inflammation and repair (Déry et al., 1998). Transient receptor potential channels (TRP) are pivotal in both nociceptive modulation and signalling, with the activation of PAR2 resulting in TRP channel sensitisation. Trypsin and tryptase, PAR2 activators, are released from a variety of cell types (e.g. mast cells) and via neurogenic mechanisms promote widespread pro-inflammatory effects (Saifeddine et al., 1996; Seeliger et al., 2003; Steinhoff et al., 2000; Vergnolle et al., 2001).

1.5. Sex-related differences in OA

It has already been shown that women manifest OA differently from males, with certain areas of the knee being disproportionately affected (Felson et al., 1995; Hanna et al., 2009; McAlindon et al., 1992a; O'Connor, 2007) as well as significant differences in the incidence, prevalence and clinical manifestation of osteoarthritis (OA) (Jordan et al., 2007; Jordan et al., 2009; Srikanth et al., 2005). Early onset OA is quickly becoming more common, especially among women who are physically active (e.g. athletes). Along with this, women are more prone to and burdened by knee OA

compared with men (Blagojevic et al., 2010; Felson et al., 1987; Felson et al., 1995; O'Connor, 2006; Srikanth et al., 2005), as well as presenting with greater pain and disability (McAlindon et al., 1992a; O'Connor, 2007; O'Connor and Hooten, 2011; Thomas, Pagura and Kennedy, 2003). Women also report more substantial reductions in both function and quality of life than their male counterparts (Zhang et al., 2010). Interestingly, the incidence of OA in a spontaneous OA murine model is the opposite of humans, with male STR/ort mice presenting with a higher incidence than their female counterparts (Uchida et al., 2012). Male and female STR/ort mice demonstrate sex-related bone architectural differences, which may contribute to the difference in OA incidence. For example differences in internal rotation of the tibia, as well as early decreases in bone mineral density (BMD) and volume of cancellous bone in male mice (Uchida et al., 2012). Various other strains of mice have also demonstrated a higher incidence of spontaneous OA in males (Silberberg and Silberberg, 1963a; Silberberg and Silberberg, 1963b; Sokoloff, 1956). However, this finding is not confined to spontaneous OA models. In both the collagenase (van Osch et al., 1993) and DMM (Ma, 2007 – unpublished data) models, female mice develop less OA than their male counterparts.

The mechanisms underlying the differences in epidemiology, development and pain between men and women with OA are unknown; however, hormonal differences present obvious candidates. Before the age of 50, the prevalence of OA in men is greater than in women (Ma et al., 2007), however, there is an increased risk of OA development amongst post-menopausal women, which has been linked with a reduction in oestrogen. During puberty androgens stimulate periosteal bone growth whilst oestrogens inhibit and thus contributing to a higher bone mass in males (Callewaert et al., 2010), another potential explanation for differential incidence in OA between sexes. Interestingly, oestrogen receptors have been identified in the articular cartilage (Richmond et al., 2000). Although the clinical relevance of these receptors is unknown, they do imply a potential link between articular cartilage and oestrogen. Ovariectomised (OVX) female mice and orchietomised (ORX) male mice present with less severe OA than intact male and female mice (Ma et al., 2007). Treatment of male ORX mice with dihydrotestosterone (DHT) re-established severe OA symptoms. Thus data further

confirming the role of sex hormones in OA. Understanding sex differences in the presentation of pain is extremely complex not only due to the influence of many physiological factors associated with chronic pain, but also psychological aspects (i.e. the perception of pain). For example, many studies have documented an increase in self-assessed pain intensity and decreased functional ability in women ; other studies, however, have shown that in regard to measured functional ability, there are no differences between sexes (Elboim-Gabyzon, Rozen and Laufer, 2012). With 80% of OA drugs being removed from the market due to adverse effects in women (Novicoff and Saleh, 2011; Petterson et al., 2007), clearly there is an immediate need for further research on this sex-related factors – and indeed for sex-based treatment for OA be implemented based on such research, as has recently been recommended (Borkhoff et al., 2008; Katz et al., 1994; MacDonald et al., 2008; O'Connor and Hooten, 2011; Suarez-Almazor et al., 2005).

1.6. Hypotheses

The central hypothesis of this thesis was that post-traumatic OA (PTOA) leads to accelerated pathogenesis. This was investigated in the current study by development of a novel murine model of PTOA; this involved inducing concomitant damage to the cartilage and knee joint destabilisation. Once validated, this model was then used to address the experimental hypotheses that PAR2 has a key role in the accelerated disease progression in PTOA. A related but further hypothesis test was that even though women are more prone to osteoarthritis with age than males, this gender differential does not apply to early OA pathology.

1.7. Aims

The following aims will address the hypotheses of this thesis:

1. Develop and characterisation of a novel murine model of PTOA by surgically inducing concurrent cartilage damage and joint destabilisation within the knee joint (Chapter 3).
2. Investigate *in vivo* the role of PAR2, both global and tissue specific, in the accelerated disease progression characteristic of the newly developed PTOA model (Chapter 4).

- 3.** Elucidate the differential effect of gender on OA pathogenesis using three murine models of OA (Chapter 5)

Chapter 2

General Methods

2.1. *In vivo* Techniques

2.1.1. Ethical approval

All *in vivo* procedures were performed in accordance with UK Home Office Regulations (PPL number P898A202D) and with study approval by Animal Welfare Ethical Review Boards (AWERB) at the University of Glasgow and the University of the West of Scotland.

2.1.2. Animals

C57BL/6 mice were utilised for all *in vivo* procedures described. Studies were carried out on animals bred in house and also sourced from Envigo, UK (outlined in thesis). Animals were housed in standard cages with food and water freely available *ad libitum*. Along with WT mice, 4 different PAR2 KO genotypes were used in this study (detailed below). For in house breeding, homozygous males and females were paired for WT and KO groups. Females were replaced after 6 litters or, if required, males/females were replaced at 1 year of age. Pups were weaned at 4-5 weeks.

2.1.2.1. Global PAR2 KO

For studies involving proteinase-activated receptor 2 global knock-out mice (PAR2 KO; *F2rl1*^{-/-}), mice were bred in-house in independent ventilated cages (IVCs). PAR2 KO mice were originally sourced via collaboration with Professor Robin Plevin (University of Strathclyde). Vector electroporation was utilised to create the PAR2 null allele gene with E14Tg2a embryonic stem (ES) cells (Smith, 1991). The vector was constructed of 9 kb of PAR2 cloned cDNA, flanked at either side of exon 2 with a reporter selection cassette (TAG3/IRES/lacZpA/MC1neopA) inserted into the internal region of exon 2. To generate male chimeras, ES cells were injected into C57BL/6 blastocysts. Male wild-type (WT) were crossed with female PAR2 KO mice to produce the first generation heterozygotes (HETs). Pups were generated from these first generation HETs and genotyped (Section 2.2.1).

2.1.2.2. Tissue-specific PAR2 KO

2.1.2.2.1. PAR2 F/F (F2r1^{fl/fl})

Generated in collaboration with Prof Neil Dear (Leeds University) from ES cells (already C57BL6 background) obtained from the Mouse Genetics Project (Sanger Centre, Cambridge).

The L1L2_Bact_P cassette, consisting of an FRT site followed by lacZ sequence and a loxP site, was inserted at position 95514758 of Chromosome 13 upstream of the critical exon. Under the control of the human beta-actin promoter, neomycin resistance gene follows the first loxP site, further followed by SV40 polyA, a second FRT site and a second loxP site. Downstream of the target exon, a third loxP site is inserted at position 95511446. Thus, the target exon is flanked by loxP sites. A floxed allele is created by flp recombinase expression in mice carrying this allele to remove the lacZ sequence and neo selection cassette, leaving loxP sites flanking the critical exon (Figure 2.1).

Redacted due to copyright restrictions. For original diagram, please contact Dr Kathryn McIntosh.

Figure 2.1. F2r1 gene sequence. Diagram obtained via personal correspondence with Dr Kathryn McIntosh, Strathclyde University.

2.1.2.2.2. Col2 Cre

This strain (B6;SJL-Tg(Col2a1-cre)1Bhr/J - Jackson Laboratories #003554) expresses Cre recombinase driven by the *Col2a1* promoter, which is specific to chondrocytes. The strain was generated on a B6SJLF1 background with the founder then crossed twice to C57BL/6. As explained previously in more detail (Ovchinnikov et al., 2000), expression of Cre recombinase was directed to developing chondrocytes by generating transgenic mice expressing a 8.4kb *Col2a1-Cre* gene construct comprising 3kb of the *Col2a1* promoter region, the first exon with a mutated initiation codon, and a 3.02kb fragment of intron 1 ligated to a splice acceptor region (Zhou et al., 1995). This is then followed by an internal ribosome-entry site, Cre recombinase coding region, and SV40 large T antigen polyadenylation signal. The gene construct was then purified from vector sequences and

injected into the pronuclei of fertilised C57BL/6 x SJL F2 hybrid eggs, resulting in the generation of transgenic mice (Brinster et al., 1985).

2.1.2.2.3. PAR2 Col2

To generate the required PAR2 Col2 conditional KO phenotype (Col2a-Cre⁺⁰;F2r11^{fl/fl}), PAR2 F/F mice (described above) were crossed onto the Col2 mouse (also described above). These were generated and supplied by Professor Drew Rowan, Newcastle University.

2.1.2.3. Animal Models of Osteoarthritis

For all surgical procedures mice were 22-31g in weight and 10 ± 2 weeks of age as at this time point mice are sexually matured and therefore considered to be adult. All surgical groups had 6-11 animals per group. Prior to surgery, animals sourced from Envigo, UK were held for 1 week in the biological unit to allow acclimatisation.. Animals were exposed to 2 % oxygen and 2 % Isoflurane (Isoflurane Vet, Merial) in an anaesthetic chamber. Once anaesthetised animals were transferred to a heat mat (Peco Services Ltd) with a constant supply of 2 % oxygen and 2 % Isoflurane via face mask. Buprenorphine (Vetergesic; 30 µg, Buprecane Animal Care) was administered intraperitoneally pre-operatively, fur was shaved from the ipsilateral leg at the knee joint and then sterilised with hibitane solution (4% w/v, HiBi SCRUB). For identification purposes an ear punch was used to make a notch on the ear of each mouse. Post-surgery, animals were placed in a recovery cage until anaesthetic wore off. Animals were monitored, and clips removed 1 week post-surgery. Animals were maintained for various time points (7, 14 and 28 days). Animal records were maintained, and weight recorded throughout the duration of the time points. Animal health indicators such as 15-20% weight loss were monitored throughout the study. For terminal experiments, mice were euthanised by cervical dislocation of the neck.

Three surgical models were utilised, each with consistent reproducibility. Three separate operators performed each the surgical techniques, with very limited variability in measurable parameters between operators. A separate Sham group served as controls.

2.1.2.3.1. Destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM)

Animals were anaesthetised and prepared for surgery as described above. DMM was carried out as described previously (Glasson, Blanchet and Morris, 2007). In short, the ipsilateral knee joint was exposed and an incision was made with a scalpel through the fascia on the medial side of the patella tendon. Using surgical forceps, the fat pad was moved to the side allowing visualisation of the joint capsule and medial meniscotibial ligament, and then returned to original position. If carrying out sham surgery, the incision would be closed and the wound clipped at this point using a clip applicator (Reflex 7mm applicator; stainless steel wound clips). If continuing to DMM surgery, fine surgical scissors were used to transect the medial meniscotibial ligament (MMTL) and looseness of the medial meniscus was confirmed before clipping the wound together.

2.1.2.3.2. Cartilage Scratch (CS)

Animals underwent the same surgical protocol as described above for sham surgeries. However, once the medial meniscotibial ligament was identified, a fine size 11 micro blade (Swann-Morton, UK) was used to carefully perform 3 scratches to the superficial cartilage on the medial side of the tibia underneath the MMTL (Figure 2.2), making sure not to damage any of the surrounding tissues and knee joint structures.

2.1.2.3.3. DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS)

Animals underwent DMM surgery (as described above). However, once the MMTL was cut and medial meniscus looseness confirmed, a fine micro blade was used to perform 3 scratches on the superficial cartilage of the tibia as described previously in the CS model (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2. Surgical induction of OA. Pictures of three-dimensional micro CT (μ CT) imaging, indicating the regions in which 3 controlled microblade scratches of the articular cartilage (red lines) were made in (A) the cartilage damage model and (B) the DCS model following DMM (white arrow). (C) Cartoon transverse section depicting the region of tibial articular cartilage where 3 microblade scratches were made only to the superficial cartilage. (D) Histological staining of the knee joint indicating superficial scratch-induced cartilage damage (black arrows). Presented μ CT and histological images taken at 14 days post-surgery.

2.1.3. Dynamic Weight Bearing

As an indirect measurement of pain, limb weight bearing was assessed in mice 14 days post-surgery at the appropriate end point using the BioSeb chamber (BioSeb, Marseilles, France). All animals were individually recorded for 5 min, 1 min of which was subsequently analysed and validated. The parameter examined was the load on the front paws.

2.2. *Ex vivo* Techniques

2.2.1. Genotyping

Ear punches were cleaned in Hibiscrub then dried and sterilised in a Steri 350 (Sigma-Aldrich, UK) dry bead steriliser at 250°C. Prior to use, instruments were cooled to room temperature. An ear punch biopsy was obtained from weaned 4-5week old pups from heterozygous pairings. Ear biopsies were

collected in clean 1.5ml eppendorf tubes and stored at -20°C until ready for genotyping (outlined below).

Using ear biopsies described above, the Phire tissue direct kit (Thermo Scientific, UK) was used for genomic DNA isolation. Dilution buffer (20µl) containing DNA release additive (0.5µl) was added to each eppendorf containing a biopsy sample and incubated at room temperature for 5 minutes, followed by a 2 minute incubation at 98°C before being centrifuged for 3 seconds in a microfuge (Jencons PLS, UK). The DNA containing supernatant was collected and used immediately for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with primers specific to the region of interest, or stored at -20°C. For PCR, 10µl Phire mastermix (Thermo Scientific, UK) and 5µl sterile water was added to a PCR tube along with 1µl of DNA sample and 1µl (100µM) of each of the 3 primers (Primer 1: 5'-AAGGCAGAGGGCTATCCGA -3'; Primer 2: 5'- CCTGGAGAACTTGTGGAGC -3'; Primer 3: 5'-GACCGCTTCCTCGTGCTTTA -3'). Samples were then micro-centrifuged for 3 seconds and transferred to a PCR machine (96 well Thermal Cycler, Applied Biosystems, UK). The PCR cycle included: 5 minutes at 95°C followed by 25 cycles of 98°C (10sec), 67°C (10sec) and 72°C (30sec), and finally 72°C for a further 5minutes. PCR products were then run on a 2% agarose gel prepared by adding: 2.6g agarose (Bio-rad, UK) and 2µl ethidium bromide (10mg/ml stock solution, ThermoFisher, UK) to 130ml of 1X Tris Borate EDTA buffer (prepared as a 10X solution with 108g TRIS base (Fisher Scientific, UK), 55g Boric acid (Fisher Scientific, UK), 9.3g ethylenediaminetetraacetic (EDTA, Fisher Scientific, UK) and made up to 1L with distilled water. 10µl O'GeneRuler Express DNA Ladder (Thermo Scientific, UK) was loaded to the first lane of the gel, followed by 15µl of sample in the remaining lanes. Product sizes are as follows: Homozygous WT – 302bp, homozygous KO – 482-512bp and heterozygotes contained both bands. Results were visualised using a UV transilluminator (Cleaver Scientific, UK), and captured using a Canon PowerShot G16 camera (Canon, Japan). Figure 2.3 shows an example gel with a DNA sizing ladder and PCR products.

Figure 2.3. Example genotyping gel. Image of PCR products generated using DNA isolated from ear punch biopsies. L: DNA ladder. Lanes 1 and 2 were genotyped WT; 3, 9, 10, 11, 12 genotyped Het and 4, 6, 8 were genotyped KO.

2.2.2. Microcomputed-tomography (μ CT)

Knee joints were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde solution for 24 h, then transferred to 70% EtOH and analysed by μ CT to examine the calcified tissues using a Skyscan 1272 μ CT scanner (Bruker, Belgium; 0.5 aluminium filter, 50 kV, 200 μ A). Samples were scanned at voxel size 4.5 μ m, 0.3 $^\circ$ rotation angle for quantification, and 2 μ m, 0.2 $^\circ$ rotation angle for imaging (Figure 2A; Figure 3A&B). Scans were reconstructed in NRecon software (Bruker, Belgium). Osteophytes were identified in the resulting three-dimensional image stacks using CTvol software (Bruker, Belgium) and then number of osteophytes per joint counted. Osteophyte bone volume was measured by manually delineating the edge of osteophytes protruding from the subchondral plate as the region of interest (ROI) for analysis, and quantified for bone volume using CTAn software (Bruker, Belgium). Subchondral bone was analysed by selecting a volume of interest (VOI) of 0.5 x 0.9 x 0.9 mm³ in the centre of load in the medial and lateral tibial plateau (Das Neves Borges et al., 2014). ROIs (medial and lateral) delineating the trabecular structure within the tibial epiphysis were selected in the 2D coronal view of the stack to analyse the bone volume and microarchitecture using CTAn.

2.2.3. Histological assessment of cartilage damage and synovitis

Joints were decalcified overnight (Formical 2000; Decal Chemical, New York, USA) and embedded in paraffin wax. Coronal sections (6 μm) were cut and then stained with haematoxylin, safranin-O/fast green. Using a validated scoring system (Glasson, Blanchet and Morris, 2007) ranging from 0 (normal) to 6 (>80% loss of cartilage) (Figure 2.4), severity of cartilage damage was assessed histologically on joints previously scanned for uCT. Two scorers blinded to the specimens, scored the medial tibial quadrant in 4-6 sections from each mouse. Initial cartilage lesions inflicted by microblade scratches in both cartilage damage and DCS models were not included in the scoring. Synovitis was assessed by two blinded scorers using a recently developed scoring system (Jackson et al., 2014) which were modified from the original to focus only on pannus formation, synovial membrane thickening and sub-synovial hyperplasia (Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.4. Histological coronal image of knee joint. Areas of interest indicated for cartilage scoring (black box) and synovitis scoring (green box).

0	Normal cartilage	3	Mild (20%) loss of cartilage
0.5	Loss of Safranin O staining with no structural changes	4	Erosion to bone/cartilage remodelling without vascularisation
1	Roughened articular surfaces with small fibrillations	5	Moderate (20-80%) cartilage loss/cartilage remodelling with vascularisation
2	Fibrillation and some loss of surface lamina	6	Severe (>80%) loss of cartilage

Figure 2.5. Validated cartilage damage scoring system. Images illustrating different degrees of cartilage damage present in the knee joint post-OA induction for guidance when scoring cartilage degradation. Magnification 100x.

Figure 2.6. Validated synovitis scoring system. Images illustrating different degrees of synovitis present in the knee joint post-OA induction for guidance when scoring synovitis severity. Scale bar = 50µm.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Prism 6 (Graphpad) was used to perform statistical analysis. For normally distributed data (e.g. osteophyte volume; osteophyte BV/TV; subchondral and trabecular BV/TV; cartilage damage and synovitis scoring; front paw load), analysis involved one- and two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple comparisons using Bonferroni correction, as well as Student t-tests. Data not normally distributed (e.g. osteophyte number) was analysed by Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis of variance and multiple comparisons using Dunn's corrections as well as Wilcoxon matched pairs test. Linear regression curves were generated and Pearson's *r* was used to establish correlation coefficients. *P* values less than 0.05 were considered significant.

Power number calculation: 8 animals per group would give 90% power to detect a 30% difference in arthritic score between groups at $\alpha = 0.05$, with a standard deviation of $\pm 20\%$. Previous studies by our group utilized an additional 2 animals per group to account for any potential losses. However, as operators are now more experienced and extremely proficient with both surgical and subsequent laboratory techniques, additional animals were not required for this study. This study had a 100% safety rate with no losses.

Chapter 3

**Accelerated osteoarthritis-like symptoms
in a novel dual injury murine model of
post-traumatic OA.**

3.1. Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) is globally the most prevalent musculoskeletal disease (Brooks, 2006), with 80% of the population >65 years of age showing radiological evidence of OA (Lawrence et al., 2008). OA is characterised by significant structural changes in joint tissues such as articular cartilage degradation, osteophyte formation (bony outgrowths), subchondral osteosclerosis, epiphyseal bone expansion, synovitis and pannus formation. Although OA is often associated with increasing age, an accelerated progression is recognised in individuals suffering previous (often sport-related) joint injury involving multi-tissue damage. Notably, 66% of patients presenting with articular surface damage in their joints progressed towards OA (Curl et al., 1997; Hjelle et al., 2002). Furthermore, current data suggests that patients with chronic OA who suffered an earlier articular trauma are, upon diagnosis, >10 years younger than those patients with no history of joint injury (Punzi et al., 2016). Taken together, post-traumatic OA (PTOA), as characterised by accelerated joint degeneration, pain and dysfunction, accounts for ~12% of all OA cases (Buckwalter, 2003).

Lapine models have been used to investigate PTOA resulting from multi-tissue joint injury, usually involving traumatic rupture of the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) and damage of surrounding tissues including the meniscus via mechanical impact on the patellofemoral joint (Christiansen et al., 2015; Fischenich et al., 2015; Fischenich et al., 2017). These have yielded valuable insight into PTOA progression, but involve relatively undefined and uncontrolled damage to various joint tissues. Murine models enable use of gene-modified mice to elucidate pathogenic mechanisms responsible for the accelerated OA progression in PTOA. Surgically-induced murine models that develop OA-like pathology are the destabilised medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM) model and anterior cruciate ligament transection (ACLT) murine models. While both recapitulate features of OA pathology, these do not arise directly from an initial multi-tissue injury, as occurs in PTOA. This may be an important limitation, as increasing evidence suggests that joint tissue interactions may play a significant role in driving disease progression (Findlay and Kuliwaba, 2016; Macchi et al., 2018; Miyaki and Lotz, 2018; Yuan et al., 2014). Other models include articular injection of agents which induce inflammation

and/or tissue toxicity/damage, but are questioned as to how well these represent the joint damage seen in OA (Teeple et al., 2013). To better understand accelerated OA progression, what is needed is a murine model that combines joint destabilisation with defined/controlled joint tissue injury, and is accessible to genetic manipulation, while enabling comprehensive evaluation of disease-related changes in relevant joint tissues (cartilage, bone, meniscus etc.). The studies carried out in this chapter are the first to present a dual injury murine model involving simultaneous cartilage damage and joint destabilisation.

3.2. Hypothesis

Concomitant cartilage damage and joint instability accelerates the onset of OA pathology as seen in PTOA.

3.3. Aims

1. Investigate the role of concurrent cartilage damage with joint destabilisation on the accelerated OA pathogenesis observed in the dual injury DCS murine model.

3.4. Methods

In this chapter both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* methods were utilised.

OA was induced on 10 week old adult wild-type C57BL/6 male mice (body weight 22-28g), sourced from Envigo, UK. All surgical groups had 8 animals per group. Under aseptic conditions OA was induced via (a) transection of the medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM) (Glasson, Blanchet and Morris, 2007), (b) microblade scratches of articular cartilage (cartilage scratch) or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS). Three cartilage scratches were made only to the superficial cartilage, as indicated in chapter 2, figure 2.2. Sham operated joints and the contralateral leg of OA-induced mice were used as controls. Animals were maintained for 7 and 14 days, with knee joints subsequently harvested for μ CT and histological analysis. For histological analysis, there was good agreement between scorers with an intraclass correlation coefficient for cartilage scoring of 0.96 (95% CI 0.92 to 0.98), and synovitis scoring of 0.83; 95% CI 0.65 to 0.92). OARSI scoring system was modified in

figure 3.4A,B to account for cartilage remodelling and vascularisation seen at day 28 post-surgery (figure 3.4E). However, to allow for appropriate comparison to previous studies, the original OARSI scores are presented in appendix II. At day 14 limb weight bearing was analysed as an indirect measurement of pain using the BioSeb Dynamic Weight Bearing chamber (BioSeb, Marseilles, France).

3.5. Results

3.5.1 Accelerated osteophyte development after dual injury

Evaluation of osteophyte formation at an early time point (7 days post-surgery) revealed that although osteophytes could be detected in some mice within each of the experimental groups, there was an increase in detectable osteophytes in the DCS model. Notably, in the DCS group 6 out of 8 mice had observable osteophytes whilst only 3 out of 8 mice in the DMM and CS showed signs of osteophytogenesis (Figure 3.1B). Moreover, at day 7 the osteophytes in the DCS group were quantifiably larger in size (Figure 3C) and in some mice more numerous (Figure 3.1B). In comparison, the DMM group osteophytes were reduced in both number and volume (Figure 3.1B, C). Analysis of osteophyte BV/TV at day 7 did not show any detectable increased bone volume across any of the 3 experimental groups (Figure 3.1D).

Figure 3.1. Osteophyte development 7 days post-surgery. (A) Three-dimensional micro CT (μ CT) imaging of developing osteophytes (arrows) following DMM; cartilage damage; and DCS in C57BL/6 mice. Quantitative data showing (B) osteophyte number (C) osteophyte tissue volume and (D) % of bone within osteophyte (bone volume/tissue volume, BV/TV) present in each sample within each surgical group. ****** $p < 0.01$; $n = 8$.

To determine how these osteophytes develop over time in these models, osteophyte morphology and structural characteristics were investigated at day 14. In the DMM group, arboreal-like osteophytes were observable in 6 out of 8 mice, whilst in the CS and DCS mice, 100% of mice exhibited osteophytes (Figure 3.2A,B,C). Importantly, at this time point, DCS mice had significantly more osteophytes than the DMM and CS groups (Figure 3.2C), with a minimum of 2 observable osteophytes. However, 5 out of 8 DCS mice presented with 3 osteophytes per joint (Figure 3.2C). In

comparison, both DMM and CS alone animals presented a maximum of 2 osteophytes, which were only seen in 3 out of 8 of mice in each group (Figure 3.2C). Both CS and DCS groups exhibited significantly larger osteophyte volume compared to DMM and sham groups (Figure 3.2C). However, the percentage of bone volume within these osteophytes did not differ significantly between experimental model groups (Figure 3.2E).

3.5.2 Dual injury promotes subchondral osteosclerosis

Analysis was undertaken to investigate the impact of DMM, CS and DCS on the subchondral bone. At day 7, μ CT analysis showed an increase of subchondral osteosclerosis in all 3 OA models when compared with sham controls (Figure 3.3A). At day 14 the level of subchondral osteosclerosis in the CS group remained constant, however there was a further increase in subchondral BV/TV in both DMM and DCS models; possibly due to joint instability and increased biomechanical loading (Figure 3.3B). There were no observable differences in epiphyseal trabecular bone in the ipsilateral (injured) leg at day 7 post-surgery (Figure 3.3C). However, at day 14, DCS mice exhibited a significant increase in trabecular BV/TV in the injured leg (Figure 3.3D).

Figure 3.3. Subchondral osteosclerosis is evident at day 7 post-surgery with increased trabecular bone volume at day 14. (A) Day 7 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis. (B) Day 14 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis. (C) Changes in trabecular bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) at day 7. (D) Trabecular BV/TV changes at day 14 post-surgery. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ (without bar is cf. Sham); $n = 6-8$.

3.5.3. Dual injury increases cartilage degradation and synovitis

While cartilage damage and/or synovitis were not normally detectable at day 14 post-induction, this study sought to investigate whether these might emerge in the DCS model at this early time-point as an indicator of accelerated PTOA. Histological analysis of the medial compartment of the knee joint at 14 days following DMM, CS or DCS surgery was performed. Over and above the initial scratch-induced cartilage damage, significant further cartilage degradation was observed in the DCS model on the tibia when compared with DMM and CS models (Figure 3.4A,B). Consistent with this finding increased cartilage degradation on the femur in the DCS model compared with DMM and CS models was also observed (Figure 3.4C). Furthermore, although there was observable synovitis in the DMM and CS groups, there was a significant increase in synovitis in the DCS model (Figure 3.4D). Correlation analysis revealed a strong relationship between cartilage damage and synovitis levels ($r=0.77$, $p=0.0004$)(Figure 3.4E), as well as between cartilage damage and osteophyte number ($r=0.59$, $p=0.003$)(Figure 3.4F). Synovitis also positively correlated with the number of osteophytes present ($r=0.49$, $p=0.02$)(Figure 3.4G).

Figure 3.4. Cartilage degradation and synovitis 14 days post-surgery. (A) Histological appearance of the medial tibial compartment of the knee joint 14 days following DMM; CS or DCS respectively, showing pannus formation (green arrow), synovial hyperplasia (red arrow), sub-synovial hyperplasia (black arrow) and Subchondral bone/osteophyte formation (blue arrow). Scale bar = 200 μ m. Quantification of (B) Medial tibial cartilage damage scores and (C) Medial femoral cartilage damage score and (D) Synovitis scores in mice following Sham, DMM, cartilage damage or DCS surgery at 14 days post-surgery. Correlation curves depicting significant correlations between (E) cartilage damage and synovitis; (F) osteophyte number and cartilage damage; (G) osteophyte number and synovitis. 95% confidence intervals are indicated by dotted lines. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; $n = 8$.

In addition, this study also sought to investigate if accelerated cartilage damage and synovitis in the DCS model persists at 28 days post-surgery (Figure 3.5A-C). Notably, both increased cartilage damage in the medial tibia and femur (Figure 3.5B,C) and synovitis (Figure 3.5D) was found in the DCS group at 28 days post-surgery. Moreover, remodelling and vascularisation of the cartilage at day 28 in the DCS model was observed (Figure 3.5E), features linked with increasing severity of OA pathology (Pufe et al., 2001). Taken together this indicates that DMM combined with cartilage scratch promotes an acute inflammatory environment with progressive and accelerated cartilage degradation, remodelling and enhanced osteophytogenesis.

Figure 3.5. Cartilage degradation and synovitis 28 days post-surgery. (A) Histological appearance of the medial compartment of the knee joint 28 days following DMM; cartilage damage or DCS, showing pannus formation (green arrow), synovial hyperplasia (red arrow), sub-synovial hyperplasia (black arrow) and subchondral bone/osteophyte formation (blue arrow). Scale bar = 200 μ m. Quantification of (B) tibial cartilage damage, (C) femoral cartilage damage and (D) synovitis. (E) Histological image of cartilage vascularisation in the DCS model. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

3.5.4 Osteophyte number and cartilage damage correlate with pain-related behaviour

Prior work by Huesa *et al.* has shown that Dynamic Weight Bearing (DWB) can be used to monitor pain-related behaviour (Huesa *et al.*, 2016). Fourteen days post-surgery, mice in the DCS group demonstrated a significant loss of loading on their ipsilateral (injured) leg when compared with DMM alone (Figure 3.6A). No significance was observed in load on the contralateral (non-injured) hind limb between all groups. Consistent with this, mice in the DCS group also demonstrated a significant increase in front paw load compared with the other models (Figure 3.6B), indicating an increase in OA-related pain. Importantly, there was a strong positive correlation between osteophyte number and front paw load at this time point ($r=0.65$, $p=0.0004$) (Figure 3.6C). Suggesting the severity of OA-related pain may be related to the extent of osteophytogenesis. As there was a positive correlation between osteophyte number and both cartilage damage and synovitis, further investigation into these parameters in relation to OA-pain related behaviour was undertaken: however, neither cartilage damage nor synovitis exhibited a significant correlation with increase front paw load ($r=0.35$, $p=0.09$ and $r=0.28$, $p=0.19$ respectively).

Figure 3.6. Increased pain-related behaviour correlates with osteophyte number and cartilage damage at day 14 post-surgery. Dynamic weight bearing measurements of the (A) ipsilateral (injured) paw and (B) front paw load for mice following DMM, cartilage damage or DCS surgery at 14 days post-surgery. Correlation curves depicting significant correlation between front paw load and (C) osteophyte number, (D) cartilage damage, and (E) synovitis across the models. 95% confidence intervals are indicated by dotted lines. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; $n = 8$. DMM, destabilised medial meniscotibial ligament; CS,

3.6. Discussion

Trauma to the joint is known to promote early osteoarthritis, but the mechanisms for accelerated disease are not well understood. This study presents a novel dual injury murine model to address the important question of whether concomitant joint destabilisation and defined cartilage damage leads to early OA characterised by progressive cartilage destruction, osteophytogenesis, synovitis and pain. This novel surgical technique provides a more consistent, robust and accelerated model of OA, whilst displaying with more hallmarks of OA than other OA murine models.

Critical to model selection and/or development, is the specific research hypothesis being addressed; and how translatable these findings are to human OA. There are various well-established and widely used experimental models of OA across a range of species. While none are ideal in modelling human disease, Little and Smith (2008) have identified preferred characteristics, which include recapitulating human joint disease in a manner amenable for measurement and monitoring, and within a reasonable time frame. Model types range from surgical induction and traumatic injury, to chemical induction methods, each with their strengths and limitations. For example, blunt trauma results in relatively undefined multi-tissue injuries, surgical approaches risk surgical artefact whilst chemical approaches such as intra-articular injection of monoiodoacetate (MIA) likely evoke joint changes by mechanisms different from those underpinning OA. This is the first study to present a novel and robust dual injury murine model allowing earlier time-point investigation into PTOA, as well as providing the research community with a versatile new tool to investigate not only PTOA, but also specific changes within the joint (osteophytogenesis; synovitis & inflammation; cartilage damage; pain pathways and bone changes). Thus highlighting the importance of the DCS model and its breadth of potential uses in future research advancements.

Murine models are important tools for research on various human diseases, and for OA, one of the most widely used is the DMM surgical induction model generated by Glasson and colleagues (Glasson, Blanchet and Morris, 2007). This induces joint instability and recapitulates the cartilage damage, osteosclerosis, osteophytogenesis and pain that characterise OA in humans, although is

technically demanding with respect to surgical skill and need for aseptic conditions. Nevertheless, an experienced researcher can achieve good reproducibility with minimal surgical artefact, and thus DMM is considered to be a robust model in OA. However, DMM does not reproduce the acute trauma-induced damage to surrounding soft tissue (including cartilage) that is observed in human sport-related injuries (Isaac, Meyer and Haut, 2010; Rosen, Jackson and Berger, 1991). PTOA is characterised by accelerated pathology post-injury, and there is a recognised sub cohort of OA patients with symptoms limiting life-style at an earlier time point than normally seen. While this is likely to be a consequence of the synergistic interaction of injury to multiple joint tissues, the exact mechanisms driving this accelerated disease progression are not fully understood. In the context of traumatic injury, altered joint loading and initial cartilage damage as a consequence of meniscal damage has been linked with OA development (Englund, Roos and Lohmander, 2003). Rabbit ACLT models involving blunt impact trauma are available to study PTOA (Ewers et al., 2002; Fischenich et al., 2015; Fischenich et al., 2017). Whilst these models can imitate and reproduce multi-tissue damage similar to that of human knee joint impact traumas, they are limited in not being able to target and confine this trauma specifically to defined tissues within the joint in a reproducible fashion. To this end this chapter presents the development of a novel dual-injury murine model specific for investigation of OA arising from simultaneous cartilage damage and joint destabilisation. The DCS procedure now enables generation of a controlled multi-tissue injury murine model mimicking significant trauma to a healthy knee. The DCS model is thus highly relevant to human disease, offering significant potential in meeting a currently unmet scientific need for a model that more accurately represents the sub cohort of young otherwise healthy individuals suffering accelerated PTOA resulting from sporting injuries. Such injuries involve simultaneous damage to various joint tissues, including ligaments, bone and cartilage. With this model accelerated PTOA is observed via combination of defined cartilage micro-lesions with altered loading due to destabilisation of the medial meniscus, allowing us to investigate mechanisms known to be key OA triggers in human disease.

Osteophyte formation is believed to be a response mechanism triggered by a loading imbalance within the joint, expanding the surface area of the tibial plateau to better support the alteration in biomechanical loading (Wang, Wluka and Cicuttini, 2005; Wang et al., 2006). It has previously been shown DMM alone can induce osteophytogenesis as early as day 7 post-surgery in C57BL/6 mice (Huesa et al., 2016). This is consistent with the present study, in which the presence of small osteophytes, low in number, in the DMM model at day 7 were reported (Figure 3.1B,C). Few, small osteophytes were also present in the CS model at day 7 (Figure 3.1A,B). However, the DCS model presented with quantifiably larger, and in most mice, more numerous osteophyte formation at day 7 (Figure 3.1A,B). These data suggest dual trauma consisting of cartilage damage and joint destabilisation can accelerate the formation of osteophytes as early as 7 days post-injury. Previous studies have reported that secondary osteophyte growth is initiated by cartilage damage (Kallman et al., 1990; Pottenger, Phillips and Draganich, 1990; van Osch et al., 1996b), however the factors influencing the formation and growth of osteophytes are poorly defined. Cartilage lesions have been associated with the formation of larger osteophytes (Markhardt, Li and Kijowski, 2018), supporting day 14 findings of both cartilage damage and DCS models presenting with larger, more numerous osteophytes compared with the DMM model (Figure 3.2C,D), where no initial cartilage damage was induced. This provides evidence that osteophytogenesis is accelerated by cartilage damage when combined with simultaneous joint loading imbalance. The specific site of cartilage damage may itself alter the type of pathologic outcome. This study focussed on cartilage damage within the medial compartment however, there could be value in future studies focussing on the impact of cartilage damage on alternative sites (i.e., non-weight-bearing areas of cartilage) to determine how this affects pathologic outcome. Whilst the DCS model was developed to test a specific hypothesis, it has considerable potential to extend beyond OA, to investigation of osteophytogenesis in various pathological scenarios. Examples include ankylosing spondylitis and degenerative disk disease. Additionally, the study of osteophytogenesis could provide a controlled tool to investigate the initiation of endochondral ossification.

Another prominent feature of OA is the development of osteosclerosis in subchondral bone. When the cartilage becomes damaged there is an increased transfer in load to the subchondral bone (Neogi et al., 2010), as well as the release of inflammatory and osteoclast stimulation factors, which can lead to an increase in bone remodelling (Bellido et al., 2010; Henrotin, Pesesse and Sanchez, 2012). Osteosclerosis was measured as an increase in bone volume (% BV/TV) in the medial subchondral region of the tibia. At both 7 and 14 days post-surgery, all disease model groups exhibited evident osteosclerosis in the loaded medial compartment of the joint, where the destabilisation and/or cartilage damage was induced. After the initial increase at day 7, osteosclerosis in the CS model remained relatively constant at 14 days, whereas both the DMM and DCS groups significantly increased, indicating altered biomechanical load plays a key role in the development of osteosclerosis. Furman *et al.* showed that intra-articular fractures led to subchondral bone thickening and sclerosis of the knee in C57BL/6 mice (Furman et al., 2007).

The observation that cartilage degradation is more extensive and progressive in the DCS model than either of the other models, suggests that interactions arising from the dual injury exacerbates cartilage breakdown. Trauma to the articular cartilage results in the activation of genes encoding for morphogens and the secretion of soluble inflammatory mediators into the joint cavity (Dell'Accio et al., 2006; Dell'Accio et al., 2008; Gruber et al., 2004; Vincent et al., 2002). In adults, healthy articular cartilage is avascular (Moses, Sudhalter and Langer, 1990). However, vascularisation of the articular cartilage is characteristic of OA pathology with osteochondral angiogenesis (growth of blood vessels from the subchondral bone into the articular cartilage) thought to facilitate OA progression (Walsh, 2004). Observation of cartilage vascularisation and remodelling at day 28 in the DCS model is consistent with other animal models that show an increase in angiogenesis in the subchondral bone during the early stages of OA and, with increasing severity, progression to vascular invasion of the osteochondral junction (Ashraf, Mapp and Walsh, 2011; Mapp et al., 2008; Saito et al., 2012). These findings are also consistent with human studies where blood vessels are observed to breach the tidemark in the proximal tibial articular cartilage in patients with OA. The formation of micro cracks

and increased vascularisation associated with abnormal bone remodelling in joints during OA facilitate molecular transport between cartilage and bone (Yuan et al., 2014), therefore soluble inflammatory mediators present in the joint cavity as a result of cartilage damage and joint destabilisation may potentiate further cartilage destruction/bone remodelling, thus accelerating joint pathology in PTOA. Interestingly, a significant correlation between cartilage damage and osteophyte number was observed (Figure 3.4H), raising the intriguing possibility that soluble factors secreted by the damaged cartilage as well as articular cartilage debris may contribute to accelerated osteophytogenesis. Cartilage damage also exhibited a positive correlation with synovitis (Figure 3.4G) suggesting a link with inflammatory factors. This increased vascularisation and remodelling of the articular cartilage requires further investigation to further understand the underlying factors promoting increased angiogenesis and cartilage remodelling within OA.

While traditionally considered a 'wear and tear' disease, inflammation is increasingly recognised to have a role in degenerative changes occurring during OA pathogenesis (Pelletier, Martel-Pelletier and Abramson, 2001). Histological features consistent with synovitis have been observed in synovium from OA patients (Farahat et al., 1993; Goldenberg, Egan and Cohen, 1982; Haraoui et al., 1991; Smith et al., 1997) as well as expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Farahat et al., 1993; Smith et al., 1997), and more recently, considerable heterogeneity of various inflammatory indices in OA synovia has been reported (Tindell et al., 2012). Indeed knee arthroscopic studies of OA patients found synovial inflammation to be associated with OA structural severity (Walsh et al., 2009), whilst another study reported that serum C-reactive protein levels in early osteoarthritis predicted likely progressive disease (Spector et al., 1997a); CRP also correlates significantly with disease joint count and radiographic score in OA (Punzi et al., 2005). Whilst the DMM model does recapitulate many of the characteristic features of OA, it is generally considered a non-inflammatory model (Chia et al., 2009). This study, however, supported by previous findings (Jackson et al., 2014), detected histologically the presence of synovitis at 14 days post-surgery. Nevertheless, given the low-level nature of this synovitis, DMM is not the model of choice for investigation of inflammation in OA

joints. While the MIA model evokes joint inflammation (Ivanavicius et al., 2007), this inflammatory response is not initiated in a manner resembling that of OA. The DCS model yielded a significant and consistently higher level of synovitis than seen in either the DMM or CS models and, similarly to cartilage degradation, synovitis was positively correlated with increased osteophyte number (Figure 3.4G). Thus DCS presents value in enabling mechanistic interrogation of the putative contribution of synovitis to OA pathogenesis.

Pain is one of the most common and physically limiting symptoms of OA, however the origin of this pain is still poorly understood. DWB presents a behavioural non-invasive means of assessing pain, although other factors (e.g. mechanical impediment) may influence the observed changes. Ipsilateral (injured) hind paw and front paw loading were analysed. There was a significant decrease in injured hind paw load with a corresponding increase in load on the front paws in the DCS model compared with all other groups (Figure 3.6A-B), suggesting the combination of cartilage damage and DMM enhances pain-associated pathology. There have been conflicting studies regarding the relationship between pain and osteophytes in OA. One previous study presented a significant correlation between knee joint pain in OA patients with osteophytes present in the medial tibial condyle (Boegard et al., 1998). However, more recently, Sengupta *et al.* challenged this finding by reporting that the presence of high-signal osteophytes detected on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) were not associated with pain or pain severity (Sengupta et al., 2006). Data demonstrates a significant and strong positive correlation between osteophyte number and front paw load at 14 days post-surgery (Figure 3.6C). Synovitis is known to lead to heightened pain sensitivity in knee OA (Neogi et al., 2016) and therefore this study elected to further explore this finding in relation to pain-associated behaviour in the DCS model. No significant correlation between front paw load and synovitis (Figure 3.6D) or an increase in cartilage degradation was reported. The association of osteophytogenesis, cartilage damage, synovitis and pain implicates a causal relationship, and this merits future research to define the nature of any such relationships; this may help identify possible molecular mechanisms driving osteophyte formation, as well as joint pain.

3.7. Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be observed that concomitant joint instability and cartilage injury that typify knee joint traumatic injury predispose to accelerated OA progression. Importantly, this model also provides a valuable research tool for investigating osteophytogenesis in various contexts, as the DCS model generates an accelerated and more extensive formation of osteophytes at an early time-point. The reproducible synovitis associated with this model also presents means to elucidate the role of synovitis in OA pathology. Similarly, the enhanced pain-related behaviour in DCS provides a robust model for *in vivo* investigation of joint pain. Further investigation into the mechanism(s) by which cartilage damage exacerbates the OA related pathology will be addressed in subsequent chapters.

Chapter 4

**PAR2 accelerates OA-like joint changes in
a dual injury murine model of post-
traumatic OA**

4.1. Introduction

One major advantage of utilising mouse models in the study of OA is the ability to use transgenic (genetically modified) mice and breed strain-specific models to investigate and understand genetic contributions to OA pathogenesis, as well as developing future treatments. These transgenic models allow animals to be genetically altered to either protect against or indeed exacerbate OA pathogenesis (Little and Hunter, 2013); they have played a pivotal role in identifying various genetic contributions to OA (Little and Zaki, 2012; Miller et al., 2013). Our group has previously discovered a novel pathway involving proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) in an experimental model of OA (DMM), in which PAR2 was found to exacerbate OA-like symptoms, since PAR2 knock-out (PAR2 KO) mice demonstrated significant protection against cartilage degradation and osteosclerosis (Ferrell et al., 2010; Huesa et al., 2016).

PAR2 has been shown to be present human OA cartilage (Xiang et al., 2006), and is known to play a pivotal role in osteophyte formation during OA progression in the DMM model (Huesa et al., 2016). Following PAR2 activation, *in vitro* studies demonstrated upregulation of inflammatory mediators and MMPs in OA cartilage (Boileau et al., 2007), as well as increased osteoblast resorption and synthesis of Receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL) in subchondral bone (Amiable et al., 2009) suggesting a pivotal link between PAR2, inflammation and the destruction/remodelling of OA-affected tissues (Amiable et al., 2011).

There is increasing evidence promoting the role of PAR receptors and their activation during nociceptive signalling and chronic pain development, with PARs being expressed in both astrocytes and neurons. Previous work has shown PAR2 KO mice to have reduced pain response (Vergnolle et al., 2001), highlighting this receptor as a potential target for analgesic therapy.

This chapter aimed to build upon previous findings identifying a key role for PAR2 in OA, by investigating if tissue-specific disruption of PAR2 conferred similar protection against arthritis, in an established murine model (DMM), and a novel dual injury model of PTOA.

4.2. Hypotheses

- PAR2 plays a role in the accelerated osteophytogenesis, bone changes, cartilage damage and OA pain related behaviour in PTOA.
- PAR2 present in the chondrocytes of cartilage exacerbate OA-like symptoms in a murine model of PTOA.

4.3. Aims

Characterise the role of PAR2 in accelerated osteophytogenesis, bone changes, synovitis and OA pain-related behaviour in a novel dual injury surgical model of OA (DCS) using PAR2-deficient mice.

4.4. Methods

In this chapter both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* methods were utilised.

OA was induced as previously described (Chapter 2, section 2.1.2.3) in 10 week old adult male (23-30g) WT, PAR2 KO and cartilage-specific PAR2-deficient mice, and their appropriate controls, bred in house. Animals were maintained for 14 and 28 days, with knee joints subsequently harvested for μ CT and histological analysis. At day 14 limb weight bearing was analysed as an indirect measurement of pain using the BioSeb Dynamic Weight Bearing chamber.

4.5. Results

4.5.1. Global PAR2 KO

4.5.1.1. PAR2 protects against osteophyte progression

Evaluation of osteophyte formation in the ipsilateral (injured) leg of PAR2 KO mice at 14 days revealed no significant differences in osteophyte number compared to WT mice in each of the experimental groups (Figure 4.1A,B). Although not significant, PAR2 KO mice in the DCS group show protection against osteophyte formation with only 2/8 mice presenting with 3 osteophytes, compared with 5/8 in WT mice. Unlike the CS model, the DCS model resulted in destabilisation of the joint, perhaps implying that PAR2 requires instability of the joint in order to confer protection. As shown previously (Chapter 4, figure 3.2D) both CS and DCS WT models showed an increase in

osteophyte volume. However, CS and DCS induced in PAR2 KO mice did not exhibit a significant decrease in osteophyte volume when compared to their WT counterparts. While not significant, PAR2 KO osteophytes did show a tendency to be of smaller size than WTs (Figure 4.1C,D). Similarly, osteophyte bone volume (%) remained similar in KO vs. WT in CS and DCS groups (Figure 4.1E,F).

Figure 4.1. Osteophyte development 14 days post-surgery in WT and PAR2 KO mice. Quantitative data showing decreased osteophytogenesis PAR2 KO mice exhibited by osteophyte number (Wilcoxon matched pairs test) in (A) CS and (B) DCS surgery; total osteophyte volume (Student's t-test) in (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery, and % of bone present within osteophytes in (E) CS and (F) DCS surgery. n=8.

Huesa and colleagues have previously shown that PAR2 deletion confers protection against osteophytogenesis at 28 days post-DMM surgery (Huesa et al., 2016), therefore experiments in this chapter were designed to investigate the role of PAR2 at 28 days in both CS and DCS models. Upon

initial visualisation of osteophytes using μ CT scans, differences in size of osteophytes between WT and PAR2 KO mice in the DCS group were found (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2. μ CT imaging of osteophyte development 28 days post-surgery in WT and PAR2 KO mice. Three-dimensional μ CT imaging of developing osteophytes (pink) following DCS surgery in (A) WT and (B) PAR2 KO C57BL/6 mice. (C-D) Corresponding transverse plane images.

Animals in the CS group showed no difference in osteophyte number between WT and KO mice (Figure 4.2A). All WT mice in the DCS group presented with at least 1 observable osteophyte, with 2 of 7 mice presenting with 3 (Figure 4.3B). Their KO counterparts however did not exceed 2 observable osteophytes, with 2 of 8 mice presenting with no osteophytes (Figure 4.3B).

Similarly to 14 day osteophyte volume PAR2 KO mice in the DCS group showed a significantly decreased osteophyte volume (Figure 4.3D), with the CS model showing no difference (Figure 4.3C). Although not significant, day 14 KOs in CS and DCS groups begin to present a trend of decreased osteophyte volume (Figure 4.1C, D). At day 28 this trend becomes significantly decreased between WT and KO in DCS groups (Figure 4.3D). This result combined with the significant decrease in the KO

DMM group, further implies that PAR2 requires instability of the joint in order to confer protection. Osteophytes present in KO mice in the DCS group also has a reduced bone volume compared to WTs. Osteophyte bone volume was significantly decreased in PAR2 KO mice in the CS group (Figure 4.3E), with PAR2 KOs in the DCS group also showing a tendency of decreased osteophyte bone volume (Figure 4.3F), and although not significant, a larger group n may address this.

Figure 4.3. Osteophyte development 28 days post-surgery in WT and PAR2 KO mice. Quantitative data showing osteophytogenesis in WT and PAR2 KO mice exhibited by osteophyte number (Wilcoxon matched pairs test) in (A) CS and (B) DCS surgery; total osteophyte volume (Student's t-test) in (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery, and % of bone present within osteophytes in (E) CS and (F) DCS surgery. *p<0.05; **p<0.01; n=8.

To investigate if PAR2 played a role in osteophytogenesis progression, experiments were designed to observe osteophytes over a 14 day period (day 14-28 post-surgery). In the CS group no significant difference in the progression of osteophyte size (volume) and BV % was observed between WT and PAR2 KO mice (Figure 4.4A). However, PAR2 KO mice in the DCS group show protection against osteophyte development with both osteophyte size significantly decreased when compared to WT's (Figure 4.4B). Osteophyte bone volume in WT v PAR2 KO's did not significantly differ over a 14 day time-point (Figure 4.4C,D).

Figure 4.4. Progression of osteophyte development over 14 days in WT and PAR2 KO mice. Quantitative data showing osteophyte progression in WT and PAR2 KO mice exhibited by total osteophyte volume in (A) CS and (B) DCS surgery (significance is comparing WT v KO line gradient), and % of bone present within osteophytes in (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery. Two-way ANOVA. **p<0.01. n=8.

4.5.1.2. PAR2 promotes osteosclerosis progression

At day 14 and 28 an increase in subchondral osteosclerosis was observed in WT mice in CS and DCS groups (Chapter 3, section 3.5.2), with previous studies also demonstrating that PAR2^{-/-} mice are protected from osteosclerosis up to 28 days post-DMM surgery (Huesa et al., 2016). The extending question here was whether knocking out PAR2 would also confer similar protection in the dual-injury

DCS model. A limiting factor of this study was the analysis of osteosclerosis bone parameters were carried out solely on the ipsilateral (injured) leg as an initial evaluation to provide proof of concept and determine if there were significant changes to indicate a strong rationale for further more in-depth analysis. Therefore results were not normalised against the contralateral (un-injured) leg, and definitive conclusions cannot be made. However, initial results observed no significant differences in subchondral osteosclerosis between WT and KO mice in both CS and DCS groups at 14 and 28 day time-points (Figure 4.5A-D), although at day 28, PAR2 KO mice tended to show a decreased BV/TV (Figure 4.5D).

Figure 4.5. Development of osteosclerosis 14 and 28 days post-surgery. Day 14 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis in (A) CS and (B) DCS surgery. Day 28 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis in (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery. n=6-8.

At day 14 post-surgery, no difference in BV/TV in metaphyseal trabecular bone in the ipsilateral (operated) leg was observed between WT and KO in DCS groups (Figure 4.6A). Interestingly, PAR2 KO mice showed an increased BV/TV in the CS model (Figure 4.6A). At day 28 there was no change in

BV/TV in DMM or CS groups (Figure 4.6B). However there was a significant decrease in trabecular BV/TV in KOs in the DCS group (Figure 4.6B).

Figure 4.6. Changes in trabecular BV/TV is evident in PAR2 KO mice. (A) Day 14 post-surgical trabecular BV/TV changes in DMM, CS and DCS models, and (B) 28 days post-surgical trabecular BV/TV changes in DMM, CS and DCS models. ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ (significance of surgery within each genotype); δ $p < 0.05$ (significance of surgery across each genotype). Two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparison test. $n = 8$.

When looking at progression of osteosclerosis over a 14 day period, there was an altered progression, favouring protection, in the DCS model in both subchondral and trabecular bone in PAR2 KO mice (Figure 4.7 A,B).

Figure 4.7. PAR2 KO mice exhibit an altered progression favouring protection against osteosclerosis in the DCS model. Quantification of (A) subchondral and (B) trabecular bone over a 14 day time period in the DCS model.

4.5.1.3. Loss of PAR2 delays cartilage degradation

As previously shown (Chapter 3, figure 3.4A-C), WT mice in the DCS group presented with significant cartilage degradation on the tibia as well as increased cartilage degradation on the femur when compared with DMM and CS models. It has previously reported that loss of PAR2 confers protection against cartilage damage in the DMM model (Ferrell et al., 2010; Huesa et al., 2016), which was subsequently confirmed by others (Amiable et al., 2011; Jackson et al., 2014). The role of PAR2 in the acceleration of cartilage degradation was further explored in the novel CS and DCS models by investigating the progression of cartilage degradation between 14 and 28 days post-surgery in WT and PAR2 KO mice. In both CS and DCS PAR2 KO groups, mice were observed to show an altered progression in articular cartilage degradation. Although not significant, both medial tibial and femoral damage scores in PAR2 KOs were lower, with a less severe level of progression over the 14 day period when compared to WTs (Figure 4.8A-D). These data further confirm previous findings in the DMM model, supporting a role for PAR2 in the degradation of cartilage in surgically-induced OA.

Figure 4.8. Loss of PAR delays cartilage damage progression in PTOA. PAR2 KO mice exhibit a delayed progression of medial tibial cartilage damage post- (A) CS and (B) DCS surgery. Medial femoral cartilage damage progression post- (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery. Progression was monitored over a 14 day time-period. Histological appearance of the medial tibial and femoral compartments of the knee joint 14 days post DCS surgery in (E) WT and (F) PAR2 KO mice. Visual image of cartilage damage 28 days post-DCS surgery in (G) WT and (H) PAR2 KO mice showing considerable loss of cartilage (black arrow) in WT mice. ** $p < 0.01$. $n = 8$. Scale bar = 200 μm .

Interestingly, unlike cartilage damage, PAR2 does not appear to have a protective effect on synovial inflammation (synovitis), with PAR2 KO mice showing only a very slight increase in synovitis progression over a 14 day time period in both CS and DCS models when compared to their WT counterparts (Figure 4.9A,B).

Figure 4.9. Loss of PAR2 has no effect on synovitis progression. Progression graphs showing synovitis development over a 14 day time period in (A) CS and (B) DCS models.

4.5.1.4. Loss of PAR2 reduces pain-related behaviour in a dual injury model

Having previously established a significant increase in front paw load in WT mice in the DCS group (Chapter 3, figure 3.6B), further experiments were designed to investigate if PAR2 played a role in this increase in OA-related pain behaviour. The hypothesis tested was that the observed increase in front paw load in WT DCS model reflects compensation for increased pain/discomfort in the operated hind-limb. No differences were seen between WT and PAR2 KO mice in sham controls (Figure 4.10A) or CS group (Figure 4.10B). In PAR2 KO mice that underwent DCS surgery a decrease in altered pain-related behaviour compared to WT was noted (Figure 4.10C), indicating PAR2 could be involved in pain sensing.

Figure 4.10. Loss of PAR2 decreases OA pain-related behaviour 14 days post-surgery. Dynamic weight bearing measurements of front paw load for mice following (A) Sham (B) CS and (C) DCS surgery. ** $p < 0.01$; $n = 3-8$.

4.5.2. Chondrocyte-specific PAR2 KO

PAR2 KO mice presented with a protected phenotype against OA pathogenesis in the 3 studied models (Section 4.5.1), and so the role of PAR2 was next investigated using specific chondrocyte PAR2-deficient mice (PAR2 Col2) to test the hypothesis that PAR2 present in the cartilage accelerates OA-like joint changes.

4.5.2.1. Osteophyte development

When compared to F/F mice, osteophyte number is increased in Col2 and PAR2 Col2 mice in the DMM group at 14 days post-surgery (Figure 4.11A). However, no significant differences were observed in the number of osteophytes present in CS and DCS groups in any of the 3 genotypes (Figure 4.11A,B). In all OA surgical groups, osteophytes appeared larger in Col2 mice, with little difference between F/F and PAR2 Col2 mice (Figure 4.11D-E). In both CS and DCS groups, PAR2 Col2 mice present with a reduced % of mineralisation in osteophytes (figure 4.11H,I). Mineralisation of

osteophytes showed no difference in the DMM group (Figure 4.11G). These results would suggest the additive cartilage injury promotes a reduction in osteophyte volume and mineralisation in PAR2 Col2 mice.

Figure 4.11. Osteophyte development 14 days post-surgery in chondrocyte-specific PAR2 KO mice. Quantitative data showing decreased osteophytogenesis PAR2 KO mice exhibited by osteophyte number (Kruskal-Wallis test) in (A) DMM (B) CS and (C) DCS surgery; total osteophyte volume (Student's t-test) in (D) DMM (E) CS and (F) DCS surgery, and % of bone present within osteophytes in (G) DMM (H) CS and (I) DCS surgery. *p<0.05; **p<0.01. n=8-11.

At 28 days post-surgery DMM and DCS groups presented no differences in osteophyte number in all genotypes, however PAR2 Col2 mice exhibited a significant decrease compared with Col2 controls (Figure 4.12B). Col2 mice presented with quantifiably larger osteophytes in all surgical groups (Figure 4.12D-F). There was no difference in osteophyte BV (Figure 4.12G-I).

Figure 4.12. Osteophyte development 28 days post-surgery in chondrocyte-specific PAR2 KO mice. Quantitative data showing osteophytogenesis PAR2 KO mice exhibited by osteophyte number (Kruskal-Wallis test) in (A) DMM (B) CS and (C) DCS surgery; total osteophyte volume (Student's t-test) in (D) DMM (E) CS and (F) DCS surgery, and % of bone present within osteophytes in (G) DMM (H) CS and (I) DCS surgery. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. $n = 3-12$.

As PAR2 KO mice showed an altered progression hinting towards PAR2 providing a protective mechanism in the DCS group over a 14 day time period, the progression of osteophytogenesis in conditional KO mice was investigated. Again, a greater level of progression was observed in Col2 mice when analysing osteophyte size between day 14 and day 28 post-surgery (Figure 4.13A-C). In contrast, there was little to no progression of size in F/F and PAR2 Col2 mice in DMM and CS groups. However, a slightly increased level of progression in F/F and PAR2 Col 2 mice begins to emerge in the dual injury DCS group (Figure 4.13C).

Figure 4.13. Progression of osteophyte formation over 14 days in chondrocyte-specific PAR2 KO mice. Quantitative data showing osteophyte progression exhibited by total osteophyte volume in (A) DMM, (B) CS and (C) DCS surgery. Two-way ANOVA. *** $p < 0.001$ (genotype) $n = 4-8$.

4.5.2.2. Trabecular bone changes

Trabecular BV/TV was analysed to evaluate the level of osteosclerosis in conditional KO mice. Similarly to section 4.5.1.2, bone parameter evaluation was performed solely on the ipsilateral leg to provide initial proof of concept, and therefore data were not normalised. All 3 genotypes (control and experimental) presented with similar BV/TV values in sham controls at both 14 and 28 day time points, indicating trabecular bone architecture is comparable across each genotype, with no alterations arising due to genetic manipulation (Figure 4.14A,B). At 14 days PAR2 F/F and Col2Cre control groups showed an increase in BV/TV % in all 3 OA-induced groups. However, PAR2 Col2 KO mice did not show the same level of osteosclerosis development with values remaining similar to the sham controls (Figures 4.14C-E). Similar results were observed in OA models at day 28 post-surgery, with both PAR2 F/F and Col2Cre groups presenting with increased osteosclerosis, and PAR2 Col2 KO mice maintaining trabecular BV/TV % comparable with sham controls (Figures 4.14F-H). Furthermore, the progression of osteosclerosis was analysed over a 14 day period. All 3 OA surgical groups presented with very similar results, indicating time was not a significant factor in the development of osteosclerosis however, genotype was observed to have a significant effect (Figures 4.14I-K). These data indicate that loss of PAR2 in chondrocytes could play a role in osteosclerosis development with a reduction seen in PAR2 Col2 KO mice, whether directly through the cartilage or indirectly through another pathway.

Figure 4.14. Development of trabecular bone changes 14 and 28 days post-surgery in chondrocyte-specific PAR2 KO mice. Osteosclerosis development in sham controls at (A) day 14 and (B) day 28 post-surgery. Day 14 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis in (C) DMM, (D) CS and (E) DCS surgery. Day 28 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis in (F) DMM, (G) CS and (H) DCS surgery. Post-surgery time-course of trabecular osteosclerosis development in (I) DMM, (J) CS and (K) DCS models. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. $n = 2-10$.

4.6. Discussion

Inducing the DCS model in PAR2 KO mice enabled the role of PAR2 in the progression of PTOA to be investigated, as well as characterising the role of PAR2 in specific tissues of the joint.

It has been previously demonstrated loss of PAR2 protects against osteophytogenesis in the DMM model at 28 days post-surgery (Huesa et al., 2016). Although Huesa and colleagues observed osteophytes in PAR2 KO mice, these were measurably different than osteophytes present in WTs (i.e. incidence, size, mineralisation and progression). Upon histological analysis, they were able to identify the osteophytes as being of chondrocytic phenotype as well as confirming the presence of PAR2 within these proliferative cells. The presence of PAR2 in developing osteophytes is speculated to be a pathological occurrence as PAR2 was not found in the growth plate where other chondrocytic growth factors have been observed (Huesa et al., 2016). Studies have also reported contrasting evidence, with no differences in osteophyte maturity and size being observed at 28 days post-DMM (Jackson et al., 2014). The data reported in this chapter supports the results published by Huesa *et al.* regarding the incidence of osteophyte formation in PAR2 KOs which, while not significant, tending to be decreased in comparison to WTs 28 days post-DCS surgery (Huesa et al., 2016). In combination with this, these osteophytes are significantly smaller in size and present with a lower bone volume, further confirming the findings by Huesa and colleagues.

A well-accepted pathological feature of OA is the altered balance between bone formation and resorption. In comparison to WTs, decreased subchondral and trabecular osteosclerosis was observed at 28 days post-surgery in PAR2 KO DCS group. PAR2 could be responsible for this altered equilibrium between bone resorption and formation, as it is known activation of PAR2 results in inhibition of osteoclast differentiation (Smith et al., 2004). In osteoblasts isolated from human OA subchondral bone, PAR2 was also found to be upregulated leading to increased bone resorption (Amiable et al., 2009) due to increased levels of various factors associated with the resorption of bone e.g. Receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL), MMP-1, MMP-9 and IL-6 (Hulejova et al., 2007; Logar et al., 2007; Shibakawa et al., 2005). PAR2 KO mice have been observed

to possess fewer osteoblast precursors as well as reduced osteoclast generation in their bone marrow when compared to WT mice (Georgy et al., 2012). There is evidence that an overload in mechanical stress leads to the activation of chondrocytic anabolic processes including MMP secretion (Loeser et al., 2012). This altered mechanical stress can affect the homeostasis of the underlying bone with an increase in load causing the appositional growth of bone (Schneider et al., 1995) Huesa and colleagues (2016) speculated that PAR2 had a role in mechanosensing and/or mechanotransduction since uCT analysis revealed the presence of osteosclerosis in WT but not PAR2 KO mice post-DMM induction. The present study also found similar results in the DCS model at 28 days post-surgery, with PAR2 KO mice presenting with a slowed progression of osteosclerosis development. During OA progression, blood vessels are observed to breach the tidemark in the proximal tibial articular cartilage with the formation of micro-cracks thought to aid transport between cartilage and bone (Yuan et al., 2014). Concomitant damage to articular cartilage, induced by increased joint loading, exacerbates thickening of the underlying subchondral bone. Gait changes, which involve an alteration in loading pattern, may initiate an increase in trabecular mass (Poulet et al., 2015) The studies in this chapter investigated the effect of PAR2 loss specifically in chondrocytes, and highlight a potential ability of PAR2 in cartilage to affect the nearby bone architecture. The changes in both subchondral and trabecular bone in PAR2 Col2 mice, indicate that that PAR2 in the chondrocytes can indirectly affect surrounding bone. These bone changes in PAR2 Col2 mice could also be due to the targeting specificity of Col2 Cre. Although Col2 is a major product of chondrocytes, and an early marker of chondrogenesis, it is also synthesised by various other cell types. Lineage mapping studies have showed the *Col2* promoter can be activated in bone marrow stromal and mesenchymal stem cells (Ono et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2014). As well as this, *Col2* is detected in the growth plate, subchondral bone, meniscus and articular cartilage of synovial joints (Fosang et al., 2013; Sakai et al., 2001). Thus demonstrating Col2 Cre transgenic mice do not specifically target only chondrocytes, but also have off site targets in various other cell populations (Nagao, Cheong and Olsen, 2016). However, as stated previously, in order to draw definitive

conclusions regarding bone parameters in this chapter more in-depth analysis, specifically normalisation against the contralateral leg, is required. Future work involving mice engineered genetically to have tissue-specific loss of PAR2 expression in bone would present a targeted approach to elucidating the relationship between PAR2, and cartilage and bone changes observed in OA pathology.

During OA, the equilibrium of cartilage remodelling shifts in favour of catabolism causing degradation of the articular cartilage. It has been demonstrated PAR2 KO mice exhibit protection against cartilage damage at 28 days post-DMM surgery (Amiable et al., 2011; Ferrell et al., 2010; Huesa et al., 2016). This phenomenon is thought to be relatively specific to PAR2, as deletion of PAR1 did not show a significant decrease in DMM-induced cartilage damage (Jackson et al., 2014). The results in this chapter evidence the role of PAR2 in cartilage damage acceleration, with WT mice in both CS and DCS groups presenting with a steep linear progression of damage to the articular cartilage between 14 and 28 days post-surgery in both medial tibial and medial femoral quadrants. In comparison, their PAR2 KO counterparts show little or no progression in cartilage damage during this time-course. PAR2 modulates the release of Interleukin β (IL- β) (Kelso et al., 2007), a potent chondrocyte catabolin (Daheshia and Yao, 2008) into the synovium, with MMP-1 and -13 release also known to be linked with selective PAR2 activation in chondrocytes (Boileau et al., 2007). MMP-1 is an important cytokine in the inflammatory process and MMP-13 is involved in remodelling (Huebner et al., 1998; Moldovan et al., 1997; O'Dell et al., 2001), both playing a role in aggrecan and collagen degradation. It could therefore be speculated that PAR2, through its effect on pro-inflammatory cytokine production and regulation in the joint space, contributes to alterations in both the surface and remodelling of articular cartilage within the joint. Alternatively, Jackson and colleagues hypothesised the chondroprotective phenomenon observed in PAR2 KO mice occur indirectly via remodelling of the subchondral bone, and also activation of synovial macrophages (Jackson et al., 2014). Further histological analysis of chondrocyte-specific PAR2 KO (PAR2 Col2) mice, with direct comparison to the global PAR2 KO mice, would be of value in extrapolating the

mechanisms by which PAR2 accelerates cartilage damage in OA, whether it be directly through chondrocyte catabolic responses, or indirectly through extra-cartilaginous events (e.g. subchondral bone remodelling).

It has been previously reported that PAR2 could mediate the inflammatory process in OA, with PAR2 KO mice showing a reduction in joint swelling in the DMM model (Amiable et al., 2011). Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) has a well-recognised pro-inflammatory role in joint swelling in arthritis, as well as the inflammatory OA pathways (Chillingworth, Morham and Donaldson, 2006; Noguchi et al., 2005). In humans COX-2 was upregulated, via PAR2 activation, in OA cartilage and various other cell types (Boileau et al., 2007; Houlston et al., 2002; Seymour et al., 2005; Wang, Wang and Bjorling, 2009). Taken together these studies indicate that PAR2 could mediate its inflammatory effect in OA via COX-2 production. The results in this chapter however, do not show reduced synovial inflammation in CS and DCS models, nor was there reduction in the progression of synovitis over a 14 day period. Instead an increase in inflammation in PAR2 KO mice was found over a 14 day time period in the CS model when compared to WT.

Pain is one of the most common and physically limiting symptoms of OA, and severely impacts upon a patient's quality of life. As discussed previously PAR2 plays a potential role in the development and modulation of a variety of pathological pain states, most notably widespread inflammation and tissue repair (Déry et al., 1998). The lack of altered pain-related behaviour in PAR2 KO mice indicates PAR2 could be involved in pain sensing, and therefore holds considerable potential as a future target for analgesic treatments of OA.

4.7. Conclusion

This chapter presents strong evidence of PAR2 contributing to the acceleration of OA-like joint changes such as osteophytogenesis, osteosclerosis, cartilage degradation, and altered OA-related pain behaviour in a dual injury murine model of PTOA. Taken together, these findings further highlight PAR2 as an attractive therapeutic target in the abrogation of OA pathology. However, in order to elucidate the optimal timing and targets of PAR2 for clinical benefits, more in-depth studies

into the specific molecular mechanisms by which PAR2 contributes to OA pathogenesis are required, as well as increasing time-points post-surgery to gain a full temporal characterisation of PAR2's influence on disease progression in OA.

Chapter 5

Sex-specific changes in osteoarthritis.

5.1. Introduction

For many years it has been recognised that there are significant sex-specific differences in the incidence, prevalence and clinical manifestation of osteoarthritis (OA) (Jordan et al., 2007; Jordan et al., 2009; Srikanth et al., 2005). It has already been shown that females manifest OA differently from males, with certain areas of the knee being disproportionately affected (Felson et al., 1995; Hanna et al., 2009; McAlindon et al., 1992a; O'Connor, 2007). However, the reasoning, and also mechanisms, contributing to the differences in presentation and progression of OA between sexes have not been extensively investigated.

Before the age of 50, the prevalence of OA in men is greater than in females (Ma et al., 2007). However, early onset OA is quickly becoming more common, especially among females who are physically active (e.g. athletes). OA becomes more prevalent in females post-menopause, with females also present with greater pain, disability (McAlindon et al., 1992a; O'Connor, 2007; O'Connor and Hooten, 2011; Thomas, Pagura and Kennedy, 2003) and report more substantial reductions in both function and quality of life than their male counterparts (Zhang et al., 2010). Along with this, females are more prone to, and burdened by, knee OA compared with men (Blagojevic et al., 2010; Felson et al., 1987; Felson et al., 1995; O'Connor, 2006; Srikanth et al., 2005). Various factors come into consideration when investigating the effect of sex on the presentation and progression of OA, such as differences in knee anatomy and mechanical alignment, kinematics, previous injury and hormones (Hame and Alexander, 2013). Females tend to present with more advanced radiographic findings (McAlindon et al., 1992b). The reasons for this are multifactorial but may be related to increased cartilage wear with less cartilage volume.

The mechanisms underlying the differences in epidemiology, development and pain between males and females with OA are unknown; however, hormonal differences may play a role. There is an increased risk of OA development amongst post-menopausal women, which has been linked to reduced oestrogen levels. Zhang *et al.* demonstrated post-menopausal females receiving oestrogen replacement therapy had a decreased risk of developing radiographic evidence of knee OA, with this

risk further reduced during the course of therapy (Zhang et al., 1998). Oestrogen receptors have been identified in the articular cartilage (Richmond et al., 2000). Although the clinical relevance of these receptors is unknown, they do imply a potential link between articular cartilage and oestrogen.

Regarding sex-related differences in functional ability and pain intensity in patients with knee OA, there is a lack of consensus. Whilst many studies have documented females to experience an increase in self-assessed pain intensity and decreased functional ability, other studies, have shown that in regard to measured functional ability there are no differences between sexes (Elboim-Gabyzon, Rozen and Laufer, 2012). Therefore, understanding sex differences in the presentation of pain is extremely complex not only due to the influence of many physiological factors associated with chronic pain, but also psychological aspects (i.e. perception of pain). It has already been shown that due to the side effects affecting females, 80% of drugs have been removed from the market as initial drug trials did not investigate sex differences (Novicoff and Saleh, 2011; Petterson et al., 2007). However, only recently have differences in recommendations and treatment based on sex been reported (Borkhoff et al., 2008; Katz et al., 1994; MacDonald et al., 2008; O'Connor and Hooten, 2011; Suarez-Almazor et al., 2005). This finding alone provides a strong rationale for this present study.

Even with access to the many robust and well validated murine models, very few studies have primarily addressed the lack of understanding of sex-specific differences in OA. Therefore, the differences of OA presentation in male and females in 3 different surgically-induced OA murine models were investigated in this chapter.

5.2. Hypothesis

Despite women being more prone to osteoarthritis later in life, this study hypothesises that this sex-related differential does not apply to early OA pathology.

5.3. Aims

To investigate whether there are differential pathological changes in male and female mice at an early time-point in 3 surgically-induced models of OA

5.4. Methods

In this chapter both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* methods were utilised.

OA was induced as previously described (Chapter 2, section 2.1.2.3) on 10 week old adult wild-type C57BL/6 male and female mice (body weight 22-28g; 16-21g), sourced from Envigo, UK. All surgical groups had 8 animals per group. Under aseptic conditions OA was induced via (a) transection of the medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM) (Glasson, Blanchet and Morris, 2007), (b) microblade scratches of articular or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS). Sham operated joints and the contralateral leg of OA-induced mice were used as controls. Animals were maintained for 14 days, with knee joints subsequently harvested for μ CT. At day 14 limb weight bearing was analysed as an indirect measurement of pain using the BioSeb Dynamic Weight Bearing chamber. Due to baseline differences in bone architecture between sexes, and the fact males and females generate bone at different rates as well as differences in gait pattern, subchondral, trabecular and DWB data were expressed as a percentage change with all mice being normalised to their sham controls before comparison between sexes.

5.5. Results

5.5.1. Size and positioning of osteophytes differs between male and females.

Evaluation of osteophyte formation in female experimental groups, although not significant, revealed 3 of 8 mice in the DMM group, 4 of 8 mice in the CS group and 5 of 8 mice in the DCS group presented with 2 or more observable osteophytes, in comparison with sham controls where there was no observation of osteophytogenesis advancing beyond 2 osteophytes (Figure 5.1A). Interestingly, upon quantification osteophytes were reported to be larger in size with more mineralised bone in the CS group (Figure 5.1B,C).

Figure 5.1. Osteophyte development 14 days post-surgery in female C57BL/6 mice. Quantitative data showing (B) osteophyte number (Kruskall-Wallis with Dunn’s multiple comparison) (C) osteophyte tissue volume and (D) bone volume (BV) present in each sample within each surgical group. *p<0.05 compared to sham; n=8.

Although formation of osteophytes in males and females did not show significant differences, notably, 100% of females in the DMM group presented with observable osteophytes, whilst only 5 out of 8 males showed the presence of osteophytogenesis (Figure 5.2A). However, the additive dual injury which was seen to rapidly accelerate osteophyte formation in the male DCS group does not seem applicable to females, with only 2 of 8 female mice presenting with 3 osteophytes in comparison with 5 out of 8 of their male counterparts (Figure 5.2C). Interestingly, females exhibited quantifiably larger osteophyte volume than males (Figure 5.2 D-F). Osteophyte bone volume (BV) did not differ between sexes, however CS females demonstrated an inclination of increased BV (Figure 5.2 G-I).

Figure 5.2. **Comparison of osteophyte formation in male and female C57BL/6 mice.** Quantitative data showing (A-C) osteophyte number (Wilcoxon matched pairs) (D-F) osteophyte tissue volume and (G-I) bone volume (BV/TV) present in each sample within each surgical group. *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001. n=8.

Visualisation of osteophytes by μ CT scans, the positioning of osteophyte formation was observed to differ between males and females in the DCS model. In males, osteophytes are predominantly observed to form off centre to the medial (left-hand) side of the tibia (Figure 5.3E). In comparison, although osteophytes were also present at the medial side of the tibia in females, large osteophyte formation at the anterior (front) of the tibia in many of the female mice was also observed (Figure 5.3F). In addition similar observations in the CS model were noted (Figure 5.3C,D), and although males also present with osteophytes located more centrally on the tibia, they are not to the same extent as witnessed in the female group. In the DMM model, both males and females presented with osteophyte formation at the medial side of the tibia (Figure 5.3A,B). This data would suggest the inflicted cartilage scratches in both CS and DCS groups may potentially influence the positioning of osteophyte formation in females.

Figure 5.3. Comparison of the position of osteophyte formation on the tibia in male and female C57BL/6 mice. Three-dimensional micro CT (μ CT) imaging of developing osteophytes (pink) and subchondral bone formation (blue) following DMM; CS; and DCS in both male and female C57BL/6 mice.

5.5.2. Single-injury alone results in accelerated cartilage damage and synovitis in females.

Histological evaluation of cartilage damage and synovitis in females revealed single-injury damage (DMM) alone can induce significant cartilage damage and synovitis (Figure 5.4A,B,C). Cartilage damage is significantly increased in DMM and DCS models on both the tibia and femur in the medial compartment, however the additive dual-injury does not advance cartilage degradation in females as is observed in males (chapter 3, section 3.5.3). Similar to cartilage damage, synovitis in females is not enhanced with the additive dual injury of the DCS model, DMM alone can provoke significant synovial inflammation (figure 5.4C).

Figure 5.4. Cartilage degradation and synovitis in females 14 days post-surgery. Quantification of (A) medial tibial cartilage damage scores, (B) medial femoral cartilage damage scores, and (C) synovitis scores in female mice following sham, DMM, CS and DCS surgeries. (D) Correlation curve depicting significant correlation between synovitis and cartilage damage. * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$. $n = 8$.

5.5.3. Males and females exhibit similar cartilage degradation and synovitis following dual injury.

Comparison of cartilage damage and synovitis in male and female mice after dual injury (DCS) demonstrates a similar level of degradation and inflammation. Interestingly, following single-injury (DMM), medial tibial cartilage damage in females is significantly higher in females than in males (figure 5.5A). After DMM surgery, female mice present with 'peak' damage score, which does not appear to increase when the additional cartilage scratch is added (DCS). Although not significant, we also see very similar results with both medial femoral cartilage damage scores and synovitis scores (figure 5.5B,C).

Figure 5.5. Cartilage degradation and synovitis in males and females 14 days post-surgery. Quantification of (A) medial tibial cartilage damage scores, (B) medial femoral cartilage damage scores, and (C) synovitis scores following sham, DMM, CS and DCS surgeries.. *** $p \leq 0.001$. $n=8$.

5.5.4. Subchondral osteosclerosis is significantly increased in males.

MicroCT analysis of the subchondral bone revealed females in both experimental groups which involved destabilisation of the joint (DMM and DCS) had a higher level of subchondral bone osteosclerosis (Figure 5.4A). There was no significant subchondral osteosclerosis in females with CS surgery alone, further supporting previous findings in males that the development of osteosclerosis is most likely due to the remodelling of the knee joint to support the altered biomechanical loading pattern.

Figure 5.6. Subchondral bone changes in female C57BL/6 mice 14 days post-surgery. Quantitative data showing (A) subchondral osteosclerosis and (B) changes in trabecular bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) (D) Trabecular BV/TV changes at day 14 post-surgery. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$ compared to sham. $n = 8$.

When quantifying subchondral osteosclerosis in males and females, it is evident male mice experience a much higher and more severe level of osteosclerosis 14 days post-surgery. Although significant osteosclerosis was observed in both female DMM and DCS groups, it was not to the same extent as exhibited by their male counterparts (Figure 5.5B,D). In regards to subchondral bone, males were visually observed to exhibit an increase in subchondral bone formation on the medial side of the knee below where the meniscus has been displaced in models involving joint destabilisation (DMM and DCS) (Figure 5.3A,E). This level of bone formation in the female groups was not observed.

Figure 5.7. Male mice present with accelerated subchondral bone osteosclerosis when compared to females. Quantitative data showing changes in subchondral bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) in male and female C57BL/6 mice 14 days post- (A) sham controls expressed as BV/TV (%) (B) DMM (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery. Values were normalised to their sham controls and expressed as % change to account for baseline differences in male and female bone architecture. *** $p < 0.001$. $n = 8$.

5.5.5. Trabecular BV/TV is significantly increased in males.

No changes in metaphyseal trabecular bone in the operated leg of any of the female experimental groups were observed (Figure 5.6A).

Figure 5.8. Trabecular bone changes in female C57BL/6 mice 14 days post-surgery. Quantitative data showing (A) changes in trabecular bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV). $n = 8$.

Comparison of male and female trabecular bone identified a difference in trabecular BV/TV % in sham mice to be significantly different between sexes (Figure 5.7A), highlighting an existing phenotypic difference in trabecular bone architecture between 'healthy' males and females.

Once male and female values were normalised to sham controls to account for baseline differences in bone architecture between sexes, results were then expressed as a % change of BV/TV. Similarly to subchondral bone results, males were observed to present with a more severe increase in trabecular BV/TV than their female counterparts (Figure 5.7C,D).

Figure 5.9. Male mice present with higher trabecular bone BV/TV. Quantitative data showing changes in trabecular bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) in male and female C57BL/6 mice 14 days post- (A) sham expressed as BV/TV (%) and (B) DMM (C) CS and (D) DCS surgery expressed as a % change normalised to sham controls to account for baseline differences in male and female trabecular bone architecture. ***p<0.001. n=8.

5.5.6. Dual injury does not increase pain-related behaviour in females.

Front paw load was recorded and analysed for all female groups and no significant differences were observed when compared to sham controls (Figure 5.8A). However, front paw load did significantly increase in DCS compared with DMM group. Interestingly, females in the CS group load their operated hind limb significantly more when compared with sham controls (Figure 5.8B), with no other groups exhibiting a difference. Unlike males in the DCS group, the additive dual injury of the DCS model was not observed to significantly alter movement patterns consistent with OA-related pain in the female group (Figure 5.8F).

Given the documented differences of pain manifestation between sexes, OA-related pain in both male and female groups was investigated. Sham controls showed no difference in front paw load between males and females, however females do show a slight trend in decreased front paw load, although not significant (Figure 5.8C). This trend continued to be observed in DMM groups (Figure 5.8D), but CS and DCS groups appear to show very little to no difference between sexes. Results would indicate there are no significant differences in OA-related pain behaviour between male and female mice.

Figure 5.10. Female mice do not present with increased pain-related behaviour as seen in males at 14 days post-surgery. Dynamic weight bearing measurements of the (A) front paw load for female mice following DMM, cartilage damage or DCS surgery and (B) rear left (injured) paw at 14 days post-surgery. Comparison of front paw load between male and female groups following (C) sham; (D) DMM, (E) CS or (F) DCS surgery. OA-induced surgical groups were normalised to sham controls to account for gender gait differences at baseline. **p<0.01; n=8.

5.6. Discussion

Understanding the differences in OA pathogenesis and underlying mechanisms between sexes is extremely important in order to allow for the most appropriate treatment of patients. Few studies have primarily addressed the lack of understanding of sex-specific differences in OA. This study presents a gender comparison of various OA-like pathological changes such as osteophytogenesis, subchondral and trabecular osteosclerosis, and pain-related behaviour in 3 different murine models of OA, both in male and female mice.

In contrast to human studies, the incidence and severity of OA in murine models is higher in males (Ma et al., 2007; Silberberg and Silberberg, 1963a; Silberberg and Silberberg, 1963b; Uchida et al., 2012; van Osch et al., 1993). There are many factors that could contribute to this, such as natural menopause and associated bone changes do not occur in animals other than primates therefore differences in hormones could play a role. Also, it is important to consider the differences in both loading and gait in humans (bipeds) and mice (quadrupeds).

A study by Felson and colleagues reported the tendency of women to have larger osteophytes (Felson et al., 2005), which is consistent with findings of female mice presenting with larger osteophytes when compared to males. It is unknown if osteophyte size or number is the strongest predictor of pain in OA, as pain does not always correlate with the degree of joint injury. With larger osteophytes there is a greater probability of joint function being restricted due to joint space narrowing and formation of bony spurs within the joint. This therefore could potentially impact upon the level of pain experienced by patients due to joint stiffness and reduced range of motion. However, more numerous osteophytes smaller in size could also impact a patient in a similar manner as although they may not protrude as much, a higher number of small osteophytes will cover a larger surface area reducing joint space and range of motion. Also, the protrusion of large osteophytes could cause an imbalance in joint stability depending on the positioning of the spur. This imbalance could result in increased pressure on other joint structures such as ligaments, and potentially lead to further injury or joint destruction, and ultimately an increase in pain. It could be

suggested larger osteophytes will have more impact upon pain levels in OA patients due to their increased protrusion impacting upon other joint structures that smaller osteophytes may not be in contact with, as well as their ability to affect joint stability and range of motion at a more severe level than smaller more numerous osteophytes.

Felson and colleagues also reported the relation of osteophytes to OA progression did not differ by sex (Felson et al., 2005). As mentioned previously (Chapter 3, section 6), osteophyte formation in OA is thought to be a response mechanism to better support the alteration in biomechanical loading by expanding the surface area of the tibial plateau (Wang et al., 2006). Women are known to have smaller knee joints which could provide a rationale as to why larger osteophytes form in women. With a smaller joint there is less tibial surface area to cope with the loading imbalance and pressure of a destabilised joint; therefore larger osteophytes could be required to compensate for the altered biomechanical loading. In addition to osteophyte size and bone volume, interestingly differences in osteophyte positioning on the tibia in male and female mice was also observed, with females in both the CS and DCS groups presenting with more centrally located osteophytes. Again, this difference could be due to knee joint size, structure and different loading patterns between males and females. However, as the female models in which these differences in osteophyte positioning were observed both involved the initial CS surgical injury (CS and DCS), it could be suggested that damage to the cartilage can somehow alter the area in which osteophytes are formed via secreted factors triggered by either the damaged cartilage or bone.

Although increased osteophyte size and mineralisation in females was noted when compared to males, dual injury does not seem to accelerate OA symptoms in the female DCS group as observed in the male DCS group. It was demonstrated that male mice present with extensive cartilage damage on both the femur and tibia in the DCS model (Chapter 3, figure 3.4A-C), and could be hypothesised dual injury exacerbates the breakdown of cartilage possibly via activation of genes which encode for various inflammatory mediators to be secreted within the joint cavity. Investigation into cartilage damage observed in female mice post-DMM, CS and DCS surgery was the next step in understanding

sex-specific differences in OA pathogenesis. Overtime women are observed to present with more cartilage loss in the knee than males (Hanna et al., 2009); this decreased cartilage volume in females is believed to be due to differences in joint surface area and bone size rather than cartilage thickness itself (Faber et al., 2001). Similarly to osteophyte formation, dual injury does not appear to further enhance cartilage damage and synovitis in females as is observed in males when comparing single (DMM) and dual (DCS) injury. This would indicate that a single-injury in females is sufficient to provoke a 'peak' damage response, with females exhibiting a significantly higher level of cartilage damage than their male counterparts post-DMM surgery. This data is in agreement with previous studies, where females presented with more severe cartilage degradation (Park et al., 2018). It is possible sex differences seen in the presentation of cartilage damage in OA may be due to the result of increased articular pressure on a smaller joint surface (Otterness and Eckstein, 2007), with women having a 3-fold increased risk of developing cartilage defects overtime (Ding et al., 2007; Hanna et al., 2009).

Osteosclerosis, which involves an increase in bone density, is a hallmark feature of OA. In WT males a substantial increase in subchondral osteosclerosis was observed as early as day 7 post-surgery (Chapter 3, figure 3.3A,B) with this further increasing at day 14 in DMM and DCS models, thought to be initially triggered by the surgical injury and then accelerated to compensate for the increasing destabilisation of the joint. In females subchondral osteosclerosis was also observed at 14 days post-surgery, but only in DMM and DCS groups, further confirming the importance of joint destabilisation in the development of subchondral osteosclerosis. Differential sex-related architectural bone changes could contribute to the difference in OA incidence. For example, male knee joints have greater subchondral bone area compared to females (Otterness and Eckstein, 2007) and would explain why a greater and more severe increase in subchondral bone density in male groups was identified when compared to female groups. Also, the rate at which bone is remodelled in males and females also differs, with males generating bone at a faster pace than females which could also explain the increased level of osteosclerosis observed in male mice.

Regarding trabecular bone changes, little to no differences in BV/TV were reported when surgical groups were compared within each sex. However, there is a significant difference between male and female trabecular BV/TV, with females exhibiting a lower trabecular bone density than their male counterparts. This observation is not only seen in OA-induced surgical groups but also sham controls, indicating an already significant difference in trabecular bone architecture that precedes any OA-like bone changes that may develop. This adds strength to the hypothesis that differences in male and female OA presentation could be strongly linked to differences in the anatomy of the male and female knee joint.

Krug and colleagues observed arthritic female mice to spend a significantly greater percentage of time, as well as increased loading of their front paws, at 4 weeks post-surgery when compared to control (non-arthritic) mice (Krug, Blanshan and Frizelle, 2017). This finding supports human studies in which females are typically seen to present with greater pain and disability (Cho et al., 2010; McAlindon et al., 1992a). However, findings in this study are contradictory, with all experimental female groups presenting with similar front paw loading as their male counterparts, suggesting they are not experiencing any greater level of discomfort and pain. A previous study by Park *et al.* also presented with no significant difference in pain between sexes post-DMM surgery (Park et al., 2018). In human studies the level of pain does not always correlate with the degree of joint injury, with many patients still reporting discomfort and pain after arthroplasty. There is no general consensus in the literature on sex-related differences in pain level intensity reported by patients, and studies regarding sex-related functional abilities are inconsistent (Belo et al., 2007; de Klerk et al., 2009). Sex differences were reported in patients when analysing results based upon self-reported pain and functional ability. However, when testing actual functional ability, no differences were observed between males and females (Maleki-Fischbach and Jordan, 2010). This implicates physiological differences based upon perception of pain and functional ability between sexes, further adding to the multifactorial reasoning underlying the sex differences observed in OA.

5.7. Conclusion

The synergistic effects of dual cartilage injury and joint destabilisation observed in male mice were not witnessed in females to the same extent. Results indicate that although females show an increase in both osteophyte size and mineralisation (often related with increased pain) they do not display altered biomechanical loading indicative of OA-like pain as observed in males, contrary to much of the literature. This study has clearly established that sex-differences are present in OA-pathogenesis, however, the mechanism behind these differences have not been elucidated. Increasing our understanding of the mechanisms underlying sex differences in the pathophysiology of OA is instrumental in the development of effective treatments, with the potential of sex specific strategies and therapeutics. Further investigation into longer time points, as well as inducing OA in older female mice would be beneficial in understanding the time point at which females switch from presenting with less severe to more severe OA symptoms than their male counterparts. This could then provide clinics with a timeframe of when best to treat female OA patients before the disease becomes exacerbated by possible hormonal changes at a later stage in life.

Chapter 6

General Discussion

Despite much research, the pathogenesis of OA and PTOA is still not fully understood, nor is the influence of sex on the development of OA. Accordingly, this thesis sought to address and investigate these topics.

Firstly, this involved design and development of a novel and reproducible dual injury murine model of OA (DCS model), involving simultaneous cartilage damage and joint destabilisation, which successfully recapitulates PTOA observed in humans.

There is increasing evidence that joint tissue interactions play a significant role in driving OA progression (Findlay and Kuliwaba, 2016; Macchi et al., 2018; Miyaki and Lotz, 2018; Yuan et al., 2014), providing a strong rationale for the development and utilisation of this new model in OA research – particularly in the context of joint trauma resulting in extensive injury (as occurs in PTOA).

Cartilage damage has been the main focus of research in OA and is well-known to accelerate disease progression (van der Kraan and van den Berg, 2012). Results presented in Chapter 3 are consistent with this finding as data supports the synergistic effects of dual cartilage injury and joint destabilisation in accelerating OA-pathogenesis with the observation of significantly larger osteophytes, increased cartilage degradation and synovitis, and increased pain-related behaviour.

There is a strong relationship between pathological changes in articular cartilage and changes in the underlying subchondral bone (Ferrell et al., 2010), with the growth of blood vessels from the subchondral bone into the cartilage facilitating OA progression (Walsh, 2004). Again, this finding is demonstrated in the DCS model with the observable cartilage vascularisation. Only recently have researchers considered OA to possess an inflammatory component, with synovitis being considered a pivotal player in pathogenesis of OA, rather than a secondary process in response to the damage of other joint tissues. Synovitis has been linked with increased pain in OA patients (Roemer et al., 2010a), and the DCS model recapitulates these findings by demonstrating a positive correlation between synovitis development and increased pain-related behaviour. Therefore it can be concluded that the concomitant joint instability and cartilage injury which typify knee joint traumatic injury predispose to accelerated OA progression.

Although the DCS model was developed for the purpose of investigating PTOA in this thesis, it has potential value to other research areas. Results presented in chapter 3 provide insight into utilising this dual injury model in various other contexts such as an inflammation, pain or bone-focused research. The DCS model generates reproducible synovitis, and therefore presents a means to specifically elucidate the role and implications of synovitis and inflammation within the knee joint. Osteophyte formation is accelerated and more extensive in this dual injury model and would allow for investigation at an earlier time-point compared with other models such as DMM and ACLT. This has important benefit to welfare issues and finance. Osteosclerosis is significantly accelerated in this model, providing the potential of interrogating the mechanisms behind bone changes within the joint in a shorter time frame. Furthermore the enhanced pain-related behaviour in DCS provides a robust model for *in vivo* investigation of joint pain. The ability to investigate pain in the DCS model is of importance as pain is considered the primary issue affecting joint function and quality of life in OA patients. Taken together this highlights the versatility of the DCS model and the breadth of potential uses in future research.

When developing the DCS model, the majority of surgeries were performed by a single operator; however, a second operator was responsible for a small remainder of surgeries. This introduced potential operator-dependent differences into results. Error bars were carefully analysed to test for operator variability, with no apparent differences observed. The best approach to ensure operator quality control across different operators in the induction of DCS, would be to quantify the dimension of cartilage injury i.e. depth and spacing. This was attempted using histological analysis, however due to the 2D nature of histological slides as well as slight differences in orientation when embedding samples, this made quantifying the quality of cartilage scratches difficult and therefore unable to perform effective comparisons between samples. Currently there is no established 3D method to measure cartilage volume, thickness, as well as examine and quantify the extent of cartilage damage at the microscopic level. The development of such a technique allowing 3D visualisation and analysis of cartilage would provide extremely beneficial in understanding the

involvement of articular cartilage in OA pathogenesis. MicroCT was employed to analyse the bone micro-architecture (Chappard et al., 2006), as well as investigating subchondral bone changes in OA (Pita et al., 1970). The utilisation of μ CT scanners to provide 3D quantification and analysis of cartilage properties is an extremely novel and beneficial future development and would allow for simultaneous measurement of both the articular cartilage and subchondral bone in the same dataset, improving knowledge of the relationship between both these tissues in OA development. . Over the last decade, there has been an increase in the novel development of high-resolution, non-destruction, 3D imaging protocols for articular cartilage assessment (Gu et al., 2012; Kotwal et al., 2012; Ruan et al., 2013; Stok and Müller, 2009). The use of radiopaque staining agents can allow for high accuracy visualisation of soft tissues by μ CT. (Johnson et al., 2006; Metscher, 2009; Pauwels et al., 2013). Das Neves Borges *et al.* utilised phosphotungstic acid (PTA) contrast enhanced μ CT (PTA-CT). PTA is an effective contrast agent to image soft tissues by μ CT (Metscher, 2009; Pauwels et al., 2013), revealing collagenous structures (Constantine and Mowry, 1968). PTA-CT imaging provides a fast and accurate method to assess cartilage morphology, with the ability to locate OA lesions and apply a quantitative approach to determine OA severity. This advancement in technique will allow for a better understanding of the OA process, as well as deciphering the complex relationship between articular cartilage and subchondral bone in the context of OA disease progression.

As the DCS murine model is accessible to genetic manipulation, it allowed for comprehensive evaluation of disease-related changes in relevant joint tissues in PAR2 KO mice, leading to the second finding of this doctoral thesis: PAR2 was found to accelerate OA-like changes (Chapter 4). Results in Chapter 4 were not normalised against the contralateral leg for control purposes as this study was intended to provide proof of concept and determine if there were significant changes to indicate a strong rationale for further more in-depth analysis. Instead, sham controls were used. However, an interesting finding by Poulet and colleagues indicated both gait and epiphyseal trabecular mass exhibited significant changes in the contralateral leg, highlighting the importance of using appropriate controls in such studies (Poulet et al., 2015).

PAR2 has previously been shown to play a pivotal role in osteophyte formation during OA progression in the DMM model (Huesa et al., 2016), and has now further been demonstrated to significantly accelerate osteophytogenesis in the dual injury DCS model. PAR2 disruption was observed to alter the progression of osteophyte formation over a 14 day time-period, suggesting the therapeutic potential of PAR2 antagonism. As osteophytes have been linked with increased pain in patients with OA (Boegard et al., 1998), therapeutic targeting of PAR2 could protect against osteophytogenesis, as well as potentially alleviating joint pain in patients.

PAR2 activation induces production of inflammatory cytokines and MMPs by osteoblasts in the subchondral bone, with these factors then acting upon the overlying chondrocytes in the articular cartilage (Amiable et al., 2009). In the DCS model, loss of PAR2 appears to offer protection against cartilage degradation, similar to previous findings in the DMM model (Ferrell et al., 2010; Huesa et al., 2016). In OA, future therapeutic approaches should target not only reduction in cartilage degradation, but also the subchondral bone remodelling process. This study, and others (Amiable et al., 2011; Ferrell et al., 2010; Huesa et al., 2016), suggest PAR2 could act on these 2 different articular tissues. Future investigation utilising murine models with tissue-specific loss of PAR2 expression in bone would provide further insight into the relationship between PAR2, cartilage and bone changes observed in OA pathology. Thus, in view of the overall results, PAR2 could be involved in early-stage OA (e.g. 14-28 days) and possibly in later stage OA. However, to confirm this, a study of longer duration (e.g. 8+ weeks) is necessary.

A limitation of this study is the use of non-littermate controls. Littermate controls ensure that both epigenetic- and environmental-caused variability is minimal. The utilisation of non-littermate controls in studies involving transgenic and KO mice introduce the potential for phenotypic variability that reflect differences in genetic and environmental backgrounds, and could lead to discrepancies in results between groups. However Cre expression can also vary within littermates (Heffner et al., 2012), therefore littermate controls do not abrogate all variability. Utilising true littermate controls may not always be feasible due to time constraints or availability of animals. In

this study appropriate controls were used in replacement of littermate controls, and data has been analysed and interpreted with the knowledge that results may differ due to genetic variability.

There is no known cure for OA, only treatments to alleviate symptoms, with analgesics, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and COX-2 drugs being the most widely used therapeutics (Amiable et al., 2011). However, to date, these drugs have not proven to reduce the joint destruction modifications that occur during the OA process, therefore there is a need to identify new potential therapeutic targets able to arrest disease progression which would spare articular tissues and prevent symptoms including pain, swelling and inflammation. PAR2 has been suggested as a crucial checkpoint mediating the effect of biomechanical instability leading to cartilage damage, synovitis and associated bone changes (Ferrell et al., 2010; Huesa et al., 2016). Now the challenge is to develop potent and selective agents to prevent PAR2 activation. PAR2 has been the focus of pharmaceutical research, however this has proved challenging (Ferrell, Lockhart and Plevin, 2008). Biological therapies have been investigated, however they require combined administration with disease-modifying-antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs), and some patients do not respond to this type of therapy. This indicates that a biologic approach may not be as successful as initially anticipated. A genomic approach has also been suggested involving small interfering Ribonucleic Acid (siRNA) to target the receptor (Kelso et al., 2006), although this approach would require a viral or other type of vector to be administered to optimise the efficacy. Furthermore, inhibiting serine proteases was considered to have promising therapeutic potential with tryptase presenting as the most likely candidate. However, the effectiveness of this approach is limited by the fact other serine proteases activate PAR2 (Uehara et al., 2003), potentially leading to exacerbated OA-like symptoms. Low-molecular-weight orally active compounds and small molecule PAR2 antagonists seem to be the focus of therapeutic PAR2 research in OA. Initially, the discovery of small-molecule antagonists proved challenging with many demonstrating to be less than successful; for instance, GD88 presented as a weak antagonist. However, recently the crystal structure of PAR2 was published leading to the formation of two distinct PAR2 antagonists and blocking antibody (Cheng et al., 2017).

AZ8838 provides promising potential as a therapeutic target due to the slow binding kinetics the compound exhibits, and AZ23451 is found to bind to a remote allosteric site outside of the helical bundle, also providing as an attractive PAR2 antagonist. Future work assessing the effect of AZ8838 and AZ23451 antagonists on the dual injury DCS model presented in this study would provide useful in furthering our understanding of PAR2 in the development of PTOA. The discovery of PAR2's crystal structure, as well as the antagonists, is a major therapeutic development as it provides a solid basis for the advancement of future effective PAR2 antagonists to be utilised in therapeutic treatment of OA. Ultimately, only clinical studies in OA patients will determine the therapeutic value of PAR2 inhibition in the treatment of OA. However, previous data combined with findings in this doctoral study strongly highlight the potential of PAR2 as a pharmacological target in the abrogation of OA pathology.

The final question this doctoral thesis sought to address was the effect of sex on OA. Sex bias in research has been highlighted with many studies favouring the utilisation of male mice in experiments, often leading to widespread application of results without investigation of potential sex differences (Beery and Zucker, 2011; Holdcroft, 2007). This is an increasingly important topic as 80% of OA drugs have been removed from market due to side effects on females (Novicoff and Saleh, 2011; Petterson et al., 2007), with sex-specific treatment of OA recently being recommended (Borkhoff et al., 2008; Katz et al., 1994; MacDonald et al., 2008; O'Connor and Hooten, 2011; Suarez-Almazor et al., 2005). The male bias in preclinical animal trials can lead to important biological findings being missed or misinterpreted due to intrinsic genetic and hormonal differences between sexes. The US National Institute of Health now requires all grant applicants to account for both sexes of chosen animal model to be included in their research proposal. However, the inclusion of both male and female mice to control sex bias in research will not ensure direct translation of results to human trials. This is observed in Chapter 5 with female mice demonstrating less severe OA than their male counterparts, however in human studies women present with greater OA severity than

males. Various animal studies have described this same finding (Silberberg and Silberberg, 1963a; Silberberg and Silberberg, 1963b; Sokoloff, 1956; Uchida et al., 2012; van Osch et al., 1993).

The results presented in Chapter 5 provide convincing evidence that sex plays a role in the pathogenesis of OA, and is an extremely important factor to consider when developing future treatments. Females have been observed to manifest OA differently from males, with certain areas of the knee being disproportionately affected (Felson et al., 1995; Hanna et al., 2009; McAlindon et al., 1992a; O'Connor, 2007). Results presented in Chapter 5 are consistent with this finding as osteophyte size and positioning was observed to affect female knee joints differently from their male counterparts. Females present with larger and more anterior osteophyte formation on the tibia in the DCS model, potentially to compensate for the smaller joint size having less tibial surface area to cope with the loading imbalance.

Another factor contributing to female mice being underrepresented in biomedical research is based upon the presumption of increased variability in females compared to males due to intrinsic differences (e.g. oestrous cycle). However, in most rodent species, females display no more variation than males. Hormonal differences have been implicated in the presentation and progression of OA between sexes. In humans before the age of 50, OA is more prevalent in males (Ma et al., 2007). However, over the age of 50 this paradigm shifts, with post-menopausal females presenting with a higher prevalence of OA as well as greater pain and disability (McAlindon et al., 1992a; O'Connor, 2007; O'Connor and Hooten, 2011; Thomas, Pagura and Kennedy, 2003). Post-menopausal women have decreased levels of oestrogen, and there is increasing evidence to suggest oestrogen plays a role in the development of OA. Joint tissues are known to contain oestrogen receptors with the hormone contributing to the protection joint structure, function and lubrication (Braidman et al., 2001; Dietrich et al., 2006; Sciore, Frank and Hart, 1998; Ushiyama et al., 1999). Hormone replacement therapy (HRT) replenishes the oestrogen deficiency in females post-menopause and it has been suggested HRT could improve symptoms of OA. Radiological evidence has suggested HRT provides a protective effect in the knee joint with a 3 fold reduction in risk of OA (Spector et al.,

1997b). The effect of HRT on joints of the hand was weaker. However, although promising, long-term (>5 years) HRT usage does carry an increased risk of developing breast cancer (Steinberg et al., 1994). Furthermore, HRT must be initiated at an optimal time (up to ~60 years of age, or the first 10 years of menopause) (Jung et al., 2018).

Therefore, as stated previously, investigation into longer time points as well as inducing OA in older female mice would be advantageous in better understanding the time point at which females switch from presenting with less severe to more severe OA symptoms than their male counterparts. This would provide invaluable insight into the most effective time-frame to administer treatment specific to male and female patients.

In conclusion, the development of the novel and robust DCS model provides the OA research field with a powerful new tool to investigate PTOA pathogenesis at an earlier time-point. This is due to the model recapitulating accelerated onset of OA-like features such as osteophytogenesis, synovitis, cartilage degradation, osteosclerosis and pain-related behaviour. Furthermore, the ability of DCS surgery to be induced in transgenic mice allows researchers to investigate and understand specific pathogenic pathways leading to OA. PAR2 was demonstrated to further accelerate OA-like joint changes, highlighting the receptor as an attractive therapeutic target in the abrogation of OA pathology. Finally, sex was exhibited to be an important factor in the differential development and presentation of OA in males and females. This finding provides a strong rationale for sex-specific treatment of OA, however further research must be carried out to identify the mechanisms underlying sex differences in the pathophysiology of OA.

Appendix I

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Appendix II

Supplementary Data

A

Sham

B

Appendix II Figure 1. Osteophyte development 14 days post-surgery in sham control. (A) Three-dimensional micro CT (μ CT) imaging of a sham control showing no observable developing osteophytes and (B) corresponding sagittal plane images.

Appendix II Figure 2. Synovitis present in male WT mice 14 days post-surgery. Histological appearance of the synovial lining of the knee joint 14 days following (A) DMM, (B) cartilage damage ad (C) DCS surgery showing pannus formation (green arrow), synovial hyperplasia (red arrow), sub-synovial hyperplasia (black arrow) and subchondral bone/osteophyte formation (blue arrow).

Appendix II Figure 3. Cartilage degradation in WT male mice at 28 days post-surgery. Quantification of (A) medial tibial cartilage damage and (B) medial femoral cartilage damage. Using Original OARSI cartilage scoring system without modification for cartilage remodelling or vascularisation properties **p<0.01.

Appendix II Figure 4. Synovitis present in male WT mice 28 days post-surgery. Histological appearance of the synovial lining of the knee joint 28 days following (A) DMM, (B) cartilage damage ad (C) DCS surgery showing pannus formation (green arrow), synovial hyperplasia (red arrow) and sub-synovial hyperplasia (black arrow).

Appendix III

Publications (papers)

Osteoarthritis and Cartilage

Accelerated post traumatic osteoarthritis in a dual injury murine model

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SUMMARY

Objective: Joint injury involving destabilisation of the joint and damage to the articular cartilage (e.g., sports-related injury) can result in accelerated post-traumatic osteoarthritis (PTOA). Destabilised medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM) surgery is one of the most commonly used murine models and whilst it recapitulates Osteoarthritis (OA) pathology, it does not necessarily result in multi-tissue injury, as occurs in PTOA. We hypothesised that simultaneous cartilage damage and joint destabilisation would accelerate the onset of OA pathology.

Methods: OA was induced in C57BL/6 mice via (a) DMM, (b) microblade scratches of articular cartilage (CS) or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS). Mice were culled 7, 14 and 28 days post-surgery. Microcomputed tomography (μ CT) and histology were used to monitor bone changes and inflammation. Dynamic weight bearing, an indirect measure of pain, was assessed on day 14.

Results: Osteophytogenesis analysis via μ CT revealed that osteophytes were present in all groups at days 7 and 14 post-surgery. However, in DCS, osteophytes were visually larger and more numerous when compared with DMM and cartilage scratch (CS). Histological assessment of cartilage at day 14 and 28, revealed significantly greater damage in DCS compared with DMM and CS. Furthermore, a significant increase in synovitis was observed in DCS. Finally, at day 14 osteophyte numbers correlated with changes in dynamic weight bearing.

Conclusion: Joint destabilisation when combined with simultaneous cartilage injury accelerates joint deterioration, as seen in PTOA. Thus, DCS provides a novel and robust model for investigating multiple pathological hallmarks, including osteophytogenesis, cartilage damage, synovitis and OA-related pain.

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Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) is globally the most prevalent musculoskeletal disease.¹ OA is characterised by significant structural changes in joint tissues such as articular cartilage degradation, osteophyte formation

(bony outgrowths), subchondral osteosclerosis, epiphyseal bone expansion, synovitis and pannus formation. Although OA is often associated with increasing age, an accelerated progression is recognised in individuals suffering previous (often sport-related) joint injury involving multi-tissue damage. Notably, 66% of patients presenting with articular surface damage in their joints progressed towards OA.^{2,3} Furthermore, current data suggests that patients with chronic OA who suffered an earlier articular trauma are, upon diagnosis, >10 years younger than those patients with no history of joint injury.⁴ Taken together, post-traumatic OA (PTOA), as characterised by accelerated joint degeneration, pain and dysfunction, accounts for ~12% of all OA cases.⁵

Lapine models used to investigate PTOA resulting from multi-tissue joint injury, usually involve traumatic rupture of the

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anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) and damage of surrounding tissues including the meniscus via mechanical impact on the patellofemoral joint.^{6–8} These have yielded valuable insight into PTOA progression, but involve relatively undefined and uncontrolled damage to various joint tissues. In comparison, surgically-induced murine models that develop OA-like pathology include the destabilised medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM) model and anterior cruciate ligament transection (ACLT) murine model. While both recapitulate features of OA pathology, these do not arise directly from an initial multi-tissue injury, as occurs in PTOA. This may be an important limitation, as increasing evidence suggests that joint tissue interactions may play a significant role in driving disease progression.^{9–12} Alternative murine models include articular injection of agents that induce inflammation and/or tissue toxicity/damage, but questions remain as to how well these represent the joint damage seen in OA.¹³ To better understand accelerated OA progression, what is needed is a murine model that combines joint destabilisation with defined/controlled joint tissue injury, and is accessible to genetic manipulation, while enabling comprehensive evaluation of disease-related changes in relevant joint tissues (e.g., cartilage, bone, meniscus). The present study is the first to present a dual injury murine model involving simultaneous cartilage damage and joint destabilisation, and was developed to test our focused hypothesis that concomitant cartilage damage and joint instability accelerates the onset of OA pathology as seen in PTOA.

Methods

Animals

Experiments were performed on 10 week old adult 22–28 g wild-type C57BL/6 male mice (Envigo, UK). Mice were housed at the University of Glasgow or University of the West of Scotland and maintained under standard animal husbandry conditions in accordance with UK home office regulations. All procedures were performed in accordance with UK Home Office Regulations, and with study approval by Animal Welfare Ethical Review Boards at the University of Glasgow and the University of the West of Scotland.

Induction of OA

OA was induced by one operator (to minimise surgical variability) under aseptic conditions via (a) transection of the medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM)¹⁴, (b) microblade scratches of articular cartilage [cartilage scratch (CS); Supplemental Fig. 1(A)] or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS) [Supplemental Fig. 1(B)]. Three CSes were made only to the superficial cartilage on the medial side of the tibia underneath the medial meniscotibial ligament (MML) using a single use size 11 microblade (Swann-Morton), as indicated in Supplemental Fig. 1. DMM was carried out prior to CSes in the DCS model, with all surgeries lasting 10 ± 2 min. Buprenorphine (Vetergesic; 30 µg intraperitoneally) was administered pre-operatively. 2% oxygen and 2% Isoflurane (Isoflurane Vet, Merial) was used to anaesthetise animals throughout the surgical procedures. Animals were maintained for 7, 14 and 28 days, with knee joints subsequently harvested for µCT and histological analysis. Sham operated joints of OA-induced mice were used as controls.

Microcomputed tomography (µCT)

Knee joints were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde solution for 24 h, then transferred to 70% EtOH and analysed by µCT to examine the calcified tissues using a Skyscan 1272 µCT scanner (Bruker,

Belgium; 0.5 aluminium filter, 50 kV, 200 µA). Samples were scanned at voxel size 4.5 µm, 0.5° rotation angle for quantification, and 2 µm, 0.2° rotation angle for imaging [Fig. 2(A); Fig. 3(A)&(B)]. Scans were reconstructed in NRecon software (Bruker, Belgium). Osteophytes were identified in the resulting three-dimensional image stacks using CTvol software (Bruker, Belgium) and then number of osteophytes per joint counted. Osteophyte bone volume was measured by manually delineating the edge of osteophytes protruding from the subchondral plate as the region of interest (ROI) for analysis, and quantified for bone volume using CTan software (Bruker, Belgium). Subchondral bone was analysed by selecting a volume of interest (VOI) of $0.5 \times 0.9 \times 0.9$ mm³ in the centre of load in the medial and lateral tibial plateau.¹⁵ ROIs (medial and lateral) delineating the trabecular structure within the tibial epiphysis were selected in the 2D coronal view of the stack to analyse the bone volume and microarchitecture using CTAn.

Histological assessment of cartilage damage and synovitis

Joints were decalcified overnight (Formical 2000; Decal Chemical, New York, USA) and embedded in paraffin wax. Coronal sections (6 µm) were cut and then stained with haematoxylin, safranin-O/fast green. Using a validated scoring system¹⁴ ranging from 0 (normal) to 6 (>80% loss of cartilage), severity of cartilage damage was assessed histologically on joints previously scanned for micro computed tomography (µCT). Two scorers blinded to the specimens, scored the medial tibial quadrant in 4–6 sections from each mouse. We did not include initial cartilage lesions inflicted by microblade scratches in both cartilage damage and DCS models in our scoring. Synovitis was assessed by two blinded scorers using a recently developed scoring system¹⁶ which we modified from the original to focus only on pannus formation, synovial membrane thickening and sub-synovial hyperplasia. For both scoring systems, there was good agreement between scorers with intraclass correlation coefficient for cartilage scoring of 0.96 (95% CI 0.92 to 0.98), and synovitis scoring of 0.83; (95% CI 0.65 to 0.92).

dynamic weight bearing

As an indirect measurement of pain, limb weight bearing was assessed in mice 14 days after surgery using the BioSeb Dynamic Weight Bearing (DWB) chamber (BioSeb, Marseilles, France). All animals were individually recorded for 5 min, 1 min of which was validated and subsequently analysed. The parameters examined were load on ipsilateral (injured) hind paw and load on front paws.

Statistical analysis

Prism 6 (Graphpad) was used to perform statistical analysis. For normally distributed data, analysis involved one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple comparisons using Bonferroni correction. Student *t*-tests were also used. Data not normally distributed was analysed by Kruskal–Wallis one-way ANOVA and multiple comparisons using Dunn's corrections. Linear regression curves were generated and Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) was used to assess strength of relationship. *P* values less than 0.05 were considered significant.

Results

Accelerated osteophyte development after dual injury

Evaluation of osteophyte formation at an early timepoint (7 days post-surgery) revealed that although osteophytes could be detected in some mice within each of the experimental groups [Fig. 1(A)

Fig. 1. Osteophyte development 7 days post-surgery. (A) Three-dimensional microCT (μ CT) imaging of developing osteophytes (arrows) following Destabilised medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM); cartilage damage; and DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS) in C57BL/6 mice. Quantitative data showing (B) osteophyte number (C) osteophyte tissue volume and (D) % of bone within osteophyte (bone volume/tissue volume, BV/TV) present in each sample within each surgical group. ** $P < 0.01$; $n = 8$. DMM; cartilage scratch (CS); DCS.

and (B)] there was an increase in detectable osteophytes in the DCS model. Notably, in the DCS group 6 out of 8 mice had observable osteophytes whilst only 3 out of 8 mice in the DMM and CS showed signs of osteophytogenesis [Fig. 1(B)]. Moreover, at day 7 the osteophytes in the DCS group were quantifiably larger in size [Fig. 1(C)] and in some mice more numerous [Fig. 1(B)]. In comparison, the DMM group osteophytes were reduced in both number and volume [Fig. 1(B) and (C)]. Analysis of osteophyte BV/TV at day 7 did not show any detectable increased bone volume across any of the three experimental groups [Fig. 1(D)].

To determine how these osteophytes develop over time in these models, we investigated osteophyte morphology and structural characteristics at day 14. In the DMM group, arboreal-like osteophytes were observable in 6 out of 8 mice, whilst in the CS and DCS mice, 100% of mice exhibited osteophytes [Fig. 2(A),(B) and (C)]. Importantly, at this time point, DCS mice had significantly more osteophytes than the DMM and CS groups [Fig. 2(C)], with a minimum of two observable osteophytes. However, 5 out of 8 DCS mice

presented with 3 osteophytes per joint [Fig. 2(C)]. In comparison, both DMM and CS alone animals presented a maximum of two osteophytes, which were only seen in 3 out of 8 of mice in each group [Fig. 2(C)]. Both CS and DCS groups exhibited significantly larger osteophyte volume compared to DMM and sham groups [Fig. 2(C)]. However, the percentage of bone volume within these osteophytes did not differ significantly between experimental model groups [Fig. 2(E)].

Dual injury promotes subchondral osteosclerosis

Analysis was undertaken to investigate the impact of DMM, CS and DCS on the subchondral bone. At day 7, μ CT analysis showed an increase of subchondral osteosclerosis in all 3 OA models when compared with sham controls [Fig. 3(A)]. At day 14 the level of subchondral osteosclerosis in the CS group remained constant, however there was a further increase in subchondral BV/TV in both DMM and DCS models; possibly due to joint instability and

Fig. 2. Osteophyte development 14 days post-surgery. (A) Three-dimensional μ CT imaging of developing osteophytes (arrows) following DMM; cartilage damage; and DCS in C57BL/6 mice, and (B) corresponding sagittal plane images. Quantitative data showing accelerated osteophytogenesis in the DCS model exhibited by (C) osteophyte number (Kruskal–Wallis with Dunn's multiple comparison); (D) total osteophyte volume (Student's *t*-test), (E) % of bone present within osteophytes. **P* < 0.05; ***P* < 0.01; ****P* < 0.001; *n* = 8. DMM, DMM; CS, DCS.

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Fig. 3. Subchondral osteosclerosis is evident at day 7 post-surgery with increased trabecular bone volume at day 14. (A) Day 7 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis. (B) Day 14 post-surgery subchondral osteosclerosis. (C) Changes in trabecular bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) at day 7. (D) Trabecular BV/TV changes at day 14 post-surgery. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ (without bar is cf. Sham); $n = 6-8$. DMM; CS; DCS.

increased biomechanical loading [Fig. 3(B)]. There were no observable differences in metaphyseal trabecular bone in the ipsilateral (injured) leg at day 7 post-surgery [Fig. 3(C)]. However, at day 14, DCS mice exhibited a significant increase in trabecular BV/TV in the injured leg [Fig. 3(D)].

Dual injury increases cartilage degradation and synovitis

While cartilage damage and/or synovitis were not normally detectable at day 14 post-induction, we sought to investigate whether these might emerge in the DCS model at this early time-point as an indicator of accelerated PTOA. Histological analysis of the medial compartment of the knee joint at 14 days following DMM, CS or DCS surgery was performed. Over and above the initial scratch-induced cartilage damage, we found significant further cartilage degradation in the DCS model on the tibia when compared with DMM and CS models [Fig. 4(A)–(D)]. Consistent with this finding we also observed increased cartilage degradation on the femur in the DCS model compared with DMM and CS models [Fig. 4(E)]. Furthermore, although there was observable synovitis in the DMM and CS groups, there was a significant increase in synovitis in the DCS model [Fig. 4(F)]. Correlation analysis revealed a strong relationship between cartilage damage and synovitis levels ($\rho = 0.77$, $P = 0.0004$) [Fig. 4(G)], as well as between cartilage damage and osteophyte number ($\rho = 0.59$, $P = 0.003$) [Fig. 4(H)]. Synovitis also positively correlated with the number of osteophytes present ($\rho = 0.49$, $P = 0.02$) [Fig. 4(I)]. In addition, we sought to investigate if accelerated cartilage damage and synovitis in the DCS model persists at 28 days post-surgery [Fig. 5(A)–(C)]. Notably, both increased cartilage damage in the medial tibia and femur [Fig. 5(D) and (E)] and synovitis [Fig. 5(F)] was observed in the DCS group at 28 days post-surgery. Moreover, we also observed remodelling of the cartilage at day 28 in the DCS model [Fig. 5(C)], a feature linked with increasing severity of OA pathology.¹⁷ Taken together this indicates that DMM combined with CS promotes an acute inflammatory environment with progressive and accelerated

cartilage degradation, remodelling and enhanced osteophytogenesis

Osteophyte number and cartilage damage correlate with pain-related behaviour

Prior work by Huesa *et al.* has shown that DWB can be used to monitor pain-related behaviour.¹⁸ Fourteen days post-surgery, mice in the DCS group demonstrated a significant loss of loading on their ipsilateral (injured) leg when compared with DMM alone [Fig. 6(A)]. No significance was observed in load on the contralateral (non-injured) hind limb between all groups. Consistent with this, mice in the DCS group also demonstrated a significant increase in front paw load compared with the other models [Fig. 6(B)], indicating an increase in OA-related pain. Importantly, there was a strong positive correlation between osteophyte number and front paw load at this time point ($\rho = 0.65$, $P = 0.0004$) [Fig. 6(C)]. Suggesting that the severity of OA-related pain may be related to the extent of osteophytogenesis. As we observed a positive correlation between osteophyte number and both cartilage damage and synovitis, we further investigated these parameters in relation to OA-pain related behaviour: however, neither cartilage damage nor synovitis exhibited a significant correlation with increase front paw load ($\rho = 0.35$, $P = 0.09$ and $\rho = 0.28$, $P = 0.19$ respectively).

Discussion

Trauma to the joint is known to promote early osteoarthritis, but the mechanisms for accelerated disease are not well understood. This study presents a novel dual injury murine model to address the important question of whether concomitant joint destabilisation and defined cartilage damage leads to early OA characterised by progressive cartilage destruction, osteophytogenesis, synovitis and pain.

Critical to model selection and/or development, is the specific research hypothesis being addressed; and how translatable these

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Fig. 4. Cartilage degradation and synovitis 14 days post-surgery. Histological appearance of the medial compartment of the knee joint 14 days following (A) DMM (B) Cartilage damage or (C) DCS, showing pannus formation (green arrow), synovial hyperplasia (red arrow), sub-synovial hyperplasia (black arrow) and Subchondral bone/osteophyte formation (blue arrow). Scale bar – 200 μ m. Cartilage damage scores for the (D) medial tibial and (E) medial femur, and (F) Synovitis scores in mice following DMM, cartilage damage or DCS surgery at 14 days post-surgery. Correlation curves depicting significant correlations between (G) cartilage damage and synovitis; (H) osteophyte number and cartilage damage; (I) osteophyte number and synovitis. 95% confidence intervals are indicated by dotted lines. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$; $n = 8$. DMM; CS; DCS.

findings are to human OA. There are various well-established and widely used experimental models of OA across a range of species. While none are ideal in modelling human disease, Little and colleagues have identified preferred characteristics, which include

recapitulating human joint disease in a manner amenable for measurement and monitoring, and within a reasonable time frame.¹⁹ Model types range from surgical induction and traumatic injury, to chemical induction methods, each with their strengths

Fig. 5. Cartilage degradation and synovitis 28 days post-surgery. Histological appearance of the medial compartment of the knee joint 28 days following (A) DMM (B) cartilage damage or (C) DCS, showing pannus formation (green arrow), synovial hyperplasia (red arrow), sub-synovial hyperplasia (black arrow) and subchondral bone/osteophyte formation (blue arrow). Scale bar = 200 μ m. Cartilage damage scores for the (D) medial tibial and (E) medial femur, and (F) synovitis scores in mice following DMM, cartilage damage or DCS surgery at 14 days post-surgery. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$. DMM, DMM; CS, CS; DCS, DCS.

and limitations. For example, blunt trauma results in relatively undefined multi-tissue injuries, surgical approaches risk surgical artefact whilst chemical approaches such as intra-articular injection of monoiodoacetate (MIA) likely evoke joint changes by mechanisms different from those underpinning OA.

Murine models are important tools for research on various human diseases, and for OA, one of the most widely used is the DMM surgical induction model generated by Glasson *et al.*¹⁴ This induces joint instability and recapitulates the cartilage damage, osteosclerosis, osteophyteogenesis and pain that characterise OA in humans, although is technically demanding with respect to surgical skill and need for aseptic conditions. Nevertheless, an experienced researcher can achieve good reproducibility with minimal surgical artefact, and thus we consider DMM to be a robust model in our OA research programme. However, DMM does not reproduce the acute trauma-induced damage to surrounding soft tissue (including cartilage) that is observed in human sport-related injuries.^{20,21} PTOA is characterised by accelerated pathology post-injury, and there is a recognised subcohort of OA patients with symptoms limiting life-style at an earlier time point than normally seen. While this is likely to be a consequence of the synergistic interaction of

injury to multiple joint tissues, the exact mechanisms driving this accelerated disease progression are not fully understood. In the context of traumatic injury, altered joint loading and initial cartilage damage as a consequence of meniscal damage has been linked with OA development.²² Rabbit ACL rupture models involving blunt impact trauma are available to study PTOA.^{7,8,23} Whilst these models can imitate and reproduce multi-tissue damage similar to that of human knee joint impact traumas, they are limited in not being able to target and confine this trauma specifically to defined tissues within the joint in a reproducible fashion. To this end we have developed a novel dual-injury murine model specific for investigation of OA arising from simultaneous cartilage damage and joint destabilisation. Our DCS procedure now enables generation of a controlled multi-tissue injury murine model mimicking significant trauma to a healthy knee. The DCS model is thus highly relevant to human disease, offering significant potential in meeting a currently unmet scientific need for a model that more accurately represents the subcohort of young otherwise healthy individuals suffering accelerated PTOA resulting from sporting injuries. Such injuries involve simultaneous damage to various joint tissues, including ligaments, bone and cartilage. With this model we

Fig. 6. Increased pain-related behaviour correlates with osteophyte number and cartilage damage at day 14 post-surgery. Dynamic weight bearing measurements of the (A) ipsilateral (injured) paw and (B) front paw load for mice following DMM, cartilage damage or DCS surgery at 14 days post-surgery. (C) Correlation curves depicting significant correlation between front paw load and osteophyte number across the models. 95% confidence intervals are indicated by dotted lines. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; $n = 8$. DMM, DMM; CS, CS; DCS, DCS.

observed accelerated PTOA via combination of defined cartilage micro-lesions (Supplemental Fig. 1(D)) with altered loading due to destabilisation of the medial meniscus, allowing us to investigate mechanisms known to be key OA triggers in human disease.

Osteophyte formation is believed to be a response mechanism triggered by a loading imbalance within the joint, expanding the surface area of the tibial plateau to better support the alteration in biomechanical loading.^{24,25} We have previously shown DMM alone can induce osteophytogenesis as early as day seven post-surgery in C57BL/6 mice.¹⁸ This is consistent with the present study, in which we report the presence of small osteophytes, low in number, in the DMM model at day seven [Fig. 1(B) and (C)]. Few, small osteophytes

were also present in the CS model at day 7 [Fig. 1(A) and (B)]. However, the DCS model presented with quantifiably larger, and in most mice, more numerous osteophyte formation at day 7 [Fig. 1(A) and (B)]. These data would suggest dual trauma consisting of cartilage damage and joint destabilisation can accelerate the formation of osteophytes as early as 7 days post-injury. Previous studies have reported that secondary osteophyte growth is initiated by cartilage damage,^{26–28} however the factors influencing the formation and growth of osteophytes are poorly defined. Cartilage lesions have been associated with the formation of larger osteophytes,²⁹ supporting our day 14 findings of both cartilage damage and DCS models presenting with larger, more numerous osteophytes compared with the DMM model [Fig. 2(C) and (D)], where no initial cartilage damage was induced. This provides evidence that osteophytogenesis is accelerated by cartilage damage when combined with simultaneous joint loading imbalance. The specific site of cartilage damage may itself alter the type of pathologic outcome. Our study focussed on cartilage damage within the medial compartment however, there could be value in future studies focussing on the impact of cartilage damage on alternative sites (i.e., non-weight-bearing areas of cartilage) to determine how this affects pathologic outcome. Whilst the DCS model was developed to test a specific hypothesis, it has considerable potential to extend beyond OA, to investigation of osteophytogenesis in various pathological scenarios. Examples include ankylosing spondylitis and degenerative disk disease. Additionally, the study of osteophytogenesis could provide a controlled tool to investigate the initiation of endochondral ossification.

Another prominent feature of OA is the development of osteosclerosis in subchondral bone. When the cartilage becomes damaged there is an increased transfer in load to the subchondral bone,³⁰ as well as the release of inflammatory and osteoclast stimulation factors, which can lead to an increase in bone remodelling.^{31,32} Osteosclerosis was measured as an increase in bone volume (% BV/TV) in the medial subchondral region of the tibia. At both 7 and 14 days post-surgery, all disease model groups exhibited evident osteosclerosis in the loaded medial compartment of the joint, where the destabilisation and/or cartilage damage was induced. After the initial increase at day 7, osteosclerosis in the CS model remained relatively constant at 14 days, whereas both the DMM and DCS groups significantly increased, indicating altered biomechanical load plays a key role in the development of osteosclerosis. Furman *et al.* showed that intra-articular fractures led to subchondral bone thickening and sclerosis of the knee in C57BL/6 mice.³³

The observation that cartilage degradation is more extensive and progressive in the DCS model than either of the other models, suggests that interactions arising from the dual injury exacerbates cartilage breakdown. Trauma to the articular cartilage results in the activation of genes encoding for morphogens and the secretion of soluble inflammatory mediators into the joint cavity.^{34–37} The formation of microcracks and increased vascularisation associated with abnormal bone remodelling in joints during OA facilitate molecular transport between cartilage and bone⁹, therefore soluble inflammatory mediators present in the joint cavity as a result of cartilage damage and joint destabilisation may potentiate further cartilage destruction/bone remodelling, thus accelerating joint pathology in PTOA. Interestingly, we observed a significant correlation between cartilage damage and osteophyte number [Fig. 4(H)], raising the intriguing possibility that soluble factors secreted by the damaged cartilage may contribute to accelerated osteophytogenesis. Cartilage damage also exhibited a positive correlation with synovitis [Fig. 4(G)] suggesting a link with inflammatory factors.

While traditionally considered a 'wear and tear' disease, inflammation is increasingly recognised to have a role in

degenerative changes occurring during OA pathogenesis³⁸. Histological features consistent with synovitis have been observed in synovium from OA patients^{39–42} as well as expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines,^{41,42} and more recently we have reported considerable heterogeneity of various inflammatory indices in OA synovia.⁴³ Indeed knee arthroscopic studies of OA patients found synovial inflammation to be associated with OA structural severity,⁴⁴ whilst another study reported that serum C-reactive protein levels in early osteoarthritis predicted likely progressive disease.⁴⁵ C-reactive protein (CRP) also correlates significantly with disease joint count and radiographic score in OA.⁴⁶ Whilst the DMM model does recapitulate many of the characteristic features of OA, it is generally considered a non-inflammatory model.⁴⁷ Our study, however, supported by previous findings,¹⁶ detected histologically the presence of synovitis at 14 days post-surgery. Nevertheless, given the low-level nature of this synovitis, DMM is not the model of choice for investigation of inflammation in OA joints. While the MIA model evokes joint inflammation,⁴⁸ this inflammatory response is not initiated in a manner resembling that of OA. Our DCS model yielded a significant and consistently higher level of synovitis than seen in either the DMM or CS models and, similarly to cartilage degradation, synovitis was positively correlated with increased osteophyte number [Fig. 4]. Thus DCS presents value in enabling mechanistic interrogation of the putative contribution of synovitis to OA pathogenesis.

Pain is one of the most common and physically limiting symptoms of OA, however the origin of this pain is still poorly understood. DWB presents a behavioural non-invasive means of assessing pain, although other factors (e.g., mechanical impediment) may influence the observed changes. Ipsilateral (injured) hind paw and front paw loading were analysed. There was a significant decrease in injured hind paw load with a corresponding increase in load on the front paws in the DCS model compared with all other groups [Fig. 6(A) and (B)], suggesting the combination of cartilage damage and DMM enhances pain-associated pathology. There have been conflicting studies regarding the relationship between pain and osteophytes in OA. One previous study presented a significant correlation between knee joint pain in OA patients with osteophytes present in the medial tibial condyle.⁴⁹ However, more recently, Sengupta *et al.* challenged this finding by reporting that the presence of high-signal osteophytes detected on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) were not associated with pain or pain severity.⁵⁰ Our data demonstrates a significant and strong positive correlation between osteophyte number and front paw load at 14 days post-surgery [Fig. 6(C)]. Synovitis is known to lead to heightened pain sensitivity in knee OA⁵¹ and we therefore elected to further explore this finding in relation to pain-associated behaviour in the DCS model. We did not observe a significant correlation between front paw load and synovitis or an increase in cartilage degradation. The association of osteophytogenesis, cartilage damage, synovitis and pain implicates a causal relationship, and this merits future research to define the nature of any such relationships; this may help identify possible molecular mechanisms driving osteophyte formation, as well as joint pain.

We conclude that the concomitant joint instability and cartilage injury that typify knee joint traumatic injury predispose to accelerated OA progression. To establish this we developed and validated a murine model of acute trauma involving simultaneous controlled damage to multiple joint tissues. This robustly mimicked the accelerated OA pathogenesis observed in otherwise normal individuals with PTOA, as characterised by osteosclerosis and (compared with DMM) enhanced cartilage degradation, synovial inflammation, osteophytogenesis and pain. Importantly, this model also provides a valuable research tool for investigating osteophytogenesis in various contexts, as the DCS model generates an

accelerated and more extensive formation of osteophytes at an early time-point. The reproducible synovitis associated with this model also presents means to elucidate the role of synovitis in OA pathology. Similarly, the enhanced pain-related behaviour in DCS provides a robust model for *in vivo* investigation of joint pain.

Author contributions

Conceived and designed the experiments: KM, CH, JCL, CSG. Performed the experiments: KM, CH, LD. Analysed the data: KM, CH, LD, GL, RjvTH, JCL, CSG.; wrote manuscript: KM, CH, JCL, CSG.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Supplementary data

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Rheumatic Disease: Protease-Activated Receptor-2 in Synovial Joint Pathobiology

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Protease-activated receptor-2 (PAR2) is one member of a small family of transmembrane, G-protein-coupled receptors. These receptors are activated *via* cleavage of their N terminus by serine proteases (e.g., trypsin), unveiling an N terminus tethered ligand which binds to the second extracellular loop of the receptor. Increasing evidence has emerged identifying key pathophysiological roles for PAR2 in both rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and osteoarthritis (OA). Importantly, this includes both pro-inflammatory and destructive roles. For example, in murine models of RA, the associated synovitis, cartilage degradation, and subsequent bone erosion are all significantly reduced in the absence of PAR2. Similarly, in experimental models of OA, PAR2 disruption confers protection against cartilage degradation, subchondral bone osteosclerosis, and osteophyte formation. This review focuses on the role of PAR2 in rheumatic disease and its potential as an important therapeutic target for treating pain and joint degradation.

Keywords: protease-activated receptor-2, rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, bone, cartilage, synovium

PROTEASE-ACTIVATED RECEPTOR-2 (PAR2)

Protease-activated receptors (PARs) 1–4 are a family of transmembrane, G-protein-coupled receptors. These receptors lack a conventional soluble ligand. Instead they are activated by serine protease-mediated cleavage of their N terminus, unveiling a “tethered ligand” which can then bind the second extracellular loop. Once activated, the continued interaction between the receptor and its tethered ligand means it cannot be subsequently reactivated. Instead, PARs are internalized and degraded post-activation. PARs 1, 3, and 4 are primarily cleaved by thrombin (1) and play important roles in vascular physiology, the coagulation pathway and the immune system. PAR2, in contrast, is activated by a number of serine proteases such as trypsin (2), mast cell trypsinase (3), neutrophil proteinase 3 (4), and matriptase (5), many of which are generated and released during tissue injury and/or inflammation. In the last decade a strong link has emerged between PAR2 and the innate and adaptive immune responses (6), and the stromal compartment. Furthermore, given the previously established role for PAR2 in nociception (7), there is now substantial evidence to support the therapeutic targeting of this receptor to combat pain as well as inflammation and joint destruction and in the rheumatic diseases. Notably, while there are no specific and potent PAR2 antagonists in clinical trials, a recent publication of the crystal structure of PAR2 (8) will accelerate design and availability of such compounds for future trials in various diseases.

RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS (RA)

The arthritides are a heterogeneous group of joint diseases with the common endpoint of structural joint degradation; the most overtly inflammatory of these is RA. This chronic, autoimmune disorder affects an estimated 1% of the world population (9). It is characterized by swelling, pain, and loss of mobility, and manifests as a result of a break in immune tolerance toward antigens associated with articular joints in genetically susceptible individuals. This leads to an adaptive driven immune response to self-antigens, such as IgG (rheumatoid factor) or posttranslationally modified proteins (citrullinated protein). The RA inflammatory synovial infiltrate consists of auto-reactive B and T cells, inflammatory monocytes, and mast cells, which together produce a network of pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., TNF- α and IL-6) (10), chemokines (e.g., CCL2 and CXCL8), and proteases, contributing to a hypoxic and inflammatory environment. The synovial membrane expands due to reduced apoptosis, increased inflammatory mediators (e.g., IL-6), and catabolic protease production by fibroblast-like synoviocytes (FLS). This aggressive phenotype is maintained (11) through epigenetic imprinting, creating an almost "transformed" synovial membrane (12). FLS hyperplasia creates structural damage due to thickening of the synovial membrane, creating an invasive pannus that can erode neighboring tissue. Structural damage is also caused by the immune cell infiltrates invading the juxta-articular bone and calcified cartilage, led by excessive osteoclast activity (derived from infiltrating myeloid cells, e.g., monocytes) and TNF- α -driven mechanisms (13). Pathogenic mechanisms driving structural joint changes in RA are summarized in **Figure 1**.

Synovium

The first "proof of concept" that PAR2 has a direct role in chronic inflammatory arthritis was demonstrated by Ferrell et al. using an adjuvant-induced monoarthritis model in wild-type (WT), PAR2 deficient homozygote (*Par2*^{-/-}) and PAR2 heterozygote (*Par2*^{+/-}) mice. This innate immune-mediated arthritis model revealed almost complete ablation of synovitis in *Par2*^{-/-} compared with WT mice, with heterozygotes demonstrating an intermediate phenotype (14). The immunological role of PAR2 in murine RA models was further investigated *in vivo* using the gold standard model of inflammatory RA, collagen-induced arthritis (CIA) in both DBA/1 and C57Bl/6J mice. Arthritis was significantly reduced following therapeutic treatment with PAR2 inhibitors (both small-molecule antagonist ENMD-1068 and SAM-11 monoclonal antibody) (15). This was associated with an altered immune response in secondary lymphoid tissue, whereby PAR2 inhibition significantly reduced IL-17 and IFN- γ levels and had a minor impact on TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-12, CCL3, and GM-CSF expression (15). Furthermore, anti-type II collagen antibodies were also significantly reduced after PAR2 inhibition. This compelling evidence supports the immunological role of PAR2 in inflammatory joint disease, pinpointing reductions in key synovitis-associated cytokines, and links PAR2 to the induction of adaptive antibody responses. The upstream ability of PAR2 to modulate multiple cytokine pathways potentially represents an over-arching approach to target multiple immunopathological

pathways. It is therefore interesting to speculate that PAR2-mediated therapeutic strategies could provide an alternative to those currently focused on targeting these pathways (i.e., JAK inhibitors).

Subsequent translational studies implicated a pathogenic role for PAR2 in the context of human RA. Notably, the level of PAR2 transcript and protein was significantly increased in both synovial tissue biopsies and isolated FLS from RA synovium when compared with osteoarthritis (OA) patients (16). An inflammatory role for PAR2 in the synovia was further implicated by the correlation of PAR2 expression in RA patients with the extent of synovial pathology (16). To understand the underlying mechanism, studies have been conducted to dissect the pathways influenced by PAR2 activation in cells associated with RA synovial infiltrates. Crilly and colleagues investigated the cell surface expression of PAR2 on CD14⁺ circulating monocytes (which likely migrate into the inflamed joint and differentiate to macrophages or osteoclasts) during both RA remission and flare (17). These studies demonstrated that the expression of PAR2 on patient monocytes correlated with classic biomarkers of disease flare such as erythrocyte sedimentation rate and C reactive protein levels. Importantly, the elevated levels of PAR2 surface expression in CD14⁺ monocytes was significantly reduced in patients receiving conventional DMARDs (17, 18). This direct correlation between receptor expression and disease activity supports a role for PAR2 in driving inflammatory disease. Moreover, at a functional level, the activation of PAR2 on human monocyte *in vitro* derived macrophages, via the agonist peptide SLIGKV, fundamentally altered the cellular cytoskeleton (elongated spindle-like appearance) and enhanced TNF- α production, both in the presence or absence of LPS stimulation (19). This confirms that enhanced PAR2 expression on monocytes (17) translates to a pro-inflammatory phenotype. However, the potential differential expression of PAR2 or the functional role of the receptor in different monocyte subpopulations remains to be elucidated. Thus far the PAR2 expression on RA monocyte subsets has been limited to analysis of CD14⁺ monocytes. Interrogation of PAR2 expression in the full monocyte compartment in RA, including classical monocytes (CD14⁺CD16⁻, responsible for higher cytokine production and inflammation), intermediate monocytes (CD14⁺CD16⁺) and non-classical monocytes (CD14⁺CD16⁺, patrolling) may provide further insights into the inflammatory role of this receptor (20).

In summation, overall increased PAR2 expression is seen across multiple cell types of the RA synovium. Assessment of PAR2 activity both *in vivo* and *in vitro* indicates that this pathway may at least in part be responsible for the disease associated activity of these cell types. Therefore, PAR2 may be dysregulated in cells of the innate immune system and stromal FLS and thus represent a therapeutically tractable pathway in RA.

Cartilage

The main contributor to cartilage degradation in RA is a hyperplastic synovium (21). The protein-binding properties of cartilage becomes altered due to decreased lubricin expression and loss of other protective mechanisms within the synovium (22). This leads to FLS adhesion and invasion of the bone and cartilage,

FIGURE 1 | Continued

FIGURE 1 | Arthritic joint changes and the pathogenic role of protease-activated receptor-2 (PAR2). **(A)** Schematic representation of a normal healthy joint, highlighting the various joint tissues, cell types residing within, and the expression of PAR2 in the healthy joint. **(B)** A schematic representation of a rheumatoid arthritis-affected joint, highlighting characteristic changes including: synovitis, degradation of the articular cartilage; bone erosion and increased inflammatory factors. PAR2 expression is also highlighted in pathogenic areas known to be influenced by PAR2 from animal studies or *in vitro* cell work. Including, increase in PAR2 expression in monocytes, macrophages, and fibroblast-like synoviocytes, and contributing to monocyte IL-6 production, macrophage cytokine production, autoantibody production, bone erosion, and cartilage destruction. **(C)** Schematic representation of an osteoarthritis (OA)-affected joint, highlighting characteristic changes including: synovitis; degradation of the articular cartilage; osteophyte formation; subchondral bone sclerosis and pannus formation. PAR2 expression is also highlighted in cells/tissues and pathogenic outcomes known to be influenced by PAR2 from animal studies or *in vitro* cell work. Increased levels of PAR2 have been found in OA chondrocytes, fibroblasts, and macrophages, with PAR2 known to play a role in osteophyte formation, cartilage degradation (through catabolic protease production), and inflammation.

resulting in the formation of pannus. Metalloproteinases (MMPs) are released from the chondrocytes and synovium, contributing to subsequent cartilage degradation. FLS predominantly release MMP-14 that also degrades the cartilage matrix (23). Chondrocytes also express a disintegrin and MMP with thrombospondin motifs 5 (ADAMTS 5), which has the ability to degrade aggrecan (ECM component) (24), as well as MMP-1; the major collagenase associated with RA (25). Moreover, the secretion of IL-1 β within the synovial environment, which drives catabolic activity within chondrocytes, also upregulates PAR2 on chondrocytes and can in turn be regulated by PAR2 activation (16).

Using the adjuvant-induced arthritis model to mimic chronic inflammatory arthritis in mice, the absence of PAR2 conferred protection against cartilage damage. By comparison, cartilage was entirely replaced by pannus in WT mice, with associated erosion of the cortical bone, while *Par2*^{-/-} mice exhibited an intermediate level of protection against cartilage damage (14). The ability of PAR2 to regulate adaptive immune pathways potentially responsible for driving cartilage damage in RA was explored in the CIA model. Histological analysis of the paws revealed that *Par2*^{-/-} mice had significantly lower cartilage damage than WT controls (15), suggesting that this protection observed in *Par2*^{-/-} mice was related to the capacity of PAR2 to drive the release of cytokines, including IL-1 β , known to induce degradation of cartilage and ECM components in this inflammatory arthritis model. While PAR2 drives cartilage damage in inflammatory arthritis, the pathogenic mechanism is poorly understood. Unanswered questions include whether PAR2 can modulate the erosive environment leading to cartilage damage, or whether its activation undermines chondrocyte biology/viability. Moreover, translational studies are required to determine if this pathogenic role is relevant in human RA.

Bone

Dysregulation of the homeostatic bone remodeling process is recognized to be a key feature of RA. This is associated with localized bone erosion at the site of inflammation, and systemic bone loss, that can contribute to an increased risk of fracture (26, 27). The high prevalence of synovial pro-inflammatory factors promotes osteoclastogenic activity resulting in focal bone erosions, especially at the interface of bone and pannus (28). In addition, the balance of bone formation and resorption is further perturbed in these patients because the inflammatory environment, including IL-1 β and IL-6 inhibit the migration and activity of the bone forming osteoblasts (29, 30). The role of PAR2 in bone erosion in inflammatory disease remains unclear, and

current literature regarding PAR2 in osteoclasts is conflicting. Studies have shown PAR2 is expressed in osteoblasts (31) and CD14⁺ monocytes (17), the latter being osteoclast precursors. Another study explored PAR2-mediated bone functions, in a bone marrow-derived coculture system; addition of soluble factors resulted in osteoblast differentiation, subsequently promoting osteoclastogenesis. When PAR2 activating peptides were included in this system, the number of tartrate-resistant acid phosphatase (TRAP) positive osteoclasts decreased. However, when osteoclasts were cultured alone (without osteoblasts), PAR2 activation had no effect. This suggests PAR2 activation inhibited osteoclastogenesis *in vitro* via an osteoblast-mediated mechanism, and it was proposed that this mechanism may protect bone from uncontrolled resorption (32). In contrast, a study of skeletal development in *Par2*^{-/-} mice revealed an increase in total bone volume and a deficit in the area of bone associated with osteoclasts. Moreover, *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis assays demonstrated that osteoclasts derived from precursors lacking PAR2 had reduced levels of TRAP (33). While conflicting, these studies do indicate that PAR2 could play a fundamental role in the differentiation of bone precursor cells into their mature forms, and therefore bone remodeling in RA may be influenced via PAR2 modulation.

OSTEOARTHRITIS

As the most prevalent musculoskeletal disease globally (34), OA is a chronic debilitating condition affecting an estimated 100 million Europeans. It has a dramatic impact on quality of life (35), through associated pain, swelling of the joint and lack of mobility/loss of normal joint function. In the absence of effective disease modifying therapies, analgesia, and ultimately arthroplasty remain the only real options for most patients. In the UK, between 2007 and 2008 over 140,000 primary hip and knee replacements were performed, with an addition of more than 10,000 revision arthroplasties. This represents an NHS cost burden in excess of £1 billion per year (36). Risk factors linked to OA include gender, obesity, genetic factors, joint injury and advancing age, with approximately 80% of the population >65 years old showing radiological evidence of OA (37). Depending on the stage of disease, an OA joint can exhibit various characteristics such as degradation of the articular cartilage, osteophyte formation (bony outgrowths), subchondral bone sclerosis, pannus formation, and inflammation of the synovial membrane (synovitis) (Figure 1C). OA is inherently heterogeneous: there is substantial inter-patient variability in clinical features, biochemical characteristics and

treatment responses. This, together with the subtle onset of OA and lack of definitive biomarkers, makes early diagnosis extremely challenging. What was once considered a degenerative “wear and tear” disease is now recognized as a complex disorder involving various molecular pathways and inflammatory mediators (38). The pathogenic mechanisms of this complex disease are still not fully understood, and accordingly this unmet clinical need is a major focus of research.

Synovium

Unlike RA, there are no systemic signs of inflammation or evidence of neutrophils within OA synovial fluid. There is, however, evidence of inflammatory (B and T cell) infiltrate into the synovium (39), together with increased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β and TNF- α) and catabolic proteases (e.g., MMPs). These are thought to be instrumental in chondrocyte mediated cartilage destruction.

Scoring of synovial thickness and monocyte infiltrates in OA demonstrated that OA synovitis correlates with levels of PAR2 expression in synovial tissue (40). While synovitis scores were reduced in OA compared with RA, increased PAR2 levels were directly associated with inflammatory conditions across all patient groups. These studies also demonstrated that a PAR2 antagonist, ENMD-1068, dose-dependently inhibited TNF- α production from OA synovial explant cultures. Increased PAR2 expression in OA synovia would therefore appear to be not merely a passive marker of inflammation, but an active contributor to pro-inflammatory cytokine production.

Cartilage

Chondrocytes are the primary source of enzymes such as MMPs responsible for the metabolism of the cartilage matrix in OA (41). Pro-inflammatory cytokines synthesized and released by both chondrocytes and the synovial membrane are important in the development and progression of OA as they play a central role in inducing cartilage catabolic processes (42). MMPs are considered crucial in cartilage catabolism, as they collectively have the ability to degrade all components of the ECM (43).

Protease-activated receptor-2 transcript is sevenfold higher in chondrocytes isolated from the cartilage of OA patients compared with control femoral fracture patients who have no evidence of arthropathy (44). Moreover, *in vitro* culture and subsequent passage of chondrocytes demonstrated that only in OA-derived samples is there maintenance of PAR2 protein. This indicates potential epigenetic alterations in these cells enabling them to retain PAR2 expression (44).

Selective activation of PAR2 in chondrocytes mediates a stress-activated protein kinases (SAPK)/p38 and extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 signaling cascade, which results in the generation of MMP-1, MMP-13 and cyclooxygenase 2 (45). In OA and RA, MMP-1 and -13 and ADAMTS aggrecanases are strongly associated with the degradation of collagen and aggrecan (46), the main components of the ECM. Moreover, pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and TNF α have been shown to upregulate PAR2 expression in OA chondrocytes (44), and PAR2 appears to regulate the synovial release of IL-1 β , a chondrocyte catabolin (16, 47). These findings collectively implicate

a potential auto-feedback loop between PAR2, inflammation and cartilage destruction.

In the murine destabilization of the medial meniscus (DMM) model, PAR2 has been identified as a critical checkpoint in the pathogenesis of experimental OA (48). *Par2*^{-/-} mice exhibit substantially less cartilage damage at 4 weeks' post DMM than WT littermates (48), a key finding confirmed in a later study (49), and across several groups (50, 51). Notably, 8 weeks' post DMM, *Par2*^{-/-} mice retain cartilage integrity while WT mice have more pronounced joint destruction (48). Using either a PAR2 agonist or monoclonal antibody specifically targeting the PAR2 protease cleavage site, inhibition of PAR2 in WT mice was observed to be as equally effective as gene deletion in curtailing OA progression *in vivo* (48), but only in early (1 week) stages of disease.

To further test the hypothesis that PAR2 drives cartilage damage in the DMM model (48, 50, 51), additional experiments using a viral vector containing human PAR2 (*hPar2*) showed that intraarticular injection of *hPar2* in *Par2*^{-/-} mice restored the pathogenic phenotype (49). While Jackson et al. demonstrated a significant correlation between cartilage damage and subchondral bone sclerosis (51), Huesa et al. demonstrated cartilage damage but no significant difference in subchondral bone sclerosis in the *hPar2*-transfected *Par2*^{-/-} mice compared with vector controls (49). The authors concluded that, in the DMM model, even in the absence of subchondral bone sclerosis, cartilage damage is mediated *via* PAR2. However, it should be appreciated that subtle differences in PAR2-dependent pathological features in these studies may reflect divergence of methodologies or temporal analyses employed by these groups. In summation, PAR2 activity, through the stimulation of MMPs and various other proteases appears to promote cartilage degradation. PAR2 deficiency may confer protection against cartilage erosion *via* inhibition of MMP production and/or alteration of chondrocyte phenotype. Many questions remain with regard to the role of PAR2 in chondrocyte biology and how it affects OA etiology. Thus future studies should consider using cartilage-specific *Par2*^{-/-} animals.

Bone

Bone pathology in OA differs from RA. In addition to bone loss in the metaphysis, OA is characterized by osteosclerosis (hardening and increased density of subchondral bone) (52) and formation of osteophytes along the joint margins (53).

Protease-activated receptor-2 has recently been reported to play an essential role in osteophyte formation during DMM progression: although osteophytes are detectable in both WT and *Par2*^{-/-} mice, the quantity, size, and growth of osteophytes over time is significantly reduced in *Par2*^{-/-} animals. The OA phenotype was subsequently “rescued” *via* intraarticular *Par2* adenovirus transfection (49), which restored the pathogenic phenotype observed in WT animals. This appears to contradict a previous study which found no significant gross difference in osteophyte formation between WT and *Par2*^{-/-} (51). However, the difference in techniques adopted in these studies (microcomputed tomography versus histology, respectively) may explain the conflicting results as the former technique offers far more quantitative measurement of osteophyte changes such as volume, density, and arboreal structure. While these studies provide important “proof

of concept" that PAR2 modulates the pathogenic bone phenotype found in murine OA models, *in vitro* studies on human osteoclasts and stroma are still needed to dissect the mechanisms involved, as well as translating these findings to human OA. This is an important future direction, since PAR2 inhibition may offer protection against osteophytogenesis in OA patients.

CONCLUSION

Arthritis studies have identified the cell types expressing PAR2, shown the receptor is up regulated and provided proof of concept that PAR2 inhibition offers therapeutic protection. PAR2 may therefore present a complete novel target that merits research focus since there remains an urgent need for targeted disease modifying agents in both RA and OA. Recent advances in RA biological treatments against specific cytokines and immune cells have not fulfilled their early promise, are expensive, and require an injection-based delivery system. In OA, disease modifying agents are virtually non-existent and current treatment options are severely limited.

Continuing research is required to achieve the ultimate therapeutic ambition of identifying new targets with high disease

specificity and good accessibility by manageable drug delivery. While PAR2 has been recognized as a potential target with significant therapeutic value, advance in this area has been severely limited by the current lack of effective small-molecule PAR2 antagonists. Given the burgeoning problem of arthritis with an ever aging population, the recent and timely publication of the crystal structure of PAR2 (8) presents a landmark step in progressing pharmaceutical research by accelerating development of such agents for future clinical studies.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The joint first authors (KM and SM) prepared the first draft of the review, and this was then revised and finalized with input from all authors (CH, LD, GL, AC, LH, WF, JL, and CG).

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Conflict of Interest Statement: CG has received consulting fees from AstraZeneca (more than \$10,000). LH is an employee of AstraZeneca. All other authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix IV

Publications (abstracts)

PAR2 ACCELERATES OSTEOARTHRITIS-LIKE JOINT CHANGES IN A MURINE MODEL OF POST-TRAUMATIC OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Background Post-traumatic osteoarthritis (PTOA) is associated with articular cartilage damage and represents a major clinical challenge due to the poor regenerative capability of cartilage. We have recently developed a novel and robust dual injury murine model of PTOA, which combines destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) and cartilage scratch¹. This model results in accelerated OA-like symptoms including enhanced osteophytogenesis. Prior studies in the DMM model have demonstrated that absence of proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) in mice results in significant protection from early OA-like symptoms^{2,3}.

Objectives To investigate if the absence of PAR2 confers protection in a dual injury PTOA murine model.

Methods PTOA was induced in both male C57BL/6 wild-type (WT) and PAR2^{-/-} mice, via combined destabilisation of the medial meniscus and cartilage scratch (DCS). Twenty-eight days post-surgery, osteophytogenesis and bone changes were monitored using microcomputed tomography. Dynamic weight bearing was assessed as an indirect measurement of pain at day 14.

Results Evaluation of the presence and number of osteophyte revealed no significant differences between WT and PAR2^{-/-} mice at day 28. However, quantification of osteophytes revealed that PAR2^{-/-} mice had significantly smaller osteophytes (p=0.006) with less mineralised bone (p=0.003). Moreover, analysis of metaphyseal trabecular bone on the operated leg showed a significant decrease in% bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) (p=0.025). Assessment of pain-related behaviour, using dynamic weight bearing at day 14, demonstrated that PAR2^{-/-} mice exerted less load on their front paws.

Conclusion The findings in this study show that PAR2 plays a role in accelerated OA-like symptoms (i.e., osteophyte formation) in a dual injury model of OA, where both destabilisation of the medial meniscus and cartilage damage drive disease pathology. Furthermore, the loss of PAR2 decreases pain behaviour suggesting that PAR2 is involved in pain sensing. Taken together, these results support the future exploration of PAR2 as a therapeutic target for PTOA.

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ACCELERATED OSTEOARTHRITIC-LIKE SYMPTOMS IN A NOVEL DUAL INJURY MODEL COMBINING DESTABILISATION OF THE MEDIAL MENISCUS AND CARTILAGE DAMAGE.

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Osteoarthritis (OA) is associated with articular cartilage damage. It is assumed OA pathogenesis can be initiated via an isolated injury, or an accumulation of joint damage over time. OA represents a major clinical challenge due to the poor regenerative capability of cartilage. Several murine models are used to study OA (e.g. destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM)), however, they do not combine simultaneous joint destabilisation with cartilage damage. The principle aim of this study was to investigate if combining DMM and cartilage damage could accelerate the onset of OA-like symptoms.

OA was induced in C57BL/6 mice via (a) transection of the medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM), (b) microblade scratches of articular cartilage (cartilage damage) or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS). Seven and 14 days post-surgery, inflammation, cartilage degradation and bone changes were monitored using histology and microcomputed tomography. Dynamic weight bearing was assessed as an indirect measurement of pain at 14 days.

Osteophytes were observed in all groups at days 7 and 14 post-surgery. When compared with DMM and cartilage damage models, osteophytes were visually larger and more numerous in the DCS model. Osteophyte total bone volume (BV) was greater at day 14 in both cartilage damage and DCS models; these osteophytes also encompassed a larger surface area of subchondral bone (14.12 ± 0.31 versus 12.4 ± 0.62 , 12.68 ± 0.54 , $p < 0.01$ respectively). With regard to other bone changes, at day 7 there was no detectable increase in BV and osteosclerosis was absent, but by day 14 osteosclerosis was detectable in both DMM and DCS models. Assessment of cartilage at day 14, revealed that there was a significant increase in damage in the DCS model when compared with DMM and cartilage damage models ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, there was a significant increase in synovitis in the DCS model compared with the cartilage scratch model ($p < 0.05$). In mice that underwent DCS surgery there was significant increase in front paw load compared with the other models. At day 14 a positive correlation was observed between osteophyte number and front paw load ($r = 0.69$, $p = 0.003$).

The combination of DMM and cartilage damage provides a robust and reproducible model for OA-associated joint changes, suggesting this novel dual injury model not only accelerates osteophytogenesis, but also includes features of OA-related pain; arguably one of the most problematic and physically limiting symptoms of OA.

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A COMBINED MODEL OF DESTABILISATION OF THE MEDIAL MENISCUS AND CARTILAGE DAMAGE ACCELERATES OSTEOPHYTOGENESIS IN OSTEOARTHRITIS.

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Purpose Injuries involving damage to the articular cartilage can be both physically limiting and painful. Articular cartilage injuries can result from an isolated injury, or in combination with other joint damage. Cartilage has a poor intrinsic regenerative capability, and therefore once damaged, presents a major clinical challenge. Joint injury is known to be a well-established precursor for the development of the osteoarthritis (OA). Pain is one of the most common, and arguably physically limiting, symptoms of OA. However, the origin of pain in OA is poorly understood. Several murine models have been used to study OA (e.g. destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) and anterior cruciate ligament transection (ACLT)). However neither of these models combines simultaneous cartilage injury with joint destabilisation. Therefore, the principle aim of this study was to investigate if the combination of cartilage damage and DMM accelerates the onset of OA-like symptoms when compared with DMM and cartilage damage alone.

Methods Three models of OA-like joint instability and damage were induced in wild-type (WT) mice. For biomechanical instability, DMM surgery induced medial compartment OA following transection of the medial meniscotibial ligament. For cartilage damage, a micro precision blade was used to make controlled "scratches" (Scratch model) on the cartilage of the tibia under the femoral medial condyle. To combine biomechanical instability with cartilage damage, both DMM and cartilage scratch (Combined model) was performed. Microcomputed tomography (μ CT) was used to monitor bone changes, and as an indirect measurement of pain, dynamic weight bearing was assessed in mice 14 days after surgery.

Results At 14 days post-surgery, osteophytes are present in all 3 groups. However, between groups, osteophytes differed in number, appearance, and bone volume. In DMM, 6/8 mice developed protruding osteophytes with an arboreal structure (the initial phase of osteophyte formation). Osteophytes were present in all mice undergoing cartilage scratch surgery, however, they had a larger more calcified appearance, suggesting cartilage could play a role in the acceleration of OA osteophyte pathology. 8/8 WT mice in the Combined model were observed to exhibit 2 or more large, protruding, calcified osteophytes. Osteophytes observed in this Combined model encompassed a larger area of the subchondral bone when compared with DMM or Scratch model alone (14.12 ± 0.31 versus 12.4 ± 0.62 , 12.68 ± 0.54 , $p < 0.01$). Compared to the osteophytes in the DMM model, it is clear that addition of cartilage damage accelerates the calcification of osteophytes. μ CT analysis of the subchondral bone shows both DMM, and Combined models have an increase in subchondral osteosclerosis compared to cartilage damage alone. Further, analysis of subchondral trabecular bone in the Combined model exhibited a significantly higher bone volume over tissue volume compared with the other models used in this study ($p = 0.0017$, two-way ANOVA). Using dynamic weight bearing 14 days post-surgery to assess OA-related pain, we found the Combined model group have a significant increase in load on their front paws when compared with the other 2 groups, suggesting an increase in OA-like pain.

Conclusion OA is a multi-factorial disease encompassing various different tissues within the joint. Accordingly, a Combined model of OA as presented here allows a more accurate representation of human OA. This study concludes that combining DMM with cartilage damage provides a more robust and reproducible model for OA due to the increased osteophytogenesis. This model also incorporates OA-related pain, which is arguably one of the most problematic and physically limiting symptoms of OA.

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Appendix V

Presentations

Cutting Edge Osteoarthritis Meeting. Oxford University, England. June 2019. Oral Presentation.

Loss of PAR2 confers protection against OA-like joint changes in a model of murine Post-traumatic osteoarthritis.

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Proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) plays a significant role in the early OA-like pathology observed in the destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) murine model. Notably, PAR2^{-/-} mice do not display DMM-induced osteophytogenesis. Recently, we developed a novel and robust dual injury murine model of Post-traumatic OA (PTOA), which combines destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM) and cartilage scratch. This model results in accelerated OA-like symptoms including enhanced osteophytogenesis. Here we investigated whether the absence of PAR2 continues to confer protection in this new dual injury PTOA murine model.

PTOA was induced in both male C57BL/6 wild-type (WT) and PAR2^{-/-} mice, via combined destabilisation of the medial meniscus and cartilage scratch (DCS). Twenty-eight days post-surgery, osteophytogenesis, bone and cartilage changes were monitored using microcomputed tomography and histology. As an indirect measurement of pain, dynamic weight bearing (DWB) was assessed at day 14.

Evaluation of joint pathology at day 28, showed that there was no significant difference in the presence and number of osteophytes between WT and PAR2^{-/-} mice. However, quantification of osteophytes revealed significantly smaller osteophytes (p=0.006) with less mineralised bone (p=0.003) in PAR2^{-/-} mice. Furthermore, analysis of metaphyseal trabecular bone on the operated leg showed a significant decrease in % bone volume/tissue volume (BV/TV) (p=0.025). Histological assessment of cartilage damage showed that in PAR2^{-/-} mice there was no progression of pathology between day 14 and 28 when compared to WT. Finally, assessment of pain-related behaviour, using dynamic weight bearing at day 14, demonstrated that PAR2^{-/-} mice do not shift their weight to the front paw to compensate for PTOA-driven pathology.

The results of this study demonstrate that PAR2 plays a role in accelerated osteophytogenesis, and other OA-like symptoms, in a murine model of PTOA. Furthermore, the loss of PAR2 decreases pain behaviour suggesting that PAR2 is involved in pain sensing. Taken together, these findings support the future exploration of PAR2 as a therapeutic target for PTOA.

American Society for Bone and Mineral Research (ASBMR) Annual Meeting. Montreal, Canada.
October 2018. Poster Presentation.

**Abstract printed above (appendix III, page 135)

Osteoarthritis Research Society International (OARSI) World Congress Conference. Liverpool, England. April 2018. Poster presentation.

**Abstract printed above (appendix III, page 136)

Glasgow Orthopaedic Research Initiative Conference (GLORI). Glasgow, Scotland. February 2018.
Poster presentation.

A novel dual injury osteoarthritis (OA) model that combines destabilisation of the medial meniscus and cartilage damage leads to accelerated osteophytogenesis.

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Introduction: Osteoarthritis is associated with articular cartilage damage. While it is not known how disease pathogenesis is initiated, it is assumed that it can be via an isolated injury, or a combination of joint damage over time. Given the fact cartilage has poor regenerative capability, OA represents a major clinical challenge. Several murine models are used to study OA (e.g. destabilisation of the medial meniscus (DMM)), however do not combine simultaneous cartilage injury with joint destabilisation. The principle aim of this study was to investigate if combining cartilage damage and DMM accelerates the onset of OA-like symptoms.

Methods: OA was induced in mice via (a) transection of the medial meniscotibial ligament (DMM), (b) microblade scratches of articular cartilage (cartilage damage) or (c) combined DMM and cartilage scratch (DCS). Fourteen days post-surgery, dynamic weight bearing was assessed as an indirect measurement of pain, and microcomputed tomography (μ CT) was used to monitor bone changes.

Results: Osteophytes were present in all groups post-surgery. However, between groups there were observable differences in number, appearance, and bone volume (Fig. 1). Osteophytes in the DCS model encompassed a larger area of subchondral bone compared with DMM or cartilage scratch models (14.12 ± 0.31 versus 12.4 ± 0.62 , 12.68 ± 0.54 , $p < 0.01$ respectively). In DMM 6/8 mice developed protruding osteophytes with an arboreal-like structure. Osteophytes were present in all mice that underwent cartilage scratch surgery, and had a larger more calcified appearance. In the DCS model, all mice exhibited ≥ 2 large, protruding, calcified osteophytes. Finally, mice in the DCS model demonstrated a significant increase in front paw load compared with the other models, suggesting an increase in OA-like pain.

Figure 1. Osteophytes differ in number, appearance and bone volume between groups. (A) DMM model exhibits and arboreal osteophyte structure. **(B)** Cartilage scratch models display osteophytes with a larger, more calcified appearance. **(C)** DCS models present with ≥ 2 large, protruding, calcified osteophytes.

Conclusion: Combining DMM with cartilage damage provides a robust and reproducible model for OA-associated osteophytogenesis. This model also incorporates OA-related pain, arguably one of the most problematic and physically limiting symptoms of OA.

European Calcified Tissue Society Annual PhD Training Course. Paris, France. July 2017. Oral presentation. "Dissecting the role of PAR2 in the osteoarthritic joint"

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